

WP1 - Strengthening AF and carbon farming policies: tools for policymakers

Deliverable 1.5: Policies and MRV methods for carbon farming in the voluntary and statutory sectors.

Project name	DigitAF (101059794)
Work-package	1: Strengthening agroforestry and carbon farming policies: tools for policymakers
Deliverable	Deliverable 1.5: Policies and MRV models for carbon farming in the voluntary and statutory sectors
Publication date	31/3/2026
Authors	Beatrice Croce (ELO), Gerry Lawson (EURAF), Michael den Herder (EFI), Ermias Betemariam (ICRAF), Paul J Burgess (CRAN), Waas Thissen (Louis Bolk Institute), Marie Gosme (INRAE)
Contact	beatrice.croce@elo.org
Approved	Marie Gosme

DigitAF project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement N°101059794. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or of the European Research Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them

Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
A. Strategic Context and Project Vision	5
B. The EU Regulatory Landscape: LULUCF, CAP, and CRCF	5
C. Technical MRV Methodologies and Additionality Gates	6
D. International Standards and National Registries	8
E. Future Architecture: whether to include agriculture and forestry in the EU ETS?	8
F. Global Perspectives and Benchmarking: Africa and North America	9
G. Conclusion: Toward an Integrated Climate–Nature Finance Architecture	10
Part 1 - Carbon Farming in the DigitAF Project	11
1.1 Goals of the DigitAF Project	11
1.2 Goals and main achievements of Task 1.4 in the DigitAF Project	11
Part 2 - Emissions reporting and carbon markets	14
2.1 National GHG inventories, emission reduction targets and the CAP	14
2.2 The CRCF Regulation	17
2.3 Existing carbon farming standards in Europe	25
2.4 Validation of Standards Organisations	48
Part 3 - Whether to include agriculture and forestry in the EU Emission Trading System?	52
3.1 Introduction	52
3.2 Five Design Models for an Agricultural ETS	52
3.3. Comparative Assessment and Social Considerations	54
3.4. Implementation Challenges	55
3.5. Institutional Strategy: Converging Goals, Different Pathways	57
3.6. Agroforestry within the EU ETS Debate	58
Part 4 - Carbon Farming Certification Worldwide	59
4.1 The Kyoto Clean Development Mechanism	59
4.2 Carbon Certification in Africa	61
4.3 United States	68
4.4 Canada	70
4.5 Comparison with EU CRCF	72
Part 5 - Linkages between carbon farming certification, CAP policies and nature policies.	75
5.1 CRCF and CAP	75
5.2 Agroforestry as a convergence point between carbon farming and biodiversity policy	76
5.3 Nature credits: complementary but distinct from carbon certification	77
5.4 Toward an integrated climate–nature finance architecture	78
Part 6 The Buyers Club, Public Procurement and Biodiversity	80
6.1 The EU Buyers' Club: Concept and Market Function	80
6.2 Public Procurement to support carbon markets	81
6.3 Regulatory Tightening: The Green Claims Directive	81
Part 7. Conclusions	84

List of acronyms

ACMI - Africa Carbon Markets Initiative	ICVCM - Integrity Council for the Voluntary Carbon Market
ACR - American Carbon Registry	IEEP - Institute for European Environmental Policy
AECMs - Agri-Environment-Climate Measures	IFM - Improved Forest Management
AFOLU - Agriculture Forestry and Other Land Use	IPCC - Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
AfSIS - African Soil Information Service	ISO - International Organization for Standardization
Agri-ETS - Agricultural Emissions Trading System	JRC - Joint Research Centre
ALM - Agricultural Land Management	KACP - Kenya Agricultural Carbon Project
ANR - Assisted Natural Regeneration	LBC - Label Bas Carbone
A/R - Afforestation and Reforestation activities	ICERs - long-term Certified Emission Reductions
ARR - Afforestation, reforestation, and revegetation	LiDAR - Light Detection and Ranging
ART - Architecture for REDD+ Transaction	LPIS - Land Parcel Information System (part of the IACS)
ASE - Agriculture Soil Emissions	LSE - LULUCF Soil Emissions
BECCS - Bioenergy Carbon Capture and Storage	LULUCF - Land use, land use change, and forestry
BCCR - Balkan Carbon Credit Registry	MAPAQ - Ministère de l'Agriculture, des Pêcheries et de l'Alimentation du Québec
BioCCS - Biogenic emission Capture with Carbon Storage	MFF - Multiannual Financial Framework
BCR - Biochar Carbon Removal	MITECO - Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico
CANZA - Canadian Alliance for Net-zero Agri-food	MRV - Monitoring Reporting and Verification
CAP - Common Agriculture Policy	MUs - Modelling Units
CAR - Climate Action Reserve	N2O - Nitrous oxide
CBAM - Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism	NECP - National Energy and Climate Plan
CCPs - Core Carbon Principles	NOBV - National Research Programme on Greenhouse Gas Dynamics in Peatlands and Organic Soils
CCS - Carbon Capture and Storage	NRPP - National and Regional Partnership Plans
CDM - Clean Development Mechanism	NRR - Nature Restoration Regulation
CDR - Carbon Dioxide Removal	ONCRA - Open Natural Carbon Accounting
CERs - Certified Emission Reductions	PCU - Peatland Carbon Unit
CH4 - Methane	PDD - Project Design Document
CO2 - Carbon dioxide	PIN - Project Idea Note
COA - EU Court of Auditors	PIU - Pending Issuance Unit
CR - Carbon Removals	PPP - Polluter Pays Principle
CRAFT - Climate-Responsible Agriculture and Food systems	QU.A.L.I.T.Y - Quantification, Additionality, Long-term storage, Sustainability
CRCF - Carbon removals and carbon farming	RCC - Registro Crediti di Carbonio
CREA - Consiglio per la Ricerca in Agricoltura e l'Analisi dell'Economia Agraria	RDI - Research Development and Innovation
CRU - Certified carbon removal unit	REDD+ - Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation
DACCS - Direct Air Capture in Carbon Storage	SDGs - Sustainable Development Goals
DBH - Diameter at Breast Height	SIGPAC - Spanish Land Parcel Identification System
DigitAF - DIGItal Tools to help AgroForestry	SNK - Stichting Nationale Koolstofmarkt
DNSH - Do Not Significant Harm	SOC - Soil Organic Carbon
EEA - European Environment Agency	SSA - Soil Sampling and Analysis
EEB - European Environmental Bureau	tCERs - temporary Certified Emission Reductions
EESC - European Economic and Social Committee	TIST - The International Small Group and Tree Planting Program
ELO - European Landowners' Organization	UNC - Uncertainty Deduction Factor
ESABCC- European Scientific Advisory Board on Climate Change	UNFCCC - United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
ESR - Effort Sharing Regulation	USDA - United States Department of Agriculture
ETS - Emissions Trading System	VCM - Voluntary Carbon Market
EUDR - EU Deforestation Regulation	VCS - Verified Carbon Standard
EURAF - European Agroforestry Federation	VVBs - Validation and Verification Bodies
FSC - Forest Stewardship Council	WCC - Woodland Carbon Code
GAEC - Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions	VCMI - Voluntary Carbon Markets Integrity Initiative
GHG - Greenhouse gas	WCU - Woodland Carbon Unit
GSAA - Geospatial Aid Application (Part of IACS)	WTO - World Trade Organization
IACS - Integrated Administration and Control System (CAP)	
ICRAF - International Centre for Research in Agroforestry	
ICROA - International Carbon Reduction and Offset Alliance	

Tables:

Table 1: UNFCCC Categories used in National Reporting of Greenhouse gases.

Table 2: Monitoring Periods, Activity Periods and renewal options in the draft CF Delegated Act.

Table 3: Forest type disturbance regime and risk rating in the CRCF Delegated Act.

Table 4: Agroforestry certification stages under the CRCF: from parcel to registry.

Table 5: Core Carbon Principles of the Integrity Council for the Voluntary Carbon Market (ICVCM).

Table 6: VERRA Methodologies relating to Agriculture Forestry and Other Land Use (AFOLU).

Table 7: VERRA Certified AFOLU Projects in Europe (Active September 2025).

Table 8: Comparison of the three main Global carbon farming certification standards.

Table 9: Use of National Carbon Registries in Member States.

Table 10: VERRA AFOLU projects in Africa (Active September 2025).

Table 11: Gold Standard AFOLU projects in Africa (Active September 2025).

Table 12: Plan Vivo AFOLU projects in Africa (Operational September 2025).

Table 13: Carbon farming certification systems in Africa, the United States, Canada and the EU CRCF.

Table 14: Characteristics of the Buyers' Club Public Procurement and EU ETS Integration

Figures:

Figure 1: The EU Commission "Pathway to Climate Neutrality in 2050".

Figure 2: GHG Reporting - fluxes of all gases from forestry plus CO₂ from agriculture are reported through the LULUCF Regulation, while non-CO₂ gases from agriculture are reported through the Effort-Sharing Regulation.

Figure 3: The five Pillars of the Carbon Farming Delegated act needed for award of certified carbon units.

Figure 4: The mathematical foundation of temporary carbon benefits for carbon and soil emissions.

Figure 5: The three-part proof of carbon-farming additionality.

Figure 6: The certification lifecycle for agriculture and agroforestry on mineral soils.

Figure 7: Links between the Commission, certification schemes, operators, national accreditation bodies, auditors and buyers envisaged in the CRCF.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

A. Strategic Context and Project Vision

The DigitAF project is focused on delivering tools to expand the use of agroforestry in European agriculture, to strengthen its prominence in policies, and assist the European Union's trajectory toward climate neutrality by 2050. A critical bottleneck remains the widening gap between high-level climate targets and the faltering delivery of emission reductions in the land sector caused by static agricultural emissions and falling sequestration in Europe's forests. DigitAF argues that a massive expansion of agroforestry can help bridge this gap, and has worked on mathematical models and practical methods to assist with digital Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification (MRV) of agroforestry carbon farming. The aim of this report is to facilitate the uptake of agroforestry carbon farming by showing its compatibility with the MRV rules being developed in the Carbon Farming Delegated Act of the Carbon Removals Certification Framework.

Core Strategic Goals of the DigitAF Project

To operationalize this vision, DigitAF has pursued five primary objectives:

- **Digital Tool Development:** Engineering open-source, user-friendly tools that link field-level data to cloud-based MRV systems for consistent carbon accounting.
- **Policy Support:** Generating the evidentiary base and technical advice necessary for policymakers to design effective carbon farming and agroforestry regulations.
- **Practitioner Optimization:** Providing farmers with management tools to optimize the design and day-to-day resilience of agroforestry systems.
- **Value Chain Enhancement:** Developing methodologies to quantify and monetize the economic and environmental benefits (carbon, biodiversity, water) of agroforestry.
- **Living Labs Infrastructure:** Utilizing a network of six local labs (IT, DE, NL, UK, FI, CZ) to test digital solutions against real-world agricultural conditions.

The plan for this Deliverable was written in 2001, and it foresaw the intensive EU legislative activity on carbon farming during the past 5 years. Procedures for voluntary carbon certification are now well advanced in the EU, and the possibility exists of extending these to a statutory scheme applicable to all of the EU's agricultural and forestry land. Since emissions by the land sector are likely to comprise around 50% of residual emissions by 2050 it is likely that some form of statutory emissions accounting and valuation will take place in the next decade, building on the rules developed for the voluntary sector. The models, data and mapping tools developed in the DigitAF project contribute, in a modest way, to this technical readiness, and to the **growing realisation that agroforestry is a hugely underused nature-based-solution for climate mitigation and adaptation needs.**

B. The EU Regulatory Landscape: LULUCF, CAP, and CRCF

European land-use and climate policy is steered by three critical regulations: the Land Use, Land-Use Change, and Forestry (LULUCF) Regulation, the Effort Sharing Regulation (ESR), and the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). The, almost impossible, aim of the LULUCF Regulation is to restore the LULUCF sector's net emissions to -310 million tonnes of CO₂ per year by 2030. There is no specific target for non-CO₂ gases in the ESR, for which agriculture currently contributes around one third (+370 Mt CO₂e/yr), but total net emissions in the EU **must** reach 90% of 1990 levels by 2040 (i.e. approx +473 MtCO₂e/yr)¹

¹ During the EU Environment Council meeting on 4-5 November 2025 a "double 5% loophole" to this target was approved: a) trading in "high-quality international carbon credits" can cover up to 5% of the total and b) individual member states can use extra 5% of international trading to meet their own **national** post-2030 targets. The new target and rules were formally approved by Council on 10/3/2026.

The Implementation and Data Gap

Despite these targets, the EU LULUCF sector achieved only -236 MtCO₂ in 2022, missing its trajectory significantly. This failure is exacerbated by a lack of institutional willingness to quantify the climate impacts of agriculture. A high-impact 2021 finding by the EU Court of Auditors (COA) revealed that €100 billion of CAP funds allocated to "climate action" had had no measurable effect on emissions. Furthermore, the 2024 "simplification" of the CAP (Regulation 2024/1468) removed landscape feature targets (GAEC-8) without an evaluation of the climate impact of the policy change.

The CRCF Framework (Regulation 2024/3012)

The Carbon Removals Certification Framework (CRCF) entered into force in December 2024 to restore credibility to carbon certification through four removal types: (a) Permanent Carbon Removals, (b) Carbon Farming, (c) Soil Emission Reductions, and (d) Carbon Storage in Products.

The CRCF draft Carbon Farming Delegated Act has 5 Pillars, extending beyond simple monitoring of sequestration and emissions to include reporting on the risk of storage and on co-benefits.

Pillar	Strategic focus	Compliance Nuance
Definitions & Eligibility	Focuses on mineral soils, silvoarable, silvopasture, and landscape features.	Minimum 5-year activity period; land +conversion cut-off: Jan 1, 2023.
Quantification	Net removal benefits measured accurately against a 3-year baseline.	Must account for all relevant carbon pools and operational "carbon debt."
Additionality	Ensures projects go beyond legal requirements and financial viability.	Practices cannot be mandated by law; must pass the Incentive Effect Test.
Storage & Liability	Manages reversal risks via buffer pools and monitoring periods.	Monitoring period: Activity period + 10 years for biomass.
Sustainability	Enforces "Do No Significant Harm" (DNSH) principles.	Mandatory documentation of biodiversity co-benefits (e.g., habitat connectivity).

The Carbon Farming Delegated Act creates the necessary rules for voluntary carbon farming certification, but its success depends on the technical methodologies developed jointly by the research community, ministries, operators, verifiers and the finance sector.

C. Technical MRV Methodologies and Additionality Gates

Robust MRV is the "currency" of credible carbon markets. To ensure environmental integrity, the CRCF defines specific quantification approaches and additionality tests that determine which removals are bankable.

Quantification Approaches and Uncertainty

Operators must balance administrative cost with credit yield by selecting one of three approaches. A key strategic consideration is the Uncertainty Deduction Factor (UNC), which penalizes lower-quality data.

Approach	Methodology	Strategic Trade-off
1: Models	Process-based computational frameworks.	High scalability; requires validation against independent datasets.
2: Measurements	Site-specific sampling and allometric equations.	Highest accuracy and credit volume; highest administrative cost.
3: Default Factors	Tier 1 (IPCC) or Tier 2 (National) factors.	Simple implementation but least capital-efficient; mandatory minimum 10% UNC deduction.

Additionality "Gates" and Regulatory Irony

To qualify for certification, a project must pass three tests: Regulatory, Incentive Effect, and Financial Viability. Ironically, because the EU removed mandatory landscape feature targets (GAEC-8) in 2024, hedges and trees that were previously "required" are now "additional" and thus eligible for carbon credits. This regulatory retreat has effectively opened the door for carbon finance to fund basic landscape feature establishment and maintenance.

Liability and Risk Rates

Agroforestry is more resilient to fire and windthrow risks than traditional forestry. The CRCF liability-first approach uses risk rates based on JRC calculations of "disturbance return periods"

- **Agroforestry Risk Rates:** 4% (Low), 8% (Medium), 24% (High).
- **Conifer Risk Rates:** 10% (Low), 20% (Medium), 50% (High).

Because agroforestry risk is roughly half that of traditional conifers, practitioners can release significantly more tradable units to the market, retaining a smaller percentage in the buffer pool. Alignment and sharing of standards is needed between existing national and international registries and the geospatial register being established by the EU in 2028 (with assistance from the Horizon OGCR and CAFAMORE projects).

D. International Standards and National Registries

As the EU moves toward a statutory framework, practitioners must choose between international voluntary standards (Verra, Gold Standard, Plan Vivo) and emerging national registries.

Strategic Selection: Verra VM0042 vs. VM0047

Two Verra standards are appropriate for agroforestry:

- **VM0042 (ALM):** is best if the goal is to monetize whole-farm soil organic carbon (SOC) and nitrogen fertilizer reductions (N₂O). This aligns most closely with the CRCF "Agriculture and Agroforestry on Mineral Soils" methodology.
- **VM0047 (ARR):** was best if the project is strictly a small-scale tree-planting intervention focused on biomass accumulation without changes to soil management, as in shelterbelt or hedge planting. This is currently not as comprehensive as the CRCF "Afforestation" methodology and may need to be updated in the same way as VM0042 recently has been.

National Progress and Interoperability

Member States are increasingly creating domestic registries to meet local demand and CAP co-financing opportunities. Examples include:

- **France (Label Bas Carbone):** Advanced methodologies for hedges and orchards, with an important methodology for "in-field trees" coming soon.
- **Italy:** National guidelines for the public registry were adopted in October 2025. Crucially, this registry focuses on sustainable management activities that go beyond GAEC standards, requiring strict additionality.
- **Spain:** Operates the *Registro de Huella*, focused strictly on reforestation and fire restoration.

The strategic choice for operators lies between National Alignment (easier local subsidies) and International Fungibility (global corporate buyers). This voluntary activity may increasingly serve as a precursor to a potential mandatory "Agri-ETS."

E. Future Architecture: whether to include agriculture and forestry in the EU ETS?

Agriculture's share of EU emissions is projected to reach 50% by 2050. Consequently, the sector's inclusion in an Emissions Trading System (Agri-ETS) may appear a strategic inevitability. However, such an approach entails significant risks for farmers. Many agricultural producers lack the financial capacity to invest in the innovations required to reduce emissions, potentially placing disproportionate pressure on smaller operators. Moreover, emissions in agriculture are inherently variable and context-dependent, influenced by factors such as climate conditions, soil characteristics, and farming practices. This variability complicates measurement, reporting, and verification (MRV) systems, which risk being imprecise and, in some cases, inequitable. Nevertheless, it is unlikely that voluntary certification schemes, already burdened by high MRV costs, will alone deliver the systemic transformation required in European agriculture and forestry.

FOR	AGAINST
<p>Incentivizing Emission Reductions: Agricultural emissions are flattening and they will represent 50% of all emissions by 2040. More intensive accounting for emissions and removals for all farmers will create a direct, market-driven financial motive for agribusinesses to reduce methane and nitrous oxide emissions. </p>	

Design Models and Institutional Friction

The Commission is evaluating five models for an agricultural ETS: three on-farm methods (1) All-GHG, (2) Livestock, (3) Peatland; and two off-farm methods (4) Upstream, and (5) Downstream. Implementing these models faces significant institutional friction. Climate experts favour carbon pricing options to radically change existing farming practices (with the unfortunate title of "Polluter Pays"), while agricultural ministries favour more modest incentive-based CAP measures. This tension represents a major implementation risk, potentially leading to fragmented policy signals.

Implementation Hurdles and CBAM

The primary barrier to an Agri-ETS in the EU is the administrative burden of monitoring emissions from 6 million registered farmers. Furthermore, there is a high risk of "carbon leakage", where production moves outside the EU to avoid costs. Addressing this would require the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) to be extended to agriculture and forestry, which would be technically very complex to implement across heterogeneous global production systems. Nevertheless, lessons for these future pricing models can be drawn from existing global benchmarks.

F. Global Perspectives and Benchmarking: Africa and North America

Global markets provide vital proof-of-concept for the EU's evolving CRCF framework, particularly regarding smallholder aggregation and governance.

- **African Lessons and Participatory MRV:** African projects (e.g., KACP, TIST) successfully use Participatory MRV (P-MRV). By training local communities to collect data (e.g., measuring tree height and DBH²), projects significantly reduce verification costs. This is a direct lesson for the EU's need for "streamlined, lower-cost verification paths" for smallholders.
- **North American Models:** a) the United States follows a "distributed innovation" model, focusing heavily on supply-chain insetting (USDA Partnerships for Climate-Smart Commodities). This contrasts with the EU's focus on regulatory credits for external offsets; b) Canada provides a

² DBH (Diameter at Breast Height) refers to the diameter of a tree trunk measured at 1.3 metres above ground level. It is the standard measurement used in forestry, agroforestry and carbon accounting to estimate tree biomass using allometric equations.

"cooperative governance" model (e.g., Sollio/Coop Carbone) where trusted intermediaries manage the MRV burden for farmers, ensuring higher legitimacy.

These benchmarks can inform the Commission on how to finalize its CRCF to be both inclusive and scientifically rigorous.

G. Conclusion: Toward an Integrated Climate–Nature Finance Architecture

The foundation for any credible voluntary carbon pricing or certification is a robust, harmonized data infrastructure, but **the transition from fragmented voluntary projects to a unified widely-implemented climate-and-nature finance architecture is non-negotiable if 2050 targets are to be achieved.**

Main Recommendations for the Commission

1. **Integrate emissions from LULUCF and Effort Sharing sectors³ in national GHG reporting** and in the CRCF to give greater visibility of the opportunities for livestock farmers to offset non-CO2 emissions against carbon sequestration from tree planting and management.
2. **Quantify the GHG contributions of all CAP Interventions** and in the next CAP favour those with the greatest climate mitigation and adaptation benefit.
3. **Mandate consistent mapping of afforestation, agroforestry and landscape feature parcels** across the LULUCF, CAP, NRR, EUDR, CRCF and nature-credits arenas to eliminate administrative inaccuracies and data vacuums.
4. **Ensure full compliance with the 2023 High Value Datasets Implementing Regulation ([2023/138](#))** for IACS LPIS and GSAA data by taking "Confirmity Clearance Procedures" against the 7 member states which do not yet meet its requirements (see EURAF [Research Report #8v2](#))
5. **Retroactively recognize the eligibility for carbon credits of early movers who planted trees** (afforestation, agroforestry and woody landscape features) in the period 2015 - 2023 via modifications to the CF Delegated Act, potentially linked to the upcoming Nature Credits frameworks.⁴
6. **Reduce MRV costs and facilitate farmer participation** by promoting the development of cost-effective MRV systems based on digital tools, remote sensing and interoperable certification registries.

By operationalizing these policies through sophisticated digital tools, the EU can transform agroforestry and woody landscape features into the cornerstone of a resilient, carbon-neutral agricultural sector.

³ As indicated in the text (and Figure 2). The separation of LULUCF Reporting (all GHG fluxes in forestry but only CO2 in agriculture) from the Emission Sharing Reporting (non CO2 gases in Agriculture) presents uncertainty and confusion in national accounting. The Commission proposed in the Ready for 55 package that they should be merged and the commission was correct.

⁴ Digital land use information was first reliably collected in EU Member States in 2005, including for the ten nations which joined in 2004. A **quality milestone** was achieved in 2010 following the introduction of the LPIS Quality Assessment introduced by Implementing Regulation [1122/2009](#). However **the 2015 "Greening Reform"** introduced the "Ecological Focus Areas" into most LPIS databases, and the declaration of specific crop types. Improvements to LPIS systems were mandated by Implementing Regulation [809/2014](#) and Delegated Regulation [640/2014](#)

Part 1 - Carbon Farming in the DigitAF Project

1.1 Goals of the DigitAF Project

The [DigitAF Project](#) (DIGItal Tools to help AgroForestry meet climate, biodiversity and farming sustainability goals: linking field and cloud) project is a Horizon Europe initiative that aims to overcome the barriers to the widespread use of agroforestry practices in Europe. It runs from July 2022 to June 2026, with goals:

- **To develop digital tools:** These open-source, user-friendly tools will assist different groups, including policymakers, farmers, and those involved in the agroforestry value chain, in implementing and managing agroforestry systems.
- **To support policy:** The project provides data and evidence to help policymakers at various levels design more effective policies that encourage the adoption of agroforestry and carbon farming.
- **To assist practitioners:** It provides farmers and other practitioners with tools to help them optimize the design and day-to-day management of agroforestry systems.
- **To enhance value chains:** The project helps actors in the value chain assess, quantify, and market the economic, environmental, and social benefits of agroforestry, such as carbon sequestration and biodiversity.
- **To implement living labs:** The project operates six "Living Labs" in Italy, Germany, the Netherlands, the United Kingdom, Finland, and the Czech Republic. These labs serve as local networks where stakeholders can test the digital tools and provide feedback.

The project brings together a consortium of 25 partners from 20 countries. Its ultimate goal is to promote agroforestry as a concrete solution for improving agricultural sustainability and resilience to climate change while contributing to biodiversity preservation and food security. A key innovation of DigitAF is the linkage between field-level data and digital MRV systems that enable consistent carbon accounting across regions. The project therefore provides a unique bridge between science-based evidence and policy implementation for carbon farming and agroforestry.

1.2 Goals and main achievements of Task 1.4 in the DigitAF Project

Task 1.4 “Policies for Carbon Farming in the EU Statutory and Voluntary Sectors” was planned to run from Month 13 to the end of the project in Month 48. Its wording, written in September 2021 (Box 1), presaged a period of intensive activity on carbon farming in the European Union.

Box 1: T1.4 Policies for Carbon Farming in the statutory and voluntary sectors (ELO, EURAF, ICRAF COOPC, EFI, SAVANNA, CRAN) (M13-M48) (GA dated 3/6/2022, with proposal text written in September 2021).

This task will assess the emerging policy opportunities for voluntary and (eventually) statutory accounting of “carbon projects”, and the technical hurdles involved in certification (e.g. VERRA, Gold Standard & ICROA). Issues like leakage, additionality and permanence will be considered. This will feed into WP3 to assess the financial impact of carbon farming with trees, and the costs and practicalities of certification. Collaboration is planned with JRC in this Task, particularly regarding the upgrades planned to the code of the JRC Carbon Calculator.⁵ ELO and EURAF will summarise national, European and international efforts to collect rules and practices for voluntary certification of carbon farming with trees. ICRAF, COOPC & SAVANNA will contribute experience from Africa and North America. Several countries and regions allow forestry and agroforestry projects within their emissions trading schemes (ETS) Currently, this is not possible in the EU-ETS, but it remains under review by the EU. EURAF and ELO will consult stakeholders on how forestry and agroforestry could be included with robust rules for monitoring and verifying EU emissions, together with methods to manage potential double counting.

⁵ The JRC Carbon Calculator has been developed by RegenFarmer into open source code repository called the "Open Farm Carbon Tracker". Its status is described in EURAF Milestone Report 5 (31.5.25), available through the [EURAF Github](#).

Many recent developments have taken place in EU policy on carbon removals

- **November 2022** - the Commission published its original proposal for creation of a voluntary eu-wide carbon removal standard;
- **March 2023** - the Carbon Removals expert group held its first meeting in Brussels to discuss and decide on details to be included in the enabling regulations for the standard
- **February 2024** - a provisional agreement was reached between the EU Parliament and Council on a Carbon Removals Certification Framework (CRCF) defining four types of carbon-removal: a) permanent removals, b) carbon farming, c) soil emission reductions and c) carbon storage in products;
- **December 2024** - the CRCF Regulation (2024/3012) entered into force
- **November 2025** - the CRCF Implementing Regulation (2025/2358) was “adopted” by the Commission laying down the rules for certification schemes, certification bodies and the audit process.
- **February 2026** - Permanent Carbon Removals Delegated Act was “adopted” (following consultation) and is expected to enter into force in April 2026.
- **February 2026** - Consultation closed on the Carbon Farming Delegated Act , with “adoption” expected in summer 2026.
- **April 2026** - certification schemes can begin to apply for recognition under the CRCF.
- **Late 2026** - recognition decisions are expected for certification schemes
- **Late 2026** - consultation is anticipated on the Carbon Storage Delegated Act
- **Early 2027** - consultation is expected on inclusion of “livestock and slurry emissions”.

This report gives an overview of the implications of these developments for voluntary carbon farming schemes and for the potential inclusion of a form of carbon farming in statutory certification, through the European Emission Trading Scheme (Agri-ETS). This report complements several EURAF Policy Briefings, produced with assistance of the DigitAF project:

- [#08](#) *History and potential contribution of agroforestry carbon farming in the EU (v4 28.3.24)*
- [#20](#) *Initial approach to MRV of agroforestry carbon farming in the EU (v5 18.2.26)*
- [#24](#) *Agroforestry and Parliament’s report on sustainable carbon cycles (v1 5.3.23)*
- [#26](#) *Agroforestry for carbon farming - mitigation of climate change (v1 23.6.23)*
- [#27](#) *Agroforestry for carbon farming - adaptation to climate change (v1 31.7.23)*
- [#64](#) *Agroforestry for carbon farming - water resources (v1 30.8.25)*
- [#66](#) *Agroforestry for carbon farming - biodiversity & protection of ecosystems (v1 27.2.25)*

The most recent update of these Briefings (#20v5, 18.2.26) was accompanied by a EURAF [press release](#) which:

... welcomes the draft Carbon Farming Delegated Act, and its strong recognition of agroforestry as a key carbon farming practice that gives multiple climate and biodiversity co-benefits. Emphasises that adjustments are needed to improve legal clarity, consistency of the Delegated Act with existing EU legislation, and to improve its practical implementability across Member States. Recommends that established CAP and LULUCF definitions are used to bring compliance with UNFCCC reporting practices, and that the realities of monitoring, reporting and verification (MRV) remain practical and affordable, using standardised remote sensing and geospatial data. Stresses that clear and harmonised definitions for agroforestry, landscape features and forests are needed to reduce administrative burdens, to avoid divergent interpretations, and to support broad uptake by farmers and land managers.

DigitAF Deliverable 1.5 focuses on the European context, with contributions on carbon certification in Africa from ICRAF. A contribution on carbon certification in North America has been made by two DigitAF

Associated Partners in that continent (Savanna Institute and Coop-Carbon). Completion of Policy Briefings on the two remaining areas of sustainability are planned by June 2026:

- [#65](#) Agroforestry for carbon farming - control of water pollution (draft)
- [#67](#) Agroforestry for carbon farming - the circular bioeconomy (draft)

The authors are delighted that the first of three methodologies in the draft CRCF Carbon Farming Delegated Act is titled "*Agriculture and Agroforestry on Mineral Soils*", and our most recent inputs are summarised in EURAF [Policy Briefing #20](#).

The Deliverable will also comment on how the digital MRV tools developed under DigitAF can operationalize the CRCF methodologies, providing a transparent and cost-effective system for verification across member states. It has the following parts.

- **Part 2** explores existing voluntary carbon markets in Europe, including the developing legislative context for the Carbon Removals Certification Framework and the existing carbon farming scheme.
- **Part 3** explores options for a "statutory" carbon market in Europe and is awaiting important policy developments, due in the next 12 months.
- **Part 4** explores the voluntary carbon farming schemes in Africa and North America and the role of agroforestry
- **Part 5** analyses the link between CAP policies, carbon certification and the emerging concept of "nature credits"
- **Part 6** focuses on how the market can be stimulated through public/private options to provide guaranteed prices and latest developments with CRCF draft legislation.

Dissemination activities.

The DigitAF project organised a session on agroforestry carbon farming at the 2nd European Carbon Farming Summit in March 2025, and two sessions are planned at the 3rd Carbon Farming Summit in March 2026. Both EURAF and ELO have provided feedback to the EU Carbon Removals Expert Group, leading to the development of the CRCF Regulation ([2024/3012](#)), known as the "Certification framework for Permanent Carbon Removals, Carbon Farming and Carbon Storage in Products". Both organisations have had significant inputs to the CRCF **draft** methodologies for a) "Agriculture and Agroforestry on Mineral Soils" ([April 2025](#)), b) "Afforestation and Reforestation" ([April 2025](#)), c) "Rewetting of Peatlands" ([May 2025](#)); and for the new drafts of the [Delegated Act and its Annex](#) presented during the expert group on February 2026

Part 2 - Emissions reporting and carbon markets

2.1 National GHG inventories, emission reduction targets and the CAP

The European Union has committed to climate neutrality by 2050 through the European Climate Law (Regulation [2021/119](#)) (Figure 1), and as a contribution to this goal, the land use sector has been given intermediate targets for 2030. These were set through the Land Use Land Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) Regulation ([2023/841](#)) and the Effort Sharing Regulation ([2023/857](#)). The former includes all CO₂ emissions resulting from land use change and all emissions in forestry. The latter covers non-CO₂ emissions in agriculture (Figure 2). The LULUCF sector in the EU has historically represented a net sink for GHGs and the LULUCF Regulation aimed to restore this sink by setting a target for annual net emissions of -310 million tonnes of CO₂e by 2030.

However, latest figures suggest that only -236 MtCO₂e was achieved in 2022 (EEA, 2024), and that the 2030 target will be missed by a considerable margin (A. J. Matthews, 2023). The non-CO₂ emissions from agriculture (covered by the Effort Sharing Regulation - *ibid*) only fell by 5% between 2005 and 2022 and are projected to increase by 2030 based on current policies and measures. Current EU GHG emission monitoring systems (e.g., LULUCF MRV) may under-represent agroforestry due to fragmented land-use definitions (Enoki et al., 2024), a gap that new CRCF methodologies may help address.

The persistent gap between LULUCF targets and observed removals, together with the static trend in agricultural non-CO₂ emissions, suggests that the challenge is not solely lack of ambition, but also a lack of willingness by agricultural authorities to quantify the climate impact of existing agricultural practices, and possible mitigation options. This lack of ambition was confirmed by the EU Court of Auditors who found that the €100 billion of CAP funds allocated by DGAGRI to “climate action” between 2014 and 2020, had had no measurable effect on emissions. It was also demonstrated when the Commission rushed through the 2024 CAP Simplification Regulation ([2024/1468](#)), in response to farmers protests, which removed area-targets for landscape features (GAEC-8) and non-productive areas. This followed an abbreviated consultation process, which skipped the normal “impact-assessment”, and was based on a “simplification [non-paper](#)” which evaluated potential financial savings but made no mention of the climate mitigation impact of GAEC-8 (COA, 2024; A. Matthews, 2024).

The need for improved data is starting to be recognised however. In May 2025 DGAGRI published an updated version of its 2024 report titled “*Rough estimate of the climate change mitigation potential of the CAP Strategic Plans (EU-27) over the 2023-2027 period*” (CAP Network, 2025). This listed at least 40 farming practices, including agroforestry, with “no data”.

The IPCC’s Good Practice Guidance for LULUCF (Calvo Buendia et al., 2019) stresses the need for consistent, transparent and comparable methodologies in national greenhouse gas inventories. Recent studies have highlighted discrepancies between emissions estimated from national national inventories and those derived from alternative modelling and satellite monitoring approaches (McGlynn et al., 2022; Melo et al., 2026; Yu et al., 2019). Clearly, emission estimates from the MRV of carbon farming projects need to use similar methodology to national GHG reporting.

In the EU context, this implies closer alignment between National Greenhouse Gas Inventory methodologies and emerging carbon farming MRV systems, including those under the CRCF. Greater methodological convergence would reduce the risk of double counting, improve data consistency and enhance the visibility of farm-level mitigation within national accounting systems. This is particularly relevant for agroforestry, which has been recognised as a strategic land-use system with multiple environmental benefits, including greenhouse gas mitigation. Monitoring systems that fail to adequately capture agroforestry’s combined soil carbon sequestration, biomass accumulation and landscape effects may underestimate its contribution to national mitigation targets.

Figure 1: The EU Commission "Pathway to Climate Neutrality in 2050" (Volpi, 2025). Showing that by 2050 residual non-CO₂ emissions from agriculture are expected to be balanced by sequestration in the LULUCF sector.

Figure 2: Fluxes of all greenhouse gases from forestry and CO₂ from agriculture are reported through the LULUCF Regulation (blue) and the Effort-Sharing Regulation (red) (European Commission, 2016) Note: the draft the "Fit for 55" Legislation proposed combining these accounting categories, but the proposal was rejected in trialogue. New legislative proposals for the "Governance Regulation on the Energy Union and Climate Action" are planned for Q4 2026, and may revive the proposal for integrated accounting from 2030 onwards including the use of "International Carbon Credits".

An important contribution of carbon farming certification to national GHG reporting, would be for the former to start reporting using the IPCC "Common Reporting Format" for GHG Emissions (Table 1). A close link to IPCC "Guidelines for GHG Inventories" already exists for most certification methods: both to the original 2006 guidelines (IPCC, 2006) and to the 2019 refinement (Calvo Buendia et al., 2019). More details on national GHG reporting is given in DigitAF Deliverable D1.3 "Methods to record agroforestry areas and greenhouse gas emissions in the EU".

Table 1 UNFCCC Categories used in National Reporting of Greenhouse gases.

These follow the UNFCCC "Common Reporting format"; some categories have "No Estimate (NE)". Carbon farming certification methodologies should also use these reporting categories to facilitate a link between the CRCF and national GHG Inventories.

CRCF Code	Category	Gas(es)	Common Reasons for "NE" (Not Estimated) reporting by EU Member States
GHG Inventory Chapter 3: Agriculture			
3.A	Enteric Fermentation	CH ₄	Emissions from minor livestock (e.g., mules, asses) may be "NE" if population data is scarce or the source is deemed insignificant compared to major livestock like cattle.
3.B	Manure Management	CH ₄ , N ₂ O	Emissions from manure of minor livestock categories or specific, less common manure management systems might be reported as "NE".
3.C	Rice Cultivation	CH ₄	Often reported as "NO" (Not Occurring) in Member States that do not cultivate rice. Could be "NE" if cultivation is minimal and data is lacking.
3.D	Agricultural Soils	N ₂ O, CO ₂	Direct and indirect N ₂ O emissions are a primary focus. CO ₂ from liming and urea application is also included here. "NE" is rare for major soil activities but could occur for specific sub-categories if activity data is unavailable.
3.E	Prescribed Burning of Savannas	CH ₄ , N ₂ O	Frequently reported as "NO" by most EU Member States, as savanna ecosystems are not a feature of their geography. This category or 3.F should include wildfire emissions on croplands and grasslands.
3.F	Field Burning of Agricultural Residues	CH ₄ , N ₂ O	Mostly reported as "NO" due to EU regulations banning the practice. Could be "NE" if a country acknowledges unauthorized burning but cannot quantify it.
3.G	Liming	CO ₂	Emissions from the application of limestone and dolomite to agricultural soils. Usually reported, but could be "NE" if data on lime use is not collected.
3.H	Urea Application	CO ₂	Emissions from the application of urea-based fertilizers. Generally reported, but "NE" might be used if urea usage data is not specifically tracked.
3.I	Other Carbon-containing Fertilizers	CO ₂	This is a residual category. It is often reported as "NO" or "NE" if no such fertilizers are used or if data is not available.
GHG Inventory Chapter 4: Land Use, Land-Use Change, and Forestry (LULUCF)			
4.A	Forest Land	CO ₂ , CH ₄ , N ₂ O	This is a key category. CO ₂ removals or emissions from changes in biomass, dead organic matter, and soils are central. "NE" can occur for specific carbon pools (e.g., soil organic carbon) if national data is incomplete. Non-CO ₂ emissions from drainage and fertilization are also reported here.
4.B	Cropland	CO ₂ , N ₂ O	Reports CO ₂ emissions and removals from changes in carbon stocks in biomass and soils. "NE" may be used for soil carbon changes in specific perennial crops if data is lacking.
4.C	Grassland	CO ₂ , N ₂ O	Accounts for CO ₂ changes in biomass and soils on grasslands. Soil carbon stock changes are complex and may be reported as "NE" if a country lacks a robust monitoring system for its diverse grasslands.
4.D	Wetlands	CO ₂ , CH ₄ , N ₂ O	Includes emissions and removals from peatlands and other wetlands. This is a very complex category. "NE" is frequently used, especially for emissions from peat extraction or for specific land-use transitions involving wetlands, due to high uncertainty and difficult data collection.
4.E	Settlements	CO ₂	Reports CO ₂ stock changes in biomass (e.g., urban trees). Often considered a minor category, and changes in soil carbon are frequently reported as "NE".
4.F	Other Land	CO ₂	A residual category for land that doesn't fall into the above categories (e.g., bare soil, rock). Carbon stock changes are typically minimal and often reported as "NE" or "NO".
4.G	Harvested Wood Products	CO ₂	Accounts for the storage of carbon in wood products that are in use. Methodologies can be complex, and some countries might report "NE" if they lack the detailed production and trade data required.
4(V)	Biomass Burning	CH ₄ , N ₂ O	This cross-cutting category includes non-CO ₂ emissions from wildfires and controlled burns across all land-use types (Forest Land, Cropland, etc.). "NE" might be used for controlled burns if the amount of biomass combusted is not tracked, though wildfire data is usually estimated.

2.2 The CRCF Regulation

Regulation [2024/3012](#) (*“establishing a Union certification framework for permanent carbon removals, carbon farming and carbon storage in products*), was published on 6/12/2024 and is designed to provide a transparent and high-quality standard for certifying carbon removals. Its primary goal is to accelerate the deployment of carbon removal technologies and sustainable farming practices, while preventing “greenwashing.” The CRCF also complements Article 6 of the [Paris Agreement](#) by creating a transparent domestic framework that can link voluntary carbon markets with international transfer mechanisms, ensuring consistency and avoiding double counting.

The CRCF is an enabling framework to underpin and provide quality assurance for various financial incentives, including the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), the EU Innovation Fund, state aid programs, and the voluntary carbon market. It is a regulatory instrument permitting other certification standards to be included within it and validated.

By setting legally binding quality requirements it aims to bring existing voluntary standards to broad alignment with its principles to maintain credibility and market access within the EU. This should lead to an improved confidence in existing standards, and a de facto two-tiered market which distinguishes between “CRCF-compliant” credits and those that are not. It is expected that CRCF-compliant credits will benefit from a price-premium and that they will have a broader suitability for a range of uses, such as possible inclusion in the EU Emissions Trading System (Agri-ETS) (see Part 3).

The CRCF enabling acts published or planned are:

- **Implementing Act** for certification schemes, certification bodies, and audits, Nov 2025, ([Reg 2025/2358](#))
- **Delegated Act 1** for DACCS, BioCCS, Biochar, adopted Feb 2026⁶, [C\(2026\)553](#)
- **Delegated Act 2** for Carbon Farming, Feb 2026, consultation draft ([Ares 2026 746080](#))
- **Delegated Act 3** for Carbon Storage in Products, consultation draft expected Q3 2026
- **Delegated Act 4** for “Advanced Farming (livestock and slurry management)”, expected late 2026.

Article 2(19) of the CRCF Regulation defines **carbon farming** as *“any practice or process carried out over an activity period of at least five years, related to the management of a terrestrial or coastal environment and resulting in the capture and temporary storage of atmospheric or biogenic carbon in biogenic carbon pools, or in the reduction of soil emissions”*

Note that this definition extends beyond carbon to soil emissions of methane and nitrous oxide, but that it **does not yet include** emissions from slurry and enteric fermentation. So far, DGCLIMA has developed MRV rules for three carbon farming activities: a) agriculture and agroforestry on mineral soils, b) afforestation, and c) rewetting of peatlands. While afforestation is included, the methodology does not include the impact of all forest management activities: such as forest grazing to reduce likelihood and importance of wildfires.

Note also that afforestation and agroforestry can generate credits for “permanent carbon removals - e.g. biochar” and “removal in products”.

Methodologies for monitoring, reporting and verification of these activities were open for public consultation until 19/2/2026, and will be further developed in consultation with the Carbon Removals Expert Group.

⁶ Direct Air Capture in Carbon Storage (DACCS), Biogenic emission Capture with Carbon Storage (BioCCS) and Biochar Carbon Removal (BCR)

2.2.1 The Carbon Farming Delegated Act

The draft Delegated Act “Establishing the Certification Methodologies for Carbon Farming Activities” ([Ares \(2026\)746080](#)) provides detailed information and procedures following Articles 3-7 of the CRCF Regulation: a) eligibility, b) quantification, c) additionality, d) storage, monitoring, liability and sustainability. The criteria reflect internationally recognised integrity standards and ensure that certified carbon removal units (CRUs) represent real, additional and sustainable climate benefits (Guidi & Aubert, 2025). The description below focuses on the methodology for “agriculture and agroforestry on mineral soils”.

Figure 3: The five Pillars of the Carbon Farming Delegated act needed for award of certified carbon units

A. DEFINITIONS & ELIGIBILITY

The Act focuses on three agroforestry practices on mineral agricultural soils, ensuring that only activities with clear sequestration potential are eligible for certification:

- **Silvopastoral and Silvoarable Systems:** The integration of tree planting within existing crop or livestock parcels.
- **Landscape Features:** The strategic planting of woody elements, such as hedges, between parcels to enhance connectivity and carbon stocks.
- **Integrated Permanent Crops:** The establishment of new orchards or perennial systems where at least two agricultural practices coexist (e.g., grazed or intercropped orchards).

Activities are generally ineligible if they occur on land where existing agroforestry systems, hedges, or trees were removed, or permanent grassland was ploughed, after January 1, 2023. However removals are permitted if they were necessitated by "control of fire, pest or windthrow events". Furthermore, the activity must maintain riparian buffer zones (riparian forests, buffer strips, or meadows) along streams to remain compliant. The framework distinguishes between the commitment to the practice (Activity Period) and the duration of oversight (Monitoring Period), with a distinction for N₂O reduction activities (Table 2).

Table 2: Monitoring Periods, Activity Periods and renewal options in the draft CF Delegated Act

Activity Type	Initial Activity Period	Renewal Options	Max Commitment	Minimum Monitoring Period
Agroforestry (Biomass)	15 Years	Once (15 years)	30 Years	Activity Period + 10 Years
Soil C Removals	5 Years	3x (5 years each)	20 Years	Activity Period + 10 Years
N ₂ O Emission Reductions	5 Years	3x (5 years each)	20 Years	Equal to Activity Period

EURAF [Policy Briefing #20](#) has requested that the activity period should be renewable up to 60 years, since 30 years will be too short for optimum timber growth of many species.

Examples of Soil C-Removals are a) improved crop management - cover crops, rotations, residue retention, b) conservation tillage - increasing carbon input, c) conversion of cropland to grassland and improved management, d) use of organic soil improvers.

Examples of N₂O emission reductions are: a) precision fertilisation, b) replacing miner N-fertilisers with legumes or biostimulants, c) use of nitrification/urease inhibitors

B. QUANTIFICATION

Quantification requires that the net carbon removal units generated by an activity are measured accurately, conservatively and transparently, based on robust monitoring methodologies and a clearly defined baseline scenario. The Delegated Act provides two equations for temporary net carbon removal benefit and soil net emission reduction benefit. (Figure 4)

Equation A: Temporary Net Carbon Removal Benefit

$$\underbrace{(CR_{baseline} - CR_{activity})}_{\substack{\text{CR = Carbon Removals. Negative} \\ \text{numbers indicate a carbon sink.}}} \times (1 - \underbrace{UNC}_{\substack{\text{Uncertainty deduction factor} \\ \text{(ensures conservative estimates)}}}) - GHG_{associated}$$

Equation B: Net Soil Emission Reduction Benefit

$$\underbrace{(LSE_{baseline} - LSE_{activity})}_{\substack{\text{LSE = LULUCF Soil} \\ \text{Emissions.}}} + \underbrace{(ASE_{baseline} - ASE_{activity})}_{\substack{\text{ASE = Agriculture Soil} \\ \text{Emissions (N2O).}}} \times (1 - UNC) - \underbrace{GHG_{associated}}_{\substack{\text{Deductions for project penalties} \\ \text{(e.g., fuel, fertilizer production).}}}$$

Figure 4: The mathematical foundation of temporary carbon benefits for carbon and soil emissions. Note: The former should account for baseline trends ($CR_{baseline}$) over time and $GHG_{associated}$ with the “emissions cost” of doing the project in terms of direct emissions from machinery and fertilisers and indirect emissions through “leakage” or external emissions.

The equations specify that a project must ensure comprehensive accounting across relevant carbon pools and gases and a conservative treatment of uncertainty. For agroforestry, this typically includes above-ground biomass, below-ground biomass and soil organic carbon, with dead organic matter and litter considered if materially impacted. Carbon pools may only be excluded if it can be demonstrated that their omission will not lead to overestimation of net removals. This full-pool accounting approach prevents apparent gains in one carbon pool (such as tree biomass) from masking losses or delayed responses in another (such as soil organic carbon), thereby avoiding distorted crediting.

For agroforestry, the project-baseline is defined as the continuation of agricultural practices⁷ without the introduction of additional trees or enhanced woody vegetation management, reflecting business as usual, and any trends in emissions that that might involve. Existing soil carbon stocks and pre-existing landscape features are incorporated into the baseline, and only incremental changes resulting from the new agroforestry are eligible for certification. This approach provides consistency with pre-existing land use data and ensures that carbon credits represent genuine improvements beyond business-as-usual rather than re-labelling of existing practices.

⁷ With evidence of these practices for at least a 3 year period prior to commencement of the project.

When an activity generates both carbon removals and soil emission reductions, the $\text{GHG}_{\text{associated}}$ (operational emissions from fuel or fertilizer) must be subtracted from both benefits proportionally based on their relative gross sizes. This ensures that the operational "carbon debt" of the project is accurately distributed across all benefit streams.

Operators must choose from three approaches, each with varying degrees of accuracy:

- **Approach 1 (Models):** Uses process-based or data-driven computational frameworks. Requires validation where the mean bias is smaller than the pooled measurement uncertainty.
- **Approach 2 (Measurements):** Site-specific soil sampling or allometric equations for biomass. This is the most demanding but yields the most accurate (and often highest) credit volume.
- **Approach 3 (Default Factors):** Uses Tier 1 (IPCC) or Tier 2 (National) factors. While administratively simple, these factors are inherently conservative, and the mandatory 10% minimum Uncertainty Deduction Factor (UNC) ensures that simplified data leads to lower yields.

Models have to be validated against independent datasets and must be “credible, accurate and transparently designed”. Accuracy should be demonstrated by an “appropriate combination” of on-site measurements, remote sensing and comparison against other models. To harmonise accuracy the Commission is providing an EU Carbon Farming Database which will include approved biophysical models, emission factors and benchmarking data. The certification body must have access to the models assumptions, input data and methods used for uncertainty management.

C. ADDITIONALITY

“Additionality” ensures that certification funds drive new environmental progress rather than subsidizing existing legal obligations or "business-as-usual" profitability. There are three “gates” to demonstrate this: the regulatory test, the incentive effect test and the financial viability test (Figure 5).

Figure 5: The three-part proof of carbon-farming additionality

The **Regulatory Test** confirms that the activity is not already mandated by Union or national law. The removal of the 4% or 6% statutory targets for GAEC8 landscape features in the 2024 CAP Simplification Regulation ([2024/1468](#)) has had the unintended consequence of ensuring that farmers who plant woody landscape features no longer have any regulatory targets to meet.

The **Incentive Effect Test** requires that the prospect of certification induces the behaviour. Crucially, the "start of work" (i.e. the "first legally binding commitment"), must follow the date of application. An "Early Adopter Grace Period" is included in the Act for farmers/operators who started work between January 1, 2023, and December 31, 2027 (or 2030 if under an existing and recognized certification scheme). This

provides a vital eligibility window for early adopters of agroforestry using CAP funds, but clarity is needed that it will also apply to agroforestry establishment with national funds in future CAP periods.

The **Financial Viability Test** requires that the carbon farming activity is not financially viable without the inducement of the certification payment. This can be proven in two ways: a) a *Simple Cost Test* - which proves that the activity incurs costs but generates no revenue/savings (e.g., non-productive hedges), or an *Investment Comparison Test* which compares the Net Present Value of the activity against alternative scenarios, and mandates use of a 3.5% discount rate across the EU. This ensures that the high upfront costs and slow-accruing revenues typical of agroforestry are assessed against a uniform capital cost benchmark.

A frequent criticism of the Delegated Act is that little recognition is given to the carbon sequestered by “early movers” of carbon farming methods. No backdating of benefits is possible before the start date of the current CAP (1.1.2023), indeed payments for net benefits will be lower for these farmers since they have already implemented most of the nature-based practices recommended by the Act. It is hoped that the Commission can revisit this issue, perhaps in the context of a statutory carbon farming ETS scheme (Part 3), or in conjunction with the Commission's recent “*Roadmap towards Nature Credits*” ([COM 2025 374](#)) (Part 5).

D. STORAGE, MONITORING LIABILITY

For agroforestry and other land-based removals, carbon storage is treated as temporary because carbon is held in living biomass and soils that are vulnerable to disturbances such as fire, drought, pests, disease, harvesting or changes in land management. Operators should conduct reversal risk assessments and implement proportionate risk mitigation measures, such as diversified species composition, soil conservation practices, fire prevention planning or contractual land-use commitments. Operators must also monitor all relevant carbon pools affected by the activity, typically including above-ground biomass, below-ground biomass and soil organic carbon. Carbon pools may only be excluded where it can be demonstrated that doing so will not lead to overestimation of net removals.

A reversal is defined as a measurable decrease in previously certified carbon stocks during the monitoring period. The Delegated Act distinguishes between intentional reversals (e.g. deliberate land-use change or tree removal) and unintentional reversals resulting from external disturbances. In both cases, corrective accounting mechanisms apply to ensure environmental integrity, including cancellation of issued units or deductions from future issuance. Operators remain responsible for managing reversal risks throughout the minimum ten-year commitment period for carbon farming activities.

The Delegated Act adopts a "liability-first" approach to manage the inherent volatility of nature-based solutions. It classifies the potential “reversal” of stored carbon into two types:

- **Avoidable Reversals:** Caused by mismanagement, neglect, or "Early Termination" of the activity. Early termination is strictly classified as a **full reversal**, making the operator liable for all units previously issued.
- **Unavoidable Reversals:** Caused by natural disturbances (wildfire, windthrow) or third-party illegal actions.

The assumed likelihood of these reversals is shown in Table 3, (Table 7 in the Delegated Act), which reflects data collated by EURAF showing that the risk of reversals from wildfires (EURAF [Research Report #53](#)) and wind (EURAF [Research Report #52](#)) is significantly less than that in conventional forestry, with a more modest reduction in the risk of pest attack (EURAF [Research Report #54](#)).

Table 3: Forest type disturbance regime and risk rating in the CRCF Delegated Act

Disturbance Regime	Broadleaves	Mixed	Conifers	Agroforestry
Low (RP ≥ 30y)	8%	8%	10%	4%
Medium (RP 15-30y)	17%	17%	20%	8%
High (RP < 15y)	48%	45%	50%	24%

Note: The risk rate is the carbon removal at risk of being released within the monitoring period and is based on the likely "return period" made available by the JRC <https://data.jrc.ec.europa.eu/collection/id-00445> (see Table 7 of Delegated Act)

The Delegated Act considers that the risk rates in agroforestry are around half those of conifers or broadleaves. This means fewer units are "locked" in a buffer pool, maximizing the volume of tradable units and making agroforestry more capital-efficient than pure afforestation.

To maintain market solvency, certification schemes manage **Buffer Pools**. A share of units equal to the risk rate is set aside. If an unavoidable reversal occurs, these retired units are replaced from the pool, ensuring the atmosphere is "made whole" without burdening the buyer.

E. SUSTAINABILITY

Sustainability is assessed in two ways: a) compliance with the "Do No Significant Harm" (DNSH) principle, and b) mandatory enhancement of biodiversity and ecosystem services

Operators must demonstrate the DNSH principle in various ways:

- **climate and land use:** a total ban on converting forestry and grassland to cropland; a total ban on peat usage, except minimal nursery bio-waste
- **water resources:** alignment with the Water Framework Directive ([2000/60/EC](#)) and prevention of water and environmental stress
- **pollution control:** adherence to the Nitrates Directive ([91/676/EEC](#)) and no increase in plant protection products compared with the baseline
- **biodiversity:** no conversion of high conservation value habitats, and exclusion of alien species
- **circular economy:** prioritizing the use of organic waste and by-products as soil improvers

Operators must "generate co-benefits for the protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems, including soil health and the avoidance of land degradation" by demonstrating compliance with:

- **peer-reviewed scientific literature on biodiversity protection and restoration**, including synthesis papers, meta reviews or meta-analyses, such as the Commission Evidence library⁸
- **at least one of the practices listed in Annex VII of Nature Restoration Regulation, Implementing Regulation** ([2025/912](#))
- **management plans and other implementing measures statutory conservation directives**, such as the Birds Directive ([2009/147/EC](#)) the Habitats Directive ([92/43/EEC3](#))

The Delegated Act allows operators to demonstrate these co-benefits through qualitative, action-based or result-based approaches, ensuring proportionality while maintaining environmental integrity.

For agroforestry systems, these co-benefits are directly linked to system design and management and extend beyond carbon sequestration alone. Typical outcomes include improved soil structure and soil organic matter through perennial root systems and reduced erosion; enhanced habitat connectivity via tree

⁸ https://datam.jrc.ec.europa.eu/datam/mashup/JRC_FP_EVIDENCE_LIBRARY/index.html

rows, hedgerows and scattered trees; increased landscape heterogeneity supporting pollinators and natural pest control; improved water regulation through greater infiltration and reduced runoff; and microclimate buffering that strengthens farm-level climate resilience. Agroforestry also contributes to nutrient cycling, wind protection and diversification of on-farm production, reinforcing both ecological stability and economic resilience.

2.2.2 Certification registries in the CRCF

The steps needed for award of a net certified unit for carbon farming are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: The certification lifecycle for agriculture and agroforestry on mineral soils.

While the Delegated Act explains how temporary carbon removal units can be recorded, the CRCF Implementing Regulation (2025/2358), adopted in November 2025, explains how the units are audited and the certificates issued. For carbon farming this regulation is crucial because it needs to handle a high volume of small-scale land managers (farmers and foresters) with streamlined, lower-cost verification paths.

The Implementing Regulation defines a “chain of trust” for carbon farming (Figure 7), involving:

- **Certification Schemes (the Registries):** which are organizations (like Verra, Gold Standard, or new EU-specific schemes) that manage the rules, and must apply to the European Commission for "recognition" to prove they meet EU standards.
- **Certification Bodies (the Auditors):** which are independent third parties that perform the actual on-site or digital inspections, and are accredited by national authorities.
- **Operators (the Farmers/Foresters):** which are individuals or companies carrying out the carbon sequestration activity.

Figure 7: Links between the Commission, Certification schemes, operators, national accreditation bodies, auditors and buyers envisaged in the CRCF (Volpi, 2025)

The certification body (auditor) verifies that the activity complies with the CRCF Regulation and the Delegated Acts and that the net carbon removal benefit has been recorded in the registry of the Certification scheme. Carbon Removal Units (CRUs) will be transparently documented, including baseline assumptions, monitoring data, reversal risk assessments, corrective measures and sustainability co-benefits.

Operators must provide spatially explicit parcel data, typically built on CAP Land Parcel Information (LPIS) geospatial data, with a unique parcel ID which can be verified with Copernicus earth observation systems. To prevent double counting and ensure traceability, certification scheme registries must be publicly accessible and contain information on activities, issued units, monitoring periods, validity status and corrective actions in case of reversals.

The Implementing Regulation further provides for interoperability between registries and anticipates the establishment of a Union-wide electronic, geospatial registry by 2028. Recognition of certification schemes is expected to begin in 2026.

EU-funded initiatives such as the [CAFAMORE](#) and [OGCR](#) projects are contributing to the development of the Union Geospatial Register and to EU databases of emission factors, soils, models and sustainability data. Taken together, the CRCF certification and registry architecture reflects a transition from fragmented voluntary registries toward a harmonised EU-wide system designed to ensure transparency, environmental integrity and interoperability with CAP spatial systems and emerging nature credit frameworks, with agroforestry providing a practical test case for parcel-level implementation and aggregation at scale (Table 4).

Table 4 : Agroforestry certification stages under the CRCF: from parcel to registry.

CRCF Step	Agroforestry-specific requirements and implications
Step 1 – Activity definition (Parcel level)	Certified under “agriculture and agroforestry on mineral soils.” Activity consists of integrating or enhancing woody perennials within active agricultural production. Certification applies at parcel level using georeferenced boundaries (LPIS/IACS). Eligible systems include alley cropping, silvopasture, hedgerows, tree rows, scattered trees, and orchards with understorey management. Agricultural production must remain the primary land use.
Step 2 – Baseline establishment	Baseline reflects continuation of existing agricultural management without additional tree establishment or enhanced woody management. Existing carbon stocks (soil and biomass) are included in the baseline. Only incremental carbon stock changes are creditable. Zero-biomass assumptions are excluded, ensuring consistency with CAP land-use definitions and preventing artificial additionality.
Step 3 – Quantification (Carbon pools)	Full accounting required across relevant pools: above-ground biomass (trees, hedgerows), below-ground biomass (roots), soil organic carbon, and where materially affected, dead organic matter and litter. Pools may only be excluded if omission does not risk overestimation. Net removals are calculated relative to baseline and adjusted for any GHG increases. Prevents internal carbon shifts from distorting credited outcomes.
Step 4 – Sustainability safeguards	Must comply with the “Do No Significant Harm” principle. Agroforestry must generate and document biodiversity and ecosystem co-benefits (e.g., soil structure improvement, habitat connectivity, pollinator support, erosion control, microclimate regulation). Existing carbon-rich features and trees must be protected.
Step 5 – Monitoring and reversal management	Minimum 10-year commitment period. Periodic verification (typically every 5 years under draft methodologies). Operators must conduct reversal risk assessments, implement mitigation measures (e.g., species diversification), monitor biomass and soil carbon, and correct reversals through registry adjustments. Biological CRUs are time-limited and expire at the end of each monitoring period; continued crediting requires recertification.

Step 6 – Certification and registry entry

After third-party verification, certified net removals are recorded by a recognised scheme and issued as Carbon Removal Units (1 CRU = 1 tonne CO₂e) for the relevant monitoring period. Units are registered in public electronic registries. By 2028, an interoperable EU geospatial registry will ensure transparency and avoid double counting. Aggregation across parcels/farms is permitted while maintaining parcel-level traceability.

2.3 Existing carbon farming standards in Europe

The European carbon farming landscape is currently defined by existing international and national voluntary standards. This section analyses three international standards (Verra, Gold Standard and Plan Vivo), and national standards in Europe.

2.3.1 The Verified Carbon Standard (VERRA/VCS)

Verra's Verified Carbon Standard (VCS) is the world's most widely used GHG crediting programme and acts as a major standard-setter in the VCM. Its HQ is in Washington DC. There are 14 methodologies which can be applied in the Agriculture Forestry and Other Land Use (AFOLU) sector (Table 6) but two are particularly relevant to agroforestry:

- **VM0042 Methodology for Improved Agricultural Land Management (ALM).**
- **VM0047 Methodology for Afforestation, Reforestation, and Revegetation (ARR)**

VM0042 (ALM) covers carbon farming practices on agricultural land. It is therefore the closest match for the CRCF methodology for "agriculture and agroforestry on mineral soil". It also conforms to the CAP Strategic Plan Regulation (2021/2115) which includes agroforestry as part of the "agricultural land". VM0042 covers a wide range of carbon farming practices like cover cropping and reduced tillage. Version 2.2 included agroforestry, but the new V3.0 standard (Verra, 2026) significantly improves the monitoring of agroforestry trees. Updates include: a) monitoring all woody biomass using the allometric equations and wood density standards in the forestry standard (VM0047), b) introducing cumulative accounting focusing on net increases in carbon stocks, c) ensuring that modelled biomass growth must be adjusted every 5-years to comply with measurements, d) launching the new Soil Sampling and Analysis Handbook (Black et al., 2026) which provides guidance for soil sampling around trees to avoid bias, e) fully applying ICVCM's "Core Carbon Principles" (Table 5), including a mandatory 40-year permanent commitment for any project claiming carbon removal from trees.

Table 5 - Core Carbon Principles of the Integrity Council for the Voluntary Carbon Market (ICVCM, 2024a)

1. **Effective Governance:** The carbon program must have robust management, transparency, and accountability.
2. **Tracking:** Every credit must be uniquely identified and tracked in a secure registry to prevent double-use.
3. **Transparency:** All project and program data must be publicly accessible to allow for scrutiny.
4. **Robust Verification:** Projects must be audited by independent, accredited third-party experts.
5. **Robust Quantification:** Emission reductions or removals must be calculated conservatively using sound science.
6. **No Double Counting:** The same credit cannot be claimed by more than one entity or counted toward more than one climate target.
7. **Permanence:** Removals must be long-lasting; programs must have "buffer pools" to replace credits if carbon is accidentally released (e.g., a forest fire).
8. **Additionality:** The project would not have happened without the incentive of carbon credit revenue.
9. **Sustainable Development Benefits:** Projects must go beyond carbon to support local communities, biodiversity, and the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).
10. **Contribution to Net Zero:** Projects must not "lock in" high-carbon technologies; they must align with the global transition to a net-zero economy

VM0047 (ARR) Covers all activities that increase woody biomass, including planting trees, seeding, and Assisted Natural Regeneration (ANR). **Version 1.0** (September 2023) replaced several older "legacy"

methods (like AR-ACM0003), and was updated in early 2025 to include dynamic baselines and improved leakage modules. Like VM0042 it was updated in February 2026 to reference the new Soil Sampling and Analysis Handbook (Black et al., 2026). VM0047 requires projects to monitor a control group of similar, matched areas of land outside the project boundary. The project's carbon sequestration is measured against what is actually happening in these matched control areas over time, accounting for real-world variables like climate change, natural disasters, or macroeconomic shifts. It has two distinct Quantification Approaches:

- **Area-Based Approach**, which relies on advanced remote sensing technologies (like satellite imagery and LiDAR) combined with statistical matching to track changes in tree canopy cover over large areas. This significantly lowers monitoring costs for large-scale projects.
- **Census-Based Approach**, which uses traditional, on-the-ground field measurements (e.g., measuring tree height and diameter), and is for smaller projects or highly diverse ecosystems where remote sensing might not yet be accurate enough.

To prove **additionality** in the “area-based approach” it used a “donor pool” or “control area” around the project area which shares the same pedoclimatic conditions and uses trends in this area identified with remote sensing to establish the “dynamic baseline”. Additionality in the “census-based approach” is assumed to be proven if the carbon farming practices in the area to be certified are already used in less than 15% of similar land in the region, i.e. they are not “common practices”. Additionally it must be demonstrated that specific barriers to planting (financial, technical, or institutional) could only be overcome by carbon market revenue.

The very recent, and still under consultation, changes in VM0042 have improved the way that woody biomass is accounted for and made it much more suitable for agroforestry.

Operators are currently advised to:

- **Choose VM0042** if they are taking a holistic, "whole-farm" regenerative approach, involving agroforestry and changes to soil management (e.g., reducing synthetic fertilizers, switching to no-till, adding cover crops, or improving livestock grazing). Under the new v3.0 rules, VM0042 allows operators generate credits for soil organic carbon (SOC) gains, claim the emission reductions from using less fertilizer (N₂O) and better manure management (CH₄), and account for the carbon sequestered in newly planted trees using the embedded VM0047 logic.
- **Choose VM0047** if the project is strictly a tree-planting intervention like introducing shade trees (like in coffee or cocoa), silvopasture boundary trees, or windbreaks, but you are not changing the underlying soil practices, tracking fertilizer reductions, or running complex soil carbon models. VM0042 requires rigorous (and expensive) ongoing soil sampling (guided by the new SSA Handbook) or complex biogeochemical modeling. It is much closer to the CRCF Delegated Act methodology.

The maximum allowable verification cycle for both methodologies is 5 years. If a project goes longer than this without submitting a verification report, Verra will flag it, put its buffer credits on hold, and eventually deactivate it. However, while 5 years is the hard limit, operators in VM0047, using remote sensing of biomass could potentially verify tree growth more frequently (e.g., annually) if they want credits to be generated faster.

“**Leakage**” handling differs between the two methods.

- **In VM0042** agroforestry doesn't change the official land use, and aims to maintain agricultural production. If the land is in crop production it should continue growing the same crops, with a 5% “leakage buffer” allowed. If crop yields drop significantly below the baseline, a deduction will be made to the operator’s generated carbon credits because crop production has been displaced elsewhere. VM0042 v2.1 and v2.2 allow cropland to be modified to grassland, but only once and

only if necessary to restore “Degraded Land” (SustainCERT, 2025). This can be seen as a disadvantage for Verra in the EU since conversion of cropland to grassland is generally encouraged by Member States.

- In VM0047 the focus is on activity displacement. Did afforestation, or agroforestation displace agricultural activity elsewhere? If the operator can prove that the agricultural activity moved elsewhere on the farm, or project area, with no loss of production or deforestation elsewhere, then leakage will be zero.

“**Regularity Additionality**” is again slightly different in the two methods.

- **VM0042** (farming and soil) is covered by existing CAP “enhanced conditionality” rules, but the 2023 CAP Simplification regulation removed landscape feature (including woody feature) area targets to be met by arable farmers. In the new CAP post 2027, most of the statutory “Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions” are being scrapped and replaced by laxer “Farm Stewardship” conditions or improved payments.⁹
- **VM0047** (afforestation and tree planting). Mandated reforestation is clearly not additional, and is not eligible for certification. Riparian buffers are mandatory in most EU countries but planting of trees on these is voluntary and should be eligible for certification.

Permanence under both methodologies is addressed through long crediting periods and buffer mechanisms, but VM0047 projects are typically subject to **longer monitoring and permanence expectations**, reflecting the long-lived nature of woody biomass.

In summary, VM0042 and VM0047 reflect two distinct paradigms:

- **VM0042 (ALM)**: management-driven, agriculture-centred, SOC-focused, scalable, and closely aligned with CRCF “Agriculture and Agroforestry on Mineral Soils”.
- **VM0047 (ARR)**: is biomass-driven, tree-centric, field-measurement intensive, and conceptually closer to CRCF “Afforestation and Reforestation”.

Table 6 shows the wide range of VERRA certification methodologies which have relevance to carbon farming, with an emphasis on VM0042 and VM0047.

Table 7 shows the 20 VERRA “AFOLU” (agriculture, forestry and other land use) which were active in Europe in 2025, with information on the certification status, duration, projected carbon sequestration and operators.

⁹ GAEC 8 (4% landscape features) has vanished already, GAEC 6 & 7 (soil cover and crop rotation) may be replaced by lax Member State rules, GAEC 1, 2 and 9 (permanent grassland, peatlands and environmentally sensitive areas) will be replaced by additional “agri-environmental-actions” - i.e. carrots rather than sticks.

Table 6 VERRA (VCS) Methodologies relating to Agriculture Forestry and Other Land Use (AFOLU) - showing in green the two methodologies relevant for agroforestry

Methodology Code	Title	Description / Common Project Type	Date of Last Update (Version)
REDD+ (Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation)			
VM0007	REDD+ Methodology Framework (REDD-MF)	A framework for projects reducing emissions from unplanned deforestation and degradation. One of the most widely used for large-scale forest conservation.	04 June 2024 (v1.8)
VM0009	Methodology for Avoided Ecosystem Conversion	Addresses deforestation in fragmented landscapes, often from subsistence agriculture. (Note: Inactivated as of 27 Nov 2023)	06 June 2014 (v3.0)
VM0015	Methodology for Avoided Unplanned Deforestation	A methodology to quantify emission reductions from preventing unplanned deforestation in a defined project area.	18 December 2023 (v1.2)
Improved Forest Management (IFM)			
VM0003	Methodology for Improved Forest Management through Extension of Rotation Age	Quantifies benefits of delaying timber harvest in commercial forests, allowing trees to store more carbon.	16 May 2023 (v1.3)
VM0005	Methodology for Conversion of Low-Productive Forest to High-Productive Forest	For projects that increase carbon stocks by improving the productivity of degraded or poorly managed forests.	23 July 2013 (v1.2)
VM0010	Methodology for Improved Forest Management: Conversion of Logged to Protected Forest	Designed for projects that halt commercial logging in a forest previously managed for timber, thereby protecting carbon stocks.	24 October 2024 (v1.4)
Afforestation, Reforestation, and Revegetation (ARR)			
VM0047	Afforestation, Reforestation, and Revegetation	A consolidated, modern methodology for a wide range of ARR activities, quantifying GHG removals from establishing or restoring vegetative cover.	14 May 2025 (v1.1)
VM0012	Improved Forest Management in Temperate and Boreal Forests (LtPF)	(Note: Primarily used for ARR projects in these forest types). Covers activities like species changes and thinning to enhance carbon stocks.	23 July 2013 (v1.2)
Agricultural Land Management (ALM)			
VM0017	Adoption of Sustainable Agricultural Land Management	Introduces practices like no-till and cover cropping to increase soil organic carbon. (Note: Inactivated as of 31 Mar 2023)	29 November 2011 (v1.0)
VM0021	Soil Carbon Quantification Methodology	Focuses on robust methods for measuring changes in soil organic carbon (SOC) from new agricultural practices. (Note: Inactivated as of 10 Mar 2022)	20 December 2012 (v1.0)
VM0042	Methodology for Improved Agricultural Land Management	A newer, streamlined methodology for various ALM practices that reduce emissions and enhance soil carbon.	22 January 2024 (v2.0, with clarifications issued 14 Mar 2024)
Wetlands Restoration and Conservation (WRC)			
VM0033	Methodology for Tidal Wetland and Seagrass Restoration	A key "blue carbon" methodology for projects that restore tidal wetlands (mangroves, salt marshes) and seagrass meadows.	04 September 2023 (v2.1)
VM0024	Methodology for Coastal Wetland Creation	Quantifies GHG benefits from the creation of coastal wetlands. (Note: Inactivated as of 11 Sep 2023)	30 January 2014 (v1.0)
Other Innovative Methodologies			
VM0044	Methodology for Biochar Utilization in Soil and Non-soil Applications	Quantifies carbon sequestered when biochar (a stable, carbon-rich charcoal) is produced and applied to soils or used in other long-lasting products.	13 August 2025 (v1.2 approval by ICVCM noted)

Table 7 VERRA Certified AFOLU Projects in Europe (Sep 2025)

Country	Project Name	Verra ID	Project Type	Start Year	Projected End Year	Projected reduction (tCO ₂ e per year)	Number of Beneficiaries	Project Proponent	Status
Bulgaria	Bulgarian Afforestation and Reforestation Project	1264	ARR	2013	2032	6,427	Local communities	Bulgarian Carbon OOD	Registered
France	Carbon Agri - Emissions Reductions in French Agriculture	2353	ALM	2013	2034	1,152,437	1,500+ farmers	France Carbon Agri Association	Registered
Germany	MoorFutures Peatland Rewetting	2208	Peatland Restoration	2012	2062	1,332	State landowners, public	Ministry of Agriculture and Environment	Registered
Ireland	Coilte Bodca-Ceateacha Peatland Restoration	4522	Peatland Restoration	2022	2062	20,654	State lands, public	Coillte	Under Validation
Italy	Impronta Verde Reforestation	4153	ARR	2022	2052	3,962	Local communities	Rete Clima	Under Validation
Latvia	Rimberga Agricultural Land Methane Reduction	845	ALM	2011	2021	13,000	Not specified	SIA "Rimberga"	Registered (Inactive)
Lithuania	Grouped agricultural project in Lithuania	1286	ALM	2014	2024	18,975	Participating farms	Agro-konsultacijos	Registered
Netherlands	Meadow Peat Pasture Project Vlist	2526	Wetland Restoration	2016	2046	4,082	Local farmers	Groot-van-der-Meer VOF	Registered
Portugal	Vale do Guadiana Reforestation Project	1927	ARR	2018	2048	1,450	Local landowners	Terraprima - Serviços Ambientais, SA	Registered
Romania	Lunca Birch and Oak Forest Creation	2801	ARR	2021	2071	3,150	Local community	Ocolul Silvic Codrii Beiusului	Registered
Spain	Cantabria Re-Greening Project	3097	ARR	2022	2052	8,915	Local communities	Bosques Sostenibles S.L.	Under Validation
Spain	Crece la Vida Reforestation	4192	ARR	2023	2053	225	Local landowners	Bosques Sostenibles S.L.	Under Validation
Spain	Foresta de la Serra de Castelltallat	4022	ARR	2021	2051	3,456	Local community	Bosques Sostenibles S.L.	Under Validation
Spain	Forests Alive - Reforestation in Galicia	2652	ARR	2017	2047	1,821	Local landowners	CO2 Revolution S.L.	Registered

Spain	Smart Reforestation Project I	4410	ARR	2023	2073	1,787	Not specified	Land Life Company	Under Validation
Spain	Soria CO2 Reforestation Project	985	ARR	2013	2052	23,267	Not specified	CO2 Revolution S.L.	Registered
Ukraine	ACME Grouped Afforestation Project in Ukraine	967	ARR	2010	2039	291,529	Not specified	ACME Sp. z o.o.	Registered
United Kingdom	Scottish Woodlands - Carbon Sequestration via Native Woodland Creation	1819	ARR	2018	2078	5,500	Multiple landowners	Scottish Woodlands Ltd.	Registered
United Kingdom	Thorne Moors and Hatfield Moors Peatland Restoration	2774	Peatland Restoration	2021	2051	12,600	General public, local nature reserves	Natural England	Registered
United Kingdom	UK Peatland Code - The Great North Bog	Multiple	Peatland Restoration	2021	2071	18,349	Local communities, landowners	The Peatland Programme	Registered

2.3.2 The Gold Standard

The Gold Standard is another leading international standard in the VCM, renowned for its rigorous requirements and its emphasis on ensuring projects contribute to sustainable development alongside climate mitigation (Lavreckyte, 2024). Its HQ is in Geneva, Switzerland. Its primary methodology for land-use projects is the "*Afforestation/Reforestation GHG Emissions Reduction & Sequestration Methodology*". A key applicability condition of this methodology is that it explicitly allows projects to integrate agricultural activities, stating that "All projects can include agriculture (agroforestry) or pasture (silvopasture) activities". This makes it a direct and viable pathway for certifying agroforestry projects. The Gold Standard's unique value proposition is its mandatory requirement for projects to monitor, report, and verify their contributions to at least three of the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), ensuring a holistic and positive impact.

Quantification of Removals: The quantification process is structured around "Modelling Units" (MUs), which are distinct strata within the project area that share similar characteristics (e.g., species, soil type, management regime). The net number of CO₂ certificates is calculated annually for each MU using the formula (The Gold Standard Foundation, 2013):

$$\text{CO}_2\text{-certificates} = (\text{CO}_2\text{-Fixation} - \text{Baseline} - \text{Leakage} - \text{Other Emissions}) * \text{Area.}$$

The methodology provides a detailed "*Conversion Procedure*" with formulas and default factors (e.g., wood density, Biomass Expansion Factors (BEF), Root-to-Shoot ratios) to convert the stem volume of trees (measured in cubic meters) into total carbon stock in tonnes of CO₂. The baseline is determined by conducting an inventory of the 'tree' and 'non-tree' biomass present on the land just before the project starts, and leakage (activity displacement) is accounted for upfront. This structured, model-based approach aims to provide a conservative and scientifically defensible estimate of net removals (Gold Standard, 2024).

Monitoring Procedures: Monitoring is centered on conducting periodic forest inventories to validate and, if necessary, adjust the growth models used for each MU. These inventories must be conducted according to established international guidelines (e.g., from the BioCarbon Fund or CarbonFix). A key requirement is the statistical precision of these inventories: the number of sample plots must be sufficient to achieve a maximum error of $\pm 20\%$ at a 90% confidence interval for the carbon stock estimate within each MU. If the error exceeds this threshold, the difference must be conservatively deducted from the credited amount. Crucially, and in contrast to purely carbon-focused standards, the Gold Standard mandates the development and implementation of a **Sustainability Monitoring Plan**. This plan must track the project's ongoing performance against its chosen SDG contributions, using specific indicators. This means that monitoring activities must collect data on both carbon stocks and socio-economic or environmental co-benefits (e.g., changes in local income, biodiversity indicators, soil health metrics) (Gold Standard, 2024).

Reporting Requirements: Project developers must prepare a comprehensive Project Design Document (PDD) at the outset, which includes not only the carbon accounting methodology but also a detailed Safeguarding Principles Assessment and a plan for delivering and monitoring SDG impacts. Subsequently, Annual Reports must be submitted, providing updates on both the carbon performance and the progress towards the sustainable development outcomes. Reporting is done through standardized templates and often facilitated through the Gold Standard's Impact Registry online registry system, ClimateProjects.

Verification Process: The verification process is conducted by an independent Validation and Verification Body (VVB) that is accredited by the Gold Standard (Gold Standard, 2025). The audit is holistic, assessing compliance with all aspects of the standard. The VVB not only verifies the accuracy of the carbon calculations and the forest inventory data but also rigorously assesses the project's adherence to all social and environmental safeguards and validates the reported contributions to the SDGs. This dual focus on climate and development integrity is a hallmark of the Gold Standard's verification process and is what underpins its reputation for certifying high-quality, high-impact projects.

However, there are currently no registered Gold Standard land-use or carbon farming projects in Europe. This is a significant difference from the Verra registry and reflects Gold Standard's specific focus. Historically, their "Land Use & Forests" projects, which include afforestation, reforestation, and sustainable agriculture, have been concentrated in developing countries where the potential for social co-benefits and sustainable development impacts, a core requirement of the standard, is most pronounced. The Gold Standard registry's portfolio in Europe is almost exclusively composed of high-impact renewable energy (wind, solar, biomass) and energy efficiency projects.

2.3.3 The Plan Vivo Standard

The Plan Vivo Standard is the longest-standing certification framework in the VCM focused specifically on community-based land use and forestry projects. Its HQ is in Edinburgh, Scotland. Its operational philosophy is built around empowering smallholder farmers and local communities, ensuring they are active participants and primary beneficiaries of the projects (Plan Vivo, 2025a). Agroforestry is a cornerstone activity for Plan Vivo projects, which often involve thousands of smallholders planting trees on their farms.

The standard's core methodology is PM001 "Agriculture and Forestry Carbon Benefit Assessment Methodology". This is not a monolithic document but a modular framework. It provides the overarching requirements and allows project coordinators to combine various approved modules and tools to create a carbon accounting system that is tailored to their specific project context. This modularity provides flexibility and is designed to make robust carbon accounting more accessible and affordable for smallholder-based initiatives. A key requirement of the standard is that at least 60% of the income from carbon credit sales must be channeled directly to the participating communities and smallholders (MyClimate, 2024).

Plan Vivo's MRV system has an emphasis on participatory approaches and practical, cost-effective methods. It is a modular system which relies on specific modules for different parts of the carbon calculation. Module [PU001](#) provides procedures for the estimation of baseline and project GHG removals by carbon pools from activities like agroforestry and reforestation. [PU002](#) covers net-reduction of GHG emissions from carbon pools as a result of forest protection, and [PU003](#) addresses project emissions from sources like fertilizer use or livestock.

Quantification often uses a combination of direct field measurements, scientifically-backed models, and approved default factors. An example of an approved tool is the SHAMBA, developed by the University of Edinburgh, which helps projects in the tropics quantify the climate benefits of tree planting and agroforestry interventions (Woolen et al., 2014). Demonstrating the standard's continuous evolution, Rabobank's Acorn program, which is certified under Plan Vivo, is developing a comprehensive suite of new modules specifically for small-scale agroforestry. These modules cover advanced topics such as dynamic baselines, leakage assessment, soil organic carbon, and ground-truthing, aiming to bring greater precision to smallholder projects (Plan Vivo, 2025b).

Monitoring under Plan Vivo is distinguished by its participatory MRV (P-MRV) model. Instead of relying solely on external experts, local community members and participating farmers are often trained and equipped to carry out monitoring activities themselves, such as measuring tree diameter and height. This approach significantly reduces monitoring costs, builds local technical capacity, and fosters a strong sense of project ownership. The data collected by the community is then aggregated and quality-checked by the project coordinator. As with the Gold Standard, monitoring is holistic. Projects are required to track not only carbon stock changes but also progress on key livelihood and biodiversity indicators, which are defined in consultation with the community at the project's outset.

Projects begin by submitting a Project Idea Note (PIN) for initial screening, followed by a detailed Project Design Document (PDD). The PDD outlines the project's activities, participants, technical specifications for carbon accounting, and the plan for monitoring social and biodiversity impacts. Once the project is running, the operator is responsible for submitting Annual Reports to the Plan Vivo Foundation. These reports

provide a transparent account of the project's progress against all its stated goals: climatic, social, and environmental (Abebe et al., 2011).

Verification is required within 5 years of the project registration and at least every 5 years thereafter. It is performed by an approved, independent third-party verifier. To manage costs for projects that involve a large number of dispersed smallholders, the verification process can be conducted on a statistically valid sample of the participating farms or communities. The verifier's role is to assess the project's internal monitoring system to ensure it is being implemented correctly and to confirm that the data in the annual report is credible and supported by evidence from the field. This pragmatic approach to verification makes certification financially viable for the community-focused projects that are the hallmark of the Plan Vivo standard.

There are currently no registered Plan Vivo land use projects in Europe. Its focus is on empowering smallholders and rural communities in developing countries to manage their natural resources more sustainably. The projects are designed from the ground up to provide direct benefits, such as diversified income streams and improved livelihoods, to these communities. Because of this specific focus on tropical and subtropical developing regions, the Plan Vivo project portfolio is concentrated in Africa, Latin America, and Southeast Asia. Across the three standards, Verra, Gold Standard, and Plan Vivo, key differences remain in MRV cost, co-benefit coverage, and project scale.

Across the three standards, clear trade-offs emerge between scalability, MRV cost, and the treatment of co-benefits (Table 8). In summary:

- **Verra** offers the most direct operational bridge to the CRCF, particularly through the recently revised VM0042, which closely aligns with the CRCF “Agriculture and Agroforestry on Mineral Soils” activity.
- **Gold Standard** offers the strongest framework for integrating sustainable development outcomes but has limited relevance for European agroforestry to date.
- **Plan Vivo** demonstrates how robust carbon accounting can be combined with participatory MRV and social integrity, though its focus on smallholder systems in developing countries limits direct transferability to Europe.

Together, these standards provide complementary lessons for CRCF implementation, particularly regarding hybrid MRV systems, co-benefit monitoring, and proportionality of verification requirements.

Table 8: Comparison of the three main carbon farming certification standards.

	Verra – VCS (VM0042 & VM0047)	Gold Standard (AF/R Methodology)	Plan Vivo (PM001)
Headquarters / Governance	Washington DC, USA; largest global VCM standard-setter	Geneva, Switzerland; NGO-led with strong sustainability mandate	Edinburgh, UK; foundation focused on community-based land use
Primary Objective	Quantification and issuance of high-integrity GHG credits at scale	Climate mitigation plus verified sustainable development outcomes	Climate mitigation with strong livelihood, biodiversity, and equity outcomes
Relevance to Agroforestry	High (via VM0042 ALM; partial via VM0047 census-based ARR)	Explicitly allows agroforestry and silvopasture	Agroforestry is a core activity
Land-use Assumption	VM0042: continuing agricultural land use; VM0047: tree establishment (often implying land-use change)	Flexible land-use systems integrating trees, crops, and pasture	Smallholder agricultural and agroforestry landscapes
Main Carbon Pools	VM0042: SOC, N ₂ O, CH ₄ (biomass secondary); VM0047: biomass-centric (all IPCC pools)	Biomass-focused with optional soil carbon	Biomass and SOC using modular accounting
Quantification Approach	VM0042: model-based SOC + activity data; VM0047: per-tree or plot-based biomass accounting	Model-based using Modelling Units (MUs) and forest inventories	Mixed: field measurements, models, default factors (modular tools)
Baseline Setting	VM0042: dynamic, management-based baseline; VM0047: zero or near-zero biomass baseline	Pre-project biomass inventory; conservative counterfactual	Project-specific baseline defined through approved modules
Additionality Logic	VM0042: behavioural/management change; VM0047: tree establishment or land-cover change	Financial, legal, and common-practice tests	Strongly contextual; assumes barriers faced by smallholders
Monitoring (MRV)	VM0042: model-driven + sampling + EO; VM0047: intensive field monitoring (DBH, height, survival)	Periodic forest inventories with statistical precision thresholds	Participatory MRV (P-MRV) led by communities
MRV Cost & Complexity	VM0042: low–moderate; VM0047: high	High	Low–moderate
Leakage Treatment	VM0042: explicit leakage assessment; VM0047 census-based often exempt	Leakage assessed and deducted upfront	Addressed through project design and community safeguards
Permanence & Reversal Risk	Buffer pools and long crediting periods; longer obligations for ARR	Long-term commitments; conservative deductions	Managed through project rules and community agreements
Co-benefits & SDGs	Optional / secondary	Mandatory (minimum 3 SDGs monitored and verified)	Central (livelihoods, biodiversity, equity)
Verification	Independent VVBs; validation + periodic verification	Independent VVBs; holistic audit including safeguards and SDGs	Independent verification every ≤5 years (sampling allowed)
Project Scale	Medium to very large; aggregator-friendly	Medium to large	Smallholder and community-scale
European Deployment	Yes (notably ARR and ALM projects)	No land-use projects in Europe	No projects in Europe
Alignment with CRCF	High (especially VM0042); VM0047 partially aligned but conceptually ambiguous for agroforestry	Conceptually aligned on sustainability; MRV heavy for EU farming	Strong on social integrity; limited EU policy alignment
Key Strength	Scalability and methodological maturity	Highest integrity on sustainability and safeguards	Cost-effective, inclusive, community-driven
Key Limitation	Agroforestry split across ALM/ARR creates ambiguity	High MRV burden; limited EU uptake	Limited applicability to EU commercial farming

2.3.4 National Voluntary Registries

A. Southern Europe

Spain's *Registro de Huella de Carbono, Compensación y Proyectos de Absorción de CO2* was established by Royal Decree in 2014, and is a public, voluntary registry managed by the Spanish Office for Climate Change (MAGRAMA, 2016). It is used exclusively for domestic Land Use, Land-Use Change, and Forestry (LULUCF) activities. Eligible land-use projects are limited to two types: a) **afforestation and reforestation on land** that has been without forest cover¹⁰ since at least 1989, and b) the **restoration of forest areas affected by fire**. The registry imposes strict requirements, including a minimum project area of 1 hectare, a 30-year permanence, and the mandatory use of a specific calculation methodology provided by the registry itself, which is based on IPCC guidelines. The register is designed to provide legal certainty and directly support Spain's national climate strategy, which relies on LULUCF sinks to absorb residual emissions to achieve its 2050 net-zero target (Trullenque, 2024). Organizations can register their carbon footprint in one section of the registry and then purchase credits from registered absorption projects to offset their emissions in another. This highly standardized approach ensures consistency but offers little of the flexibility and stakeholder-led innovation seen in the French Label Bas Carbone (qv). It highlights a fundamental design choice for carbon registries: a trade-off between centralized control and standardization versus decentralized flexibility and innovation.

Italy. Carbon farming registries in Italy are proceeding down two routes. **On the public side**, a national registry for carbon credits in agriculture and forestry has been established under guidance of the *Consiglio per la Ricerca in Agricoltura e l'Analisi dell'Economia Agraria* (CREA) by the art 45 of law L. 41 of 21 April 2023. The guidelines were adopted by Decreto 15 ottobre 2025 and published in the Gazzetta Ufficiale (Serie Generale n. 268, 18 novembre 2025) under the title "*Adozione delle linee guida volte a individuare i criteri per l'attuazione del registro pubblico dei crediti di carbonio generati su base volontaria dal settore agricolo e forestale nazionale - Sezione forestale*". It was created to reward those "who carry out reforestation and sustainable agricultural and forestry management activities in addition to those required by current European and national legislation in the sector" (ConsulenzaAgricola, 2023). In practice, this excludes from crediting any practices that are already mandatory under EU or national law, including CAP conditionality (GAEC standards), statutory forest protection rules, LULUCF accounting obligations, national forest legislation, regional forest management plans, compulsory environmental compensation measures, and obligations linked to protected areas. Eligible activities are therefore limited to voluntary actions that exceed regulatory baselines, such as non-mandatory afforestation or agroforestry on agricultural land, forest management practices going beyond legal minimum requirements, and soil carbon practices surpassing baseline GAEC standards.

While broadly consistent with CRCF additionality principles, this approach is currently applied through national legal interpretation rather than harmonised EU-level methodologies. In parallel, **a private market** is emerging based on platforms like the [Registro Crediti di Carbonio](#) (RCC) and [Carbon Planet](#). Both are using blockchain technology to ensure the unique identification of carbon units and to align their standards with the emerging CRCF criteria. It is not known how the Italian public registry interacts with the private registries. In particular, there are no established rules on mutual recognition, avoidance of overlap, or credit fungibility. Furthermore, it remains unclear how either the public or private Italian registries will interface with the EU-wide geospatial registry mandated under the CRCF Regulation and to be operational by 2028. In the absence of early alignment, this institutional ambiguity risks creating fragmentation and potential

¹⁰ 'Forest' areas are defined as: minimum 1 ha, minimum 20% canopy cover at maturity, 3m tree height at maturity, and compulsory to have a forest management plan. The Spanish "Ley de Montes" has a very broad definition of "forest land" and includes as forest very large areas of "dehesa" and scrub vegetation. A study conducted by EURAF ([Policy Briefing #15](#)) showed that the forest map produced by the Spanish *Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico* (MITECO) indicates almost ten times more forest in the Region of Extremadura than is recorded as "forest" in the Spanish Land Parcel Identification System (SIGPAC) for the same region.

double counting, underscoring the need for clearer national guidance on interoperability with CRCF certification and Union-level registries.

B. Western Europe

Austria does not currently operate a dedicated national carbon farming registry for agricultural or forestry carbon credits. Nevertheless, national policy frameworks increasingly recognise the role of agroforestry, sustainable forest management, and soil-based carbon sequestration as part of the country's broader climate mitigation strategy. The Austrian Carbon Management Strategy (2024) identifies land-based carbon removals as a key pillar of climate neutrality, highlighting forests, soils, and tree-based systems in agricultural landscapes as important carbon sinks. While the strategy does not establish a carbon credit registry, it emphasises improved carbon accounting, MRV development, and compatibility with EU-level certification frameworks. In agriculture, the [ÖPUL programme](#), Austria's agri-environmental and climate scheme under the CAP, supports practices relevant to carbon farming, including permanent soil cover, reduced tillage, and tree-based landscape elements, but functions as a subsidy mechanism rather than a system for generating tradable carbon credits. Agroforestry systems are therefore incentivised primarily through public payments rather than carbon markets. In parallel, the [Climate and Energy Fund](#) has financed pilot projects on carbon farming, carbon removals, and innovative land-use practices, including tree-based and agroforestry-related interventions, contributing to early experience with MRV approaches. At present, voluntary carbon projects involving forestry or agroforestry in Austria are typically developed under international standards or NGO-led initiatives rather than through a domestic public registry. With the implementation of the EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming (CRCF) framework and the planned EU geospatial registry by 2028, Austria is expected to progressively align its agroforestry-relevant MRV systems and policy instruments with Union-level certification requirements, potentially paving the way for more formalised national approaches to carbon farming certification.

In Belgium carbon farming uptake has been advanced predominantly through voluntary and collaborative initiatives rather than a formal public carbon registry. Notably, the Flemish "[Carbon Farming](#)" initiative, developed through a partnership including the regional government Claire, Boerenbond, and the Bodemkundige Dienst van België, facilitates carbon sequestration in agricultural soils by matching farmers with companies willing to finance carbon storage, with financial support linked to CO₂ removed and stored in soil organic carbon. This collaboration provides an early example of local carbon credit valuation and farmer compensation in practice in Flanders. In addition, Belgian farmers are participating in the EU-wide [LIFE Carbon Farming project](#), which aims to reduce the carbon footprint of mixed crop-livestock systems through result-based financing mechanisms and shared MRV tools, with Belgium among the partner countries implementing and testing low-carbon farming practices on hundreds of farms. Beyond national borders, Belgium has been involved in the [Interreg North Sea Region "Carbon Farming"](#) project, which explored barriers, incentives, and business models for carbon sequestration in agricultural soils and engaged farmers across the North Sea region, including Belgian stakeholders, to stimulate adoption and knowledge exchange on carbon farming techniques. Together, these initiatives demonstrate a **grassroots and pilot-driven approach** to carbon farming in Belgium, focused on farmer engagement, soil carbon sequestration, and the co-development of financing models, while also contributing insights to broader European policy development on carbon farming.

France's Label Bas Carbone (LBC), or "Low-Carbon Label," is a certification framework established in 2018 by the French Ministry for Ecological Transition (Steffan, 2023) and managed by them. It is a national tool designed to certify and promote GHG emission reduction and sequestration projects located within France, thereby helping to achieve the country's national climate targets and channeling private and public finance toward local projects (Duault, 2025). The LBC operates across multiple sectors, including agriculture, forestry, construction, and transport (Steffan, 2023). It is built upon a series of government-approved methodologies that provide the technical rules for different project types. While a dedicated, comprehensive "in parcel agroforestry" methodology is still reported to be in development, and uses root modelling to predict deep-carbon sequestration. Several finalised methodologies are directly applicable to agroforestry systems and practices. The "Haies" (Hedges) methodology, developed by the Chamber of

Agriculture of Pays de la Loire, allows for the certification of carbon sequestered in newly planted or sustainably managed hedgerows. The "*Plantation de vergers*" (Orchard Planting) methodology applies to planting new orchards on previously uncultivated land. Furthermore, forestry methodologies such as "Boisement" (Afforestation) can be applied to agroforestry projects that involve planting forest stands on agricultural land. This suite of methodologies provides several avenues for French farmers to certify agroforestry-related activities. Quantification of Removals: Each approved methodology specifies its own detailed rules for defining the baseline scenario ("scénario de référence") and quantifying the project's climate impact. For instance, the "Haies" method provides tools to calculate the carbon stored in the above- and below-ground biomass of the hedge based on its length, height, width, and species composition. The quantification process is often supported by specific calculation tools that are recognized by the methodology, such as the CAP'2ER tool for agricultural emissions diagnostics (L'Hôte, 2022). The overarching principle is to calculate the net benefit of the project compared to what would have happened in its absence.

- **Monitoring Procedures:** The project developer (e.g., a farmer, cooperative, or project aggregator) is responsible for implementing a monitoring plan as described in the project's labeling application. This involves tracking the implementation of the project activities (e.g., dates of planting, length of hedges managed, species planted) and collecting all necessary data to perform the quantification calculations required by the chosen methodology.
- **Reporting Requirements:** The process begins with the operator notifying the competent regional authority, the *Direction Régionale de l'Environnement, de l'Aménagement et du Logement* (DREAL), of the project (MASA, 2022). The operator then submits a full application file for labeling. Once the project is completed (after a 5-year period for agriculture or 30 years for forestry), the developer submits a monitoring report and a request for the verification of the emission reductions achieved (Duault, 2025).
- **Verification Process:** The reported emission reductions or removals must be verified by an independent, accredited auditor. Based on a satisfactory audit, the regional prefect officially recognizes the GHG reductions. These recognized reductions are then recorded in a dedicated public registry, ensuring transparency and preventing double counting. These credits are intended for voluntary use and cannot be used for compliance with the EU ETS (Triple Performance, 2025) .

The existence of a national standard like the LBC illustrates a fundamental dynamic in the carbon market. It offers the benefit of close alignment with national policies and stakeholders, which can facilitate access to domestic funding sources like CAP co-financing. However, credits generated under a national scheme are generally not fungible on the international VCM, where standards like Verra and Gold Standard dominate. This presents a strategic choice for operators in France: pursue LBC certification to tap into local demand and policy support, or seek certification under an international standard to access a larger global pool of corporate buyers. This suggests a future where national and international schemes may coexist (e.g. both registered in the CRCF), serving different market segments. The French Label Bas Carbone methodologies on hedgerows and orchards offer transferable models for CRCF agroforestry pilots and could be adapted to other member states.

Germany's climate policy has historically focused on industrial decarbonization through large-scale public funding for technologies like hydrogen and CCS, and compliance mechanisms like the EU ETS (Anon, 2025a). Carbon farming and forestry removals have been promoted through federal research and demonstration projects, such as the Federal Humus Programme, but without a national credit-issuing mechanism (BMEL, 2024). Consequently, the voluntary market is dominated by international standards like Verra and is the primary avenue for land-sector carbon projects in Germany (Streck et al., 2025). Verra has registered forestry projects in the country and is verifying large-scale soil carbon projects across Europe that include German farms. This delay in developing a national standard suggests that Germany is awaiting the forthcoming CRCF to provide the necessary integrity and structure to scale up private investment in carbon farming.

Ireland does not yet have an operational registry but is in the advanced stages of creating a national Carbon

Farming Framework, having completed public consultations in late 2023 (DAFM, 2023). The Irish government is seeking to reward farmers not just for carbon sequestration but also for co-benefits such as improved biodiversity and water quality. The state agricultural research and extension agency, Teagasc, is participating in several EU-wide projects like "LIFE Carbon Farming" which has ambitious plans for 700 farms across Europe, generating carbon credits with low carbon practices and technologies (Teagasc, 2025). Carbon farming issues in Ireland are discussed in a recent research paper for the Irish Parliament (Brennan, 2025).

In Luxembourg, formal carbon farming registries or carbon credit markets are not yet established at the national level. National climate policy has historically prioritised emissions reductions, with carbon removals playing only a limited role in earlier planning documents; for example, Luxembourg's National Energy and Climate Plan ([NECP 2024](#)) initially made little reference to carbon removal, though more recent updates have begun to include it among a broader set of mitigation measures while the LULUCF sector remains a modest net sink. The Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Viticulture emphasises the need for agricultural methods to adapt to environmental requirements and climate change to guarantee sustainable production that protects natural resources and biodiversity, reflecting a growing recognition of the climate role of land management practices including soil carbon enhancement. Luxembourg's CAP Strategic Plan also identifies carbon sequestration as an objective alongside reducing greenhouse gas and ammonia emissions within agriculture, although specific carbon farming instruments are not detailed in a registry or crediting framework at this stage. While the national policy architecture does not yet include a carbon credit registry analogous to systems in France or Spain, Luxembourg's climate and agricultural strategies signal an intent to strengthen forest management, soil restoration, and agricultural practices that increase carbon sequestration, particularly for nature-based removals complementing engineered approaches. In practice, carbon farming uptake in Luxembourg currently occurs through participation in EU-wide and regional initiatives (e.g. LIFE Carbon Farming), research programmes focused on sustainability and MRV in agriculture, and collaborative networks rather than through a dedicated domestic registry. This reflects the early stage of policy evolution in the country and the broader trend in several Member States where strategic frameworks precede operational registry development. With the implementation of the EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification Framework (CRCF) and the planned Union geospatial registry by 2028, Luxembourg is expected to integrate its national climate-agriculture policy instruments more explicitly into EU-level certification and registry systems, potentially enabling future national carbon farming certification once methodological and administrative arrangements are in place.

Netherlands, the Dutch approach to carbon farming is characterized not only by a strong science-based MRV foundation, but also by an increasingly active domestic voluntary carbon market. Rather than relying on a single national credit registry, the Netherlands currently hosts several certifiers with their own methodologies and registries, notably Stichting Nationale Koolstofmarkt (SNK) (Anon, 2026d), Open Natural Carbon Accounting (ONCRA) (Anon, 2026b), and Proba. SNK (Anon, 2026c), established with public support, has played an important role in structuring the Dutch voluntary carbon market, while ONCRA and Proba have developed alternative certification frameworks and registries for land-based and biobased carbon removal projects. Importantly, most Dutch projects are not certified directly under international standards, instead they use method documents developed by the certifiers above, although these may draw on international guidance. Dutch registries also show a diversity of project types, ranging from peatland and mineral-soil interventions to biobased construction value chains. A distinctive feature of the Dutch system is the parallel development of public demand-side support (Arkema, 2024). In addition to voluntary market activity, the government has introduced procurement schemes for carbon certificates linked to biobased building materials, under which the National Green Fund purchases certificates from growers and processors (MaterialDistrict, 2025). Recent tender documentation indicates a new 2026 tranche with a budget of €2.5 million and a purchase price corridor of €95–110 per certificate, explicitly aimed at stimulating both the voluntary carbon market and the biobased construction sector (Oerlemans, 2025). Public information around the scheme indicates that certification routes such as SNK and ONCRA are part of the emerging implementation landscape. On the MRV side, the Netherlands has invested heavily in Tier 3 approaches tailored to different soil types. For peatland soils, the National Research Programme on Greenhouse Gas Dynamics in Peatlands and Organic Soils (NOBV) (Anon, 2026a) was launched to improve

understanding and prediction of greenhouse-gas emissions; this work underpins advanced modelling approaches such as SOMERS, which is currently strongest for CO₂, while methane and nitrous oxide remain more challenging areas for further development. For mineral soils, the Praktijktool BodemCoolstof (Soil Carbon Tool) (Hendriks et al., arch 2023), developed under the Slim Landgebruik programme, uses a RothC-based calculation core and combines default datasets with parcel-specific inputs such as soil organic matter, clay content, crop rotation and yields via the FarmMaps platform (Farmmaps, 2026). In practice, Dutch certification methods such as SNK rely on differentiated MRV approaches, using SOMERS for peat soils and BodemCoolstof-type modelling for mineral soils. Overall, the Dutch experience suggests that the Netherlands may bring to the CRCF a particularly data-rich and methodologically demanding approach. At the same time, an important gap remains: while peatland and mineral-soil modelling frameworks are comparatively advanced, a widely accepted Tier 3 model for agroforestry is still lacking. This makes the Dutch case especially relevant for DigitAF, which could help reflect on how agroforestry MRV can evolve toward the same level of methodological maturity needed for robust CRCF implementation.

United Kingdom. In the UK, validated woodland and peatland carbon units have been created through the UK Woodland Carbon Code and the UK Peatland Code. The Woodland Carbon Code was initiated in 2011 and the Peatland Code was initiated in 2015. A woodland carbon unit (WCU) is defined as a tonne of carbon dioxide which has been sequestered in a Woodland Carbon Code-certified woodland. A peatland carbon unit (PCU) is defined as a tonne of carbon dioxide equivalent to emissions reduction recorded by the Peatland Code. At present, the current maximum duration that growers can commit to carbon storage in the Woodland Carbon Code is 100 years. All projects certified in the UK Peatland Code and Woodland Carbon Code are recorded on the UK Land Carbon Registry (Anon, 2026e). At present, in the UK, there are only a limited number of Woodland Carbon Units available for purchase as they only become available once the trees reach a certain age. In addition, the Woodland Carbon Code can issue a tradeable pending issuance units (PIUs). These are effectively promissory notes which confirm that the ownership of a given amount of a woodland's future capacity to capture carbon. From year 5 after woodland planting and then every 10 years after, an owner can start to convert PIUs to WCUs. However this process requires a third-party verification. The UK Woodland and Peatland Codes provide useful lessons on long-term permanence commitments and transparent registries that could inform future EU and international frameworks

C. Northern Europe

Denmark is pursuing a dual-track carbon removal strategy combining large-scale technological removals with continued support for land-based mitigation. The national CCS Strategy positions Denmark as a future European hub for carbon capture and storage, underpinned by substantial public investment in Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS) and Direct Air Carbon Capture and Storage (DACCS). These activities are primarily financed through the NECCS Fund, which operates via competitive tenders to procure high-durability removals aligned with Denmark's climate neutrality targets. In parallel, Denmark's Climate Programme 2022 continues to support forestry and land-use measures, including afforestation and improved forest management, as part of the national contribution from the LULUCF sector. These interventions are funded through public climate and agricultural instruments rather than through a domestic carbon crediting scheme, and agroforestry-type systems remain incentivised mainly via CAP-linked payments and national climate programmes rather than market-based credits. Denmark also maintains a national accounting infrastructure through the [Danish Kyoto Registry](#), operated by the Danish Business Authority. This registry serves compliance purposes under international climate reporting frameworks and does not function as a voluntary carbon market platform for agricultural or forestry credits. As in Sweden, Denmark's approach prioritises state-procured, permanent removals while land-based sequestration remains embedded in public policy instruments rather than tradable registries. Voluntary land-use projects therefore continue to rely on international standards where applicable. With the forthcoming implementation of the CRCF and the EU-wide geospatial registry by 2028, Denmark is expected to progressively align its forestry and agricultural MRV systems with Union-level certification requirements, potentially enabling future CRCF-certified agroforestry and soil carbon activities alongside its nationally supported BECCS and DACCS programmes.

Estonia's land-use carbon market is currently driven almost entirely by private voluntary initiatives rather than public registry systems. Innovative platforms such as Arbonics have emerged in response to perceived shortcomings in traditional international standards, seeking to offer more transparent, landowner-centred forestry carbon projects with improved MRV and permanence safeguards (Vardar 2025). These initiatives focus primarily on afforestation, reforestation and improved forest management, positioning Estonia as an early adopter of digitally enabled VCM approaches in the Baltic region. At larger scales, project developers such as Ecobase are aggregating land across Estonia and neighbouring Baltic states to supply forestry-based credits under international standards, notably Verra. This aggregation model enables economies of scale but has also raised concerns about ecological integrity and land-use conflicts. Recent media coverage has highlighted cases where carbon credit projects risk undermining biodiversity values, including reported impacts on rare bird habitats, underscoring the limitations of current VCM governance when biodiversity safeguards are weak or inconsistently applied. Estonia does not yet operate a national public registry for agricultural or forestry carbon credits, and land-based projects therefore remain embedded in international voluntary markets. This context illustrates both the dynamism and the risks of privately led carbon farming deployment in the absence of harmonised public frameworks. With the forthcoming implementation of the EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification Framework (CRCF) and the Union geospatial registry by 2028, Estonia's existing private initiatives are likely to face increasing pressure to align with EU sustainability safeguards, additionality rules and spatial traceability requirements. In this sense, Estonia represents a test case for how CRCF may help rebalance market-driven forestry carbon projects toward stronger environmental integrity, including clearer protection for biodiversity alongside carbon sequestration.

Finland combines strong public investment in research and innovation with emerging private voluntary carbon initiatives, positioning itself as one of the most advanced Member States in preparing for CRCF-aligned land-based removals. A cornerstone of Finland's approach is the national "*Catch the Carbon*" (*Hiilestä kiinni*) programme, which has funded more than 150 research, development and innovation projects aimed at strengthening the scientific basis for climate-smart agriculture and forestry. The programme focuses on improving MRV methodologies, developing scalable soil carbon and forest carbon solutions, and supporting farmer-led experimentation with regenerative practices. Complementary initiatives such as the Carbon Action Network bring together farmers, researchers and businesses to test cultivation methods and co-develop scientifically grounded approaches to verifying soil carbon sequestration, directly addressing one of the key implementation challenges anticipated under CRCF. Alongside public RDI efforts, private actors are beginning to offer voluntary land-use credits. Platforms such as [Green Carbon Finland](#) market forestry-based "climate units" to corporate buyers, using ISO-aligned accounting approaches and project-level monitoring to quantify removals from afforestation and improved forest management. While these credits currently operate outside a national public registry, they demonstrate growing private-sector engagement in Finnish land-based carbon markets. Finland is also at the forefront of developing biodiversity valuation concepts, including nationally anchored biodiversity units, reflecting a broader policy interest in linking carbon removals with ecosystem outcomes. Taken together, Finland's combination of large-scale public RDI investment, participatory on-farm pilots, and early private market activity provides a strong foundation for future CRCF implementation. With the planned EU geospatial registry and delegated MRV methodologies, Finland is well positioned to transition existing soil and forestry initiatives toward harmonised EU certification, potentially integrating agroforestry, soil carbon and forest management within a coherent CRCF-aligned framework.

Latvia's carbon farming activities are currently centred on peatland restoration and climate-responsible agriculture, driven primarily by EU-funded pilot programmes rather than a national carbon credit registry. A flagship initiative is the [LIFE PeatCarbon](#) project, which focuses on rewetting drained peatlands and restoring degraded organic soils to reduce emissions and enhance long-term carbon storage. Given the high mitigation potential of peatland restoration in Latvia, this programme represents one of the country's most impactful land-use climate interventions. In parallel, Latvia participates in the LIFE CRAFT (Climate-Responsible Agriculture and Food Systems) project, which supports farmers in adopting low-emission practices, improving soil management, and integrating climate considerations into agricultural production. [LIFE CRAFT](#) emphasises farm-level experimentation, advisory support, and MRV development,

providing practical experience with result-oriented approaches to agricultural mitigation. Together, these LIFE projects illustrate Latvia's emphasis on publicly supported demonstration and capacity-building rather than market-based carbon crediting. At present, voluntary carbon projects in Latvia are typically developed through international standards or regional aggregators rather than a domestic registry framework. However, the strong focus on peatland rewetting and soil-based mitigation aligns closely with CRCF activity categories, particularly for organic soils. With the forthcoming implementation of the EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification Framework and the Union geospatial registry by 2028, Latvia's LIFE-supported pilots are well positioned to transition toward CRCF-aligned certification. The country's experience with peatland MRV and climate-responsible farming practices could therefore form an important foundation for scaling verified land-based removals, while ensuring consistency with EU sustainability safeguards.

Lithuania's climate policy framework is anchored in its national strategy to achieve climate neutrality by 2050, which recognises carbon sequestration in land-based sinks as an integral part of meeting long-term mitigation goals. According to recent analyses, Lithuania's LULUCF sector contributes to national greenhouse gas balances, and the strategic framing of carbon farming and soil carbon enhancements is increasingly incorporated into broader policy discussions as part of the climate neutrality pathway ([Zero Tracker, Lithuania COU-0067](#)). Although a dedicated national carbon credit registry has not yet been established, the country's overarching climate targets create an enabling policy environment for scaling land-based removals. At the project level, private sector engagement has been growing, with ambitious partnerships emerging to generate farm-based carbon credits and to mobilise investment in regenerative agricultural practices. Notably, Lithuania has been associated with a €100 million initiative aimed at producing soil carbon and land-use credits tied to farm-level sequestration activities, signalling robust market interest and private financing potential. However, like other Baltic states, Lithuania currently relies on the voluntary carbon market (VCM) and international standards for carbon project development rather than on a formal public registry mechanism. Voluntary projects, particularly those involving afforestation, soil organic carbon improvements, or peatland restoration, are typically registered under standards such as Verra, reflecting the region's engagement with international carbon markets. Looking forward, the implementation of the EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification Framework (CRCF) and the establishment of an interoperable Union geospatial registry by 2028 are likely to catalyse the transition from predominantly voluntary activity toward harmonised EU-aligned certification. Lithuania's climate neutrality commitments, combined with growing private sector participation and pilot MRV experience, position the country to integrate its land-based removal activities into CRCF-compatible frameworks, potentially expanding the scope for agroforestry, soil carbon projects and other sustainable land management approaches that deliver verified climate and biodiversity benefits.

Sweden has adopted a highly proactive state-led approach to carbon removals, with a particular emphasis on permanent, technology-based solutions alongside land-based sinks. Central to this strategy is large-scale public funding for Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS) through competitive reverse auction mechanisms. The government has earmarked substantial resources, in the order of tens of billions of SEK, to support BECCS projects at industrial facilities, with the explicit objective of procuring verified durable removals that can contribute to net-zero goals and supply credits into voluntary markets (Tracker Carbon Gap, Sweden). These procurement schemes aim to catalyse private investment in long-lived capture and storage infrastructure while providing price discovery and volume certainty for producers of engineered removals. Sweden's Industrial Leap (Industriellt Klimasprång) initiative complements these procurement mechanisms by offering co-funding and innovation support for climate tech development, particularly in sectors where emissions are hard to abate. This broader industrial strategy situates Sweden at the forefront of public support for climate innovation policies that combine mitigation with economic competitiveness, reinforcing the synergies between decarbonisation and carbon removals at scale. Despite this strong orientation toward technological removals, land-based climate action remains significant within Sweden's overall mitigation portfolio. Forestry contributes substantially to the national LULUCF sink, and forest management practice improvements, afforestation and avoided deforestation are embedded in national climate planning. However, Sweden does not currently operate a dedicated national carbon farming registry for agricultural or forest credits. Land-based projects continue to rely on international voluntary standards

or on national incentive programmes rather than on a domestic tradable registry. Sweden's dual emphasis on high-durability engineered removals and continued support for land-based mitigation illustrates a diversified national strategy. With the unfolding implementation of the EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification Framework (CRCF) and the Union geospatial registry by 2028, Sweden's substantial experience with both engineered and land-based removals suggests that it will be well placed to integrate land-sector activities, including forestry, soil carbon and potentially agroforestry, into harmonised EU-level certification streams while maintaining support for high-integrity technological removals at scale.

D. Eastern Europe

Bulgaria's engagement with carbon removals is framed primarily through national climate policy rather than a formal public carbon farming registry. The country's Long-Term Climate Mitigation Strategy identifies land use, land-use change and forestry (LULUCF) as an important contributor to Bulgaria's pathway toward climate neutrality, alongside growing interest in technological removals such as carbon capture and storage. This is reinforced by the inclusion of climate-relevant land management measures within Bulgaria's CAP Strategic Plan, which supports soil protection, sustainable forestry and landscape features, but operates through practice-based subsidies rather than outcome-based carbon certification. On the technological side, Bulgaria is exploring CCS through initiatives such as the ANRAV CCS project, signalling early engagement with permanent removal pathways, although these remain at pilot stage. In parallel, land-based carbon activities are emerging mainly through voluntary and regional initiatives rather than national governance structures. Notably, Bulgaria hosts the Balkan Carbon Credit Registry (BCCR), accessible via Balkan Carbon Credit Registry, a nascent regional platform aiming to support agricultural and nature-based carbon projects across Southeast Europe with an emphasis on transparency and farmer participation. While still small in scale, BCCR illustrates growing private-sector interest in carbon farming in the absence of a state-operated registry. According to Carbon Gap's national analysis, Bulgaria currently lacks dedicated domestic mechanisms for issuing land-based carbon credits, relying instead on EU-funded pilots and voluntary market activity. As a result, projects involving soil carbon or agroforestry are typically developed under international standards or through regional platforms rather than within a Bulgarian public framework. Looking ahead, Bulgaria's combination of climate policy commitments, CAP-supported land management measures, early CCS exploration and emerging voluntary registries positions it as a transitional case within Eastern Europe. With the rollout of the EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification Framework (CRCF) and the Union geospatial registry by 2028, Bulgaria is likely to move from fragmented pilot activity toward more structured CRCF-aligned certification, potentially enabling agroforestry, soil carbon and forest management projects to access harmonised EU markets while maintaining consistency with national climate objectives.

The Czech Republic's approach to carbon removals is currently anchored in national climate policy instruments rather than in a dedicated public carbon farming registry. The country's Climate Protection Policy and National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP) both recognise the role of land use and emerging carbon farming practices in achieving long-term climate objectives, explicitly referencing soil carbon enhancement and sustainable land management as part of the mitigation portfolio. However, these commitments remain largely strategic, with implementation occurring through CAP measures and research programmes rather than through market-based carbon certification. Agricultural and forestry climate action in Czechia is therefore primarily supported via CAP-funded agri-environmental schemes, which incentivise practices relevant to carbon farming, such as grassland preservation, soil conservation and landscape features, but operate on a practice-based subsidy model rather than outcome-based carbon accounting. Agroforestry is increasingly discussed within policy and research circles, yet it is not currently embedded within a national carbon credit framework. On the technological side, Czechia is exploring permanent removals through Bio-CCS research initiatives, reflecting a broader regional interest in engineered solutions alongside land-based sinks. According to Carbon Gap's national analysis, the Czech Republic does not yet have a domestic registry for carbon removals, and voluntary projects are typically developed under international standards or remain at pilot stage. As with other Central and Eastern European Member States, Czechia's readiness for CRCF implementation is being shaped largely by EU-funded research and demonstration projects, which are building MRV capacity and stakeholder engagement ahead of formal

certification pathways. With the rollout of the EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification Framework and the Union geospatial registry by 2028, the Czech Republic is expected to progressively align its soil carbon and agroforestry-relevant practices with EU-level methodologies, potentially enabling a transition from policy-level recognition to operational carbon farming certification.

Croatia's engagement with carbon removals is primarily through national climate policy instruments rather than a dedicated public carbon farming registry. The country's Low-Carbon Development Strategy and National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP) both highlight the importance of the LULUCF sector in achieving long-term decarbonisation objectives, with measures focused on forest management, afforestation, soil protection and the preservation of natural carbon sinks. These strategies recognise land-based sequestration as a supporting pillar of Croatia's climate neutrality pathway, but implementation remains largely policy-driven and subsidy-based rather than market-oriented. In agriculture and forestry, climate-relevant actions are supported mainly through CAP mechanisms and national programmes, which incentivise sustainable land management practices without generating tradable carbon credits. Agroforestry and tree-based systems are increasingly acknowledged for their potential to enhance resilience and carbon storage, yet they are not currently embedded within a formal certification or registry framework. Alongside land-based mitigation, Croatia is exploring technological removal pathways through pilot initiatives such as geothermal CCS research projects, reflecting early interest in permanent storage solutions. However, these remain at an experimental stage and have not yet translated into operational carbon markets. According to Carbon Gap's national analysis, Croatia does not operate a domestic carbon removals registry, and voluntary land-use projects typically rely on international standards or EU-funded demonstration programmes. As with other Central and Eastern European Member States, Croatia's preparedness for the EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification Framework (CRCF) is being shaped primarily through participation in EU research and capacity-building initiatives. With the planned implementation of CRCF delegated acts and the Union geospatial registry by 2028, Croatia is expected to progressively align its LULUCF-related measures with EU certification requirements. This could open pathways for agroforestry, soil carbon and forest management activities to transition from policy-supported practices toward verified carbon removals, provided that MRV capacity and farmer engagement continue to develop.

Hungary's engagement with carbon removals is primarily articulated through national climate policy frameworks rather than through a dedicated public carbon farming registry. The National Clean Development Strategy places significant emphasis on the LULUCF sector as a contributor to Hungary's long-term climate objectives, highlighting forests, soils and sustainable land management as key mitigation assets. This strategic focus reflects growing recognition of land-based sequestration potential, although implementation remains largely embedded within CAP instruments and national environmental programmes rather than market-based carbon certification. Agricultural and forestry climate actions are mainly supported via practice-based subsidies, including afforestation, forest management improvements and soil conservation measures. Agroforestry is increasingly discussed within adaptation and mitigation contexts, particularly as a tool for enhancing landscape resilience, yet it is not currently operationalised within a national carbon credit framework. Hungary has also established platforms such as the Forestry Climate Adaptation Forum, which brings together policymakers, researchers and practitioners to address climate risks in forest ecosystems and to explore adaptive management strategies. These initiatives contribute to capacity building and knowledge exchange but do not generate tradable carbon units. According to Carbon Gap's national analysis, Hungary does not yet operate a domestic registry for carbon removals, and voluntary land-use projects are typically pursued under international standards or remain at pilot stage. As with other Central and Eastern European Member States, Hungary's readiness for CRCF implementation is therefore being shaped primarily by EU-funded research and demonstration activities. With the rollout of the EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification Framework (CRCF) and the Union geospatial registry by 2028, Hungary is expected to progressively align its LULUCF-related practices with EU certification requirements, potentially enabling soil carbon, forestry and agroforestry interventions to transition from policy-supported measures toward verified removals within a harmonised European framework.

Poland's national climate strategy remains principally focused on emissions reduction from energy, industry and transport, with relatively less emphasis on creating domestic carbon farming or carbon crediting mechanisms. The Polish NECP and other strategic planning documents recognise the role of the LULUCF sector as a contributor to climate neutrality, particularly through sustainable forest management and soil conservation measures, but these are framed as policy aspirations rather than operational market instruments designed to generate tradable carbon credits. Despite the absence of a formal national public carbon farming registry, voluntary carbon market (VCM) activity is active in Poland, particularly in forestry-based removals. Large-scale projects registered under international standards such as Verra are underway, including aggregated afforestation and forest conservation initiatives. For example, the project listed on the Markit Registry ([ref](#)) demonstrates market interest in land-sector removals and provides practical experience with quantification, monitoring and verification consistent with VCM methodologies. Polish participation in VCM projects offers valuable insights into forest carbon dynamics, landowner engagement and project aggregation, all capacities that are transferable to the emerging EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification Framework (CRCF). However, without a domestic registry or market infrastructure, these voluntary projects remain decoupled from public climate policy instruments and largely operate through international certification standards. With the implementation of CRCF and the planned Union geospatial registry by 2028, Poland's existing experience with VCM forestry projects may serve as a foundation for future alignment with EU-level certification and MRV requirements. Integrating Polish forestry and land management practices into CRCF could enable soil carbon, afforestation and potentially agroforestry activities to access harmonised certification pathways, bridging the current gap between national emissions strategies and market-based carbon removals.

Romania's climate policy framework increasingly recognises land-based removals as part of its broader mitigation strategy, although it does not yet operate a dedicated national registry for carbon farming credits. The National Forest Strategy 2030 and Romania's National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP) both explicitly identify the role of the LULUCF sector, particularly sustainable forest management, afforestation and soil carbon sequestration, in contributing to long-term climate targets, including the 2050 climate neutrality objective (Tracker Carbon Gap, Romania). These strategic commitments lay policy groundwork for enhanced utilisation of land sector removals but have not yet translated into a formal market or certification mechanism at the national level. In the absence of a public carbon farming registry, Romania is actively engaged in voluntary carbon market (VCM) initiatives, often in collaboration with international partners. Aggregated forestry projects, such as those registered under Verra, are being developed at scale, demonstrating landowner participation, MRV implementation and institutional experience with carbon project development. These initiatives provide practical examples of carbon quantification and monitoring that could be informative for future alignment with EU certification frameworks. Romania has also participated in EU-funded pilot and demonstration programmes focused on carbon farming, MRV capacity building, and landscape-level practice adoption, building a base of technical experience that can support future CRCF engagement. While current activity remains largely embedded in international voluntary standards, the strategic emphasis on LULUCF in national planning suggests growing readiness to integrate land-based removals into formalised certification architectures. With the rollout of the EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification Framework (CRCF) and the establishment of a Union geospatial registry by 2028, Romania is well-positioned to formalise its land-sector mitigation efforts within harmonised EU certification pathways. This would enable sustainable forest management, soil carbon enhancements and potentially agroforestry systems to transition from voluntary projects toward CRCF-aligned carbon farming certification, supporting both national climate objectives and broader EU climate integrity standards.

Slovakia's engagement with carbon farming is currently emerging through policy dialogue and collaborative capacity-building rather than through a formal national carbon credit registry. The country's National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP) recognises the LULUCF sector, including sustainable forest management, soil carbon sequestration and land-based sinks, as a key component of its pathway toward climate neutrality. This strategic emphasis positions land-sector removals as an important mitigation contributor, even though operational market mechanisms for carbon farming have not yet been established. At the implementation level, Slovakia has hosted stakeholder roundtables and discussions aimed at building consensus around carbon farming development. Notably, the Carbon Farming Central Europe (Carbon Farming CE) project

convened a [national roundtable in Slovakia](#), bringing together policymakers, researchers, farm advisers and private sector actors to explore enabling environments for carbon farming, MRV requirements and potential certification pathways. These discussions are contributing to early network building and knowledge exchange necessary for eventual participation in EU-level certification systems. Despite this preparatory activity, Slovakia does not currently operate a dedicated public carbon farming registry, and voluntary land-based projects remain limited or are pursued under international standards where applicable. As reflected in analyses of national policy frameworks, Slovakia's focus remains on integrating LULUCF mitigation within a [broader climate strategy](#) rather than on creating domestic carbon markets. With the forthcoming implementation of the EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification Framework (CRCF) and the establishment of a Union geospatial registry by 2028, Slovakia's ongoing stakeholder engagement and policy development may facilitate a transition from strategic recognition to operational certification. Continued dialogue, MRV capacity building and alignment with EU sustainability and additionality criteria will be critical to enabling soil carbon, sustainable forestry and potentially agroforestry activities to access harmonised CRCF-aligned certification streams in the near future.

Slovenia has recently strengthened its climate policy framework with the adoption of its national Climate Act in June 2025, establishing a legally binding pathway toward climate neutrality by 2045. The Act provides an overarching structure for mitigation, adaptation and climate finance, formally integrating land use, land-use change and forestry (LULUCF) into national climate planning. While Slovenia does not yet operate a dedicated public carbon farming registry, this legislative milestone significantly enhances the policy basis for future land-based removals. In parallel, Slovenia's CAP Strategic Plan explicitly promotes soil carbon storage, sustainable land management and climate-resilient agricultural practices, signalling growing institutional recognition of soil carbon and ecosystem functions within the farming sector. These measures currently operate through practice-based subsidies rather than outcome-based carbon certification, and agroforestry remains incentivised primarily through CAP instruments and environmental schemes rather than through market mechanisms. According to Carbon Gap's national analysis, Slovenia's current mitigation focus remains on embedding LULUCF sinks within a broader climate strategy rather than operationalising domestic carbon credit markets. As a result, any voluntary land-use projects are typically pursued under international standards or within EU-funded research and demonstration initiatives, rather than through nationally regulated registries. With the implementation of the EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification Framework (CRCF) and the establishment of the Union geospatial registry by 2028, Slovenia is well positioned to build on its strengthened legal framework. Alignment between the Climate Act, CAP-supported soil carbon measures and CRCF methodologies could enable soil carbon, sustainable forest management and potentially agroforestry systems to transition from policy priorities into verified carbon removals, supporting both national climate objectives and harmonised EU certification pathways.

Table 9 - Use of National Carbon Registries in Member States

Member State	Official National Registry/Scheme	Governance Body	Status	Primary Focus	Key VCM Presence	National Carbon Farming Strategy/Initiatives
Austria	None	N/A	Awaiting CRCF	N/A	ACR, ICR	Carbon Management Strategy (2024); ÖPUL program; Climate and Energy Fund
Belgium	None	N/A	Awaiting CRCF	N/A	Verra, Gold Standard	Go2Positive, Claire initiatives; LIFE Carbon Farming participant
Bulgaria	Balkan Carbon Credit Registry (BCCR)	Private Entity	Operational	Agriculture, Soil Carbon	Verra	Long-Term Climate Mitigation Strategy; CAP Strategic Plan; ANRAV CCS project
Croatia	None	N/A	Awaiting CRCF	N/A	Verra	Low-Carbon Development Strategy; NECP measures for LULUCF; Geothermal CCS project
Cyprus	None	N/A	Awaiting CRCF	N/A	Verra, Gold Standard	LIFE AgrOasis project; GreenCarbonCY project; National Recovery Plan funding
Czech Republic	None	N/A	Awaiting CRCF	N/A	Verra	Climate Protection Policy; NECP mentions carbon farming; Bio-CCS research project
Denmark	Danish Kyoto Registry (State-level)	Danish Business Authority	Operational	State compliance	Verra, Puro.earth	CCS Strategy; NECCS Fund (for BECCS/DACCS); Climate Program 2022 (supports forestry)
Estonia	None	N/A	Awaiting CRCF	N/A	Verra, Puro.earth	Private initiatives (e.g., Arbonics); Ecobase VCM projects
Finland	None	N/A	Awaiting CRCF	N/A	Verra, Puro.earth	"Catch the Carbon" program; Private initiatives (e.g., Green Carbon Finland)
France	Label Bas-Carbone (LBC)	Min Ecol Transition	Operational (2018)	For, Agriculture, Buildings, Transport	Verra, Gold Standard	National Low Carbon Strategy; LIFE Carbon Farming participant
Germany	None	N/A	Awaiting CRCF	N/A	Verra, Gold Standard	Climate Action Programme 2030; Federal Humus Programme; Industrial CCS funding
Greece	None	N/A	Awaiting CRCF	N/A	Verra, Gold Standard	Developing national VCM framework; LIFE projects (AgrOasis, CarboFarmHub, GOV4ALL)
Hungary	None	N/A	Awaiting CRCF	N/A	Verra	National Clean Development Strategy (focus on LULUCF); Forestry Climate Adaptation Forum
Ireland	None	N/A	In Development	N/A	Verra, Gold Standard	National Carbon Farming Framework (in development); LIFE Carbon Farming participant
Italy	Public Agroforestry Registry (under CREA)	CREA / MASAF	In Development	Agroforestry	Verra, Gold Standard	Private platforms (RCC, Carbon Planet) aligning with CRCF; LIFE Carbon Farming participant
Latvia	None	N/A	Awaiting CRCF	N/A	Verra	LIFE PeatCarbon project; LIFE CRAF project on climate-responsible agriculture
Lithuania	None	N/A	Awaiting CRCF	N/A	Verra	National climate strategy (2050 neutrality target)
Luxembourg	None	N/A	Awaiting CRCF	N/A	Verra, Gold Standard	National Strategic Plan (CAP) promotes carbon sequestration
Malta	None	N/A	Awaiting CRCF	N/A	Verra, Gold Standard	NECP includes LULUCF commitment; "Project Green" for afforestation
Netherlands	SOMERS (monitoring system)	National Research Programme	Operational	Peatland soil emissions monitoring	Verra, Gold Standard	National Research Programme on Greenhouse Gases in Peatlands (NOBV)
Poland	None	N/A	Awaiting CRCF	N/A	Verra (Agreena), Markit	National strategies focus on emissions reduction; VCM projects active
Portugal	None	N/A	Awaiting CRCF	N/A	Verra, Gold Standard	National climate strategies rely on LULUCF sink
Romania	None	N/A	Awaiting CRCF	N/A	Verra (Agreena)	National Forest Strategy 2030; NECP targets LULUCF removals
Slovakia	None	N/A	Awaiting CRCF	N/A	Verra	Carbon Farming CE project roundtable; NECP identifies LULUCF as key sink.
Slovenia	None	N/A	Awaiting CRCF	N/A	Verra	Climate Act; CAP Strategic Plan promotes soil carbon storage

Spain	National Carbon Footprint Registry	Spanish Office for Climate Change	Operational (2014)	Forestry (Afforestation, Reforestation)	Verra, Gold Standard	Long-Term Climate Strategy; LIFE Agromitiga project; LIFE Carbon Farming participant
Sweden	None	N/A	Awaiting CRCF	N/A	Verra, Puro.earth	Major state funding for BECCS (reverse auctions); Industrial Leap initiative

2.4 Validation of Standards Organisations

Independent “integrity bodies” play an important role in the voluntary carbon market (VCM) by setting benchmarks that help buyers and intermediaries screen carbon credits and reduce reputational and environmental integrity risks. While the EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification Framework (CRCF) is a regulatory system with legally binding requirements for EU-recognised certification schemes, these private benchmarks remain relevant for market alignment, especially where CRCF-certified units may be purchased by international voluntary buyers.

2.4.1 ICROA

The International Carbon Reduction and Offset Alliance (ICROA, 2023a) is an industry-led initiative that has historically played a key role in promoting integrity in the voluntary carbon market (VCM) in support of the Paris Agreement. Its core objective has been to advance best practices in corporate climate action, including science-aligned emissions reductions and the responsible use of high-quality carbon credits. ICROA’s main instrument is its Code of Best Practice (ICROA, 2023b), which establishes minimum requirements for organisations offering carbon management and offsetting services. These requirements cover governance, transparency, monitoring and reporting, claims integrity, and the appropriate use of carbon credits within corporate climate strategies. Through its endorsement mechanism (ICROA, 2024), ICROA has assessed both service providers and crediting programmes against defined quality criteria, signalling to corporate buyers which actors meet its standards.

ICROA has recognised a range of independent crediting programmes, such as Verra (VCS), Gold Standard, American Carbon Registry (ACR), Climate Action Reserve (CAR), Architecture for REDD+ Transactions (ART) and Plan Vivo, as acceptable sources of carbon credits, provided they meet requirements related to additionality, baseline setting, quantification, permanence, and leakage. Many of these programmes include methodologies applicable to land-based activities, including agroforestry, where carbon accounting typically covers above- and below-ground biomass and, in some cases, soil carbon. In these frameworks, carbon remains the primary unit of certification, while biodiversity and ecosystem services are generally addressed through safeguards or co-benefit approaches rather than mandatory outcome-based criteria.

From a governance perspective, ICROA has functioned primarily as a market signalling mechanism, rather than a regulatory authority. Its endorsement framework has helped shape early norms around credit quality and corporate claims, contributing to increased transparency and buyer confidence in the VCM.

However, ICROA has announced plans to wind down its operations by late 2026. Its functions are increasingly being absorbed or complemented by more institutionalised initiatives, notably the Integrity Council for the Voluntary Carbon Market (ICVCM), and the Voluntary Carbon Markets Integrity Initiative (VCMI), which focuses on guidance for credible corporate claims. As a result, ICROA’s role is transitioning from an active standard-setting body to a legacy framework that has influenced the development of current integrity architectures. While still relevant in signalling market practices, its long-term importance is expected to diminish as ICVCM and VCMI become the primary reference points for voluntary carbon market integrity. From a CRCF perspective, ICROA remains relevant insofar as it reflects the evolution of voluntary market expectations. However, the CRCF introduces legally binding sustainability safeguards and structured MRV requirements that go beyond ICROA’s buyer-driven model, embedding environmental integrity directly into certification rules and public oversight.

2.4.2 ICVCM

The Integrity Council for the Voluntary Carbon Market (ICVCM) (ICVCM, 2023) is a multi-stakeholder-led independent governance body. It establishes and maintains the highest standards of ethics, sustainability, and transparency for the global voluntary carbon market. It seeks a high-integrity voluntary carbon market that contributes to the goals of the Paris Agreement and the UN’s Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs),

by setting and enforcing a global benchmark for high-quality carbon credits, the Core Carbon Principles (CCPs) (ICVCM, 2025). These establish a global benchmark for high-integrity carbon credits that "set rigorous thresholds on disclosure and sustainable development". At the core of its work are the Core Carbon Principles (CCPs), which define the essential characteristics of high-quality carbon credits.

The CCPs cover key integrity dimensions, including:

- effective programme governance;
- robust additionality;
- conservative baseline setting and quantification;
- permanence and reversal risk management;
- leakage mitigation;
- and sustainable development safeguards.

ICVCM does not develop carbon accounting methodologies itself. Instead, it assesses existing carbon crediting programmes and their methodologies against the CCP benchmark (ICVCM, 2024b). Only methodologies that satisfy CCP technical criteria are listed as CCP-Approved, and credits issued under them may carry the CCP label.

For agroforestry and other land-based removals, ICVCM operates as a meta-governance filter rather than a direct regulator. Agroforestry projects enter the ICVCM system through methodologies developed by recognised voluntary standards (e.g., Verra, Gold Standard, American Carbon Registry, Climate Action Reserve, Plan Vivo). These methodologies are assessed for alignment with CCP criteria. Within this framework, agroforestry is primarily treated as a carbon removal or emission reduction activity. Biodiversity and ecosystem services are addressed mainly through safeguard requirements intended to prevent environmental harm, rather than through mandatory, outcome-based biodiversity performance metrics. Positive biodiversity impacts may be recognised, but they are not a core certification objective under CCP criteria.

From an EU policy perspective, ICVCM provides a globally recognised benchmark for carbon integrity, particularly relevant for additionality, quantification rigour, permanence and governance. However, the EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification Framework (CRCF) extends beyond carbon integrity alone.

While ICVCM focuses on ensuring that voluntary carbon credits meet high climate standards, CRCF embeds sustainability requirements directly into EU law, including mandatory "do no significant harm" provisions and explicit biodiversity and ecosystem safeguards. In this respect:

- ICVCM strengthens voluntary market credibility through a global integrity label;
- CRCF establishes a regulatory certification system integrating carbon removals with broader environmental objectives under EU legislation.

For agroforestry, this distinction is particularly important. Under ICVCM, agroforestry is validated primarily as a carbon removal mechanism. Under CRCF, agroforestry is positioned as a multifunctional land-use system contributing simultaneously to climate mitigation, biodiversity protection, soil health and ecosystem resilience.

Together, ICVCM and CRCF illustrate the evolving architecture of carbon governance: one providing global voluntary market integrity benchmarks, the other embedding carbon removals within a legally binding European climate–nature framework.

2.4.3 VCMI

The Voluntary Carbon Markets Integrity Initiative (VCMI) (Espinosa et al., 2024) is a multi-stakeholder initiative that focuses on strengthening integrity on the demand side of the voluntary carbon market. While ICVCM establishes quality benchmarks for carbon credits themselves, VCMI provides guidance on how companies should use carbon credits credibly within their climate strategies and communicate related claims (de Wit et al., 2023).

At the core of VCMI's framework is the **Claims Code of Practice** (de Wit et al., 2023), which sets out requirements and guidance for companies seeking to make credible voluntary use of carbon credits. The Code establishes rules for how organisations can integrate carbon credits into their transition pathways while ensuring that such use is additional to, and not a substitute for, science-based emissions reductions. The Claims Code requires companies to meet a set of foundational criteria, including:

- setting science-based near-term emission reduction targets;
- committing to net-zero emissions by no later than 2050;
- demonstrating progress in reducing emissions across scopes 1, 2 and 3;
- ensuring transparency through public disclosure of climate strategies and credit use.

Only after meeting these conditions can companies use carbon credits to make **Carbon Integrity Claims** (VCMI, 2024), which signal that they are contributing to global climate mitigation beyond their own value chain. These claims are structured in tiers (e.g. Silver, Gold, Platinum), reflecting increasing levels of ambition and the volume of high-quality credits retired relative to residual emissions. A key feature of the VCMI framework is its alignment with broader integrity initiatives. In particular, the Claims Code explicitly relies on **high-quality carbon credits**, typically expected to meet benchmarks such as the ICVCM Core Carbon Principles. In this sense, VCMI and ICVCM operate as complementary components of the voluntary carbon market architecture:

- ICVCM ensures **supply-side integrity** (credit quality);
- VCMI ensures **demand-side integrity** (credible use and claims).

For land-based activities such as agroforestry, VCMI does not introduce specific accounting methodologies. Instead, it governs how credits generated under recognised standards are used by companies. Agroforestry-related credits therefore enter the VCMI framework indirectly, through their compliance with recognised certification standards and integrity benchmarks. As in ICVCM, biodiversity outcomes are not the primary unit of certification; rather, VCMI emphasises that credits used for claims must be of high quality and supported by transparent reporting and credible corporate transition strategies.

From an EU policy perspective, VCMI is particularly relevant in addressing concerns around **greenwashing and claims credibility**, which have been central to debates on voluntary carbon markets. By defining clear rules for corporate communication and credit use, VCMI contributes to building trust among investors, regulators, and consumers. This function is complementary to the CRCF, which focuses on regulating the supply of certified carbon removals within the EU.

Together, ICVCM and VCMI form a two-tier integrity framework for voluntary carbon markets: one addressing the **quality of credits**, the other the **credibility of their use**. The CRCF, in turn, represents a third layer, embedding carbon removals within a legally binding regulatory system that integrates climate mitigation with broader environmental objectives.

2.4.4 Considerations on integrity frameworks

Across ICROA-endorsed programmes, ICVCM's Core Carbon Principles, and VCMI's Claims Code of Practice, a common structural feature of voluntary carbon market governance emerges: a strong emphasis on carbon

integrity, particularly in relation to additionality, quantification, permanence, and leakage, combined with a more limited integration of biodiversity as a core certification outcome.

While ICVCM focuses on the integrity of carbon credits (supply side) and VCMI on the credibility of their use and associated corporate claims (demand side), both frameworks prioritise robust carbon accounting and transparency. Environmental and social safeguards are generally included to prevent harm; however, positive biodiversity and ecosystem outcomes are typically treated as co-benefits rather than as mandatory, outcome-based performance criteria. This reflects the historical evolution of voluntary carbon markets, where carbon has remained the primary unit of accounting and value creation, and where broader ecological outcomes have been incorporated in a secondary or optional manner. By contrast, the EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification Framework (CRCF) introduces a more integrated approach, embedding sustainability safeguards and biodiversity considerations directly into certification requirements. This signals a broader transition from carbon-centric accounting towards multifunctional land-use certification, particularly relevant for agroforestry systems. (See part 5 for the linkages between carbon farming certification, CAP policies and Nature policies).

This distinction has important implications for market alignment. CRCF-certified units may need to demonstrate compatibility not only with global carbon integrity benchmarks such as ICVCM, but also with emerging expectations around credible corporate claims (as reflected in VCMI) and enhanced biodiversity and ecosystem performance. In this sense, CRCF may act as a bridge between voluntary market practices and a more comprehensive, regulation-driven model of climate and environmental integrity.

Part 3 - Whether to include agriculture and forestry in the EU Emission Trading System?

3.1 Introduction

A key report titled "*Incentivising Climate Action Across the Agri-Food Value Chain*", by Trinomics, IEEP and Wageningen University is expected soon on this subject. It was delivered to DGCLIMA in October 2025 but publication has been delayed. It is the result of extensive consultation and will deal with a potential expansion of the EU **Emissions Trading System** to include agriculture and forestry (Agri-ETS), including the design of a cap-and-trade system for agricultural methane and nitrous oxide, and options for including carbon in the same scheme.

This section summarises the earlier study, "*Pricing agricultural emissions and rewarding climate action in the agri-food value chain*" (Bognar et al., 2023) which evaluated the same issue. Agricultural emissions (mainly methane and nitrous oxide) are technically harder to measure and attribute at farm level compared to industrial CO₂ emissions, posing a fundamental challenge to ETS inclusion.

Nevertheless, agriculture's share of EU total emissions is rising in percentage terms (around 11-12% in 2025 rising to around 50% by 2050 (ESABCC, 2026), and yet agriculture remains untargeted by the EU ETS framework. The Commission's 2024 Agri-Food Transition Pathway emphasises cooperation, sustainability and competitiveness rather than punitive mechanisms such as mandatory ETS inclusion (European Commission, 2024). Meanwhile, the European Economic and Social Committee (EESC) supports a "*just transition*" to sustainable agri-food systems that balances environmental ambition with social equity. The Commission's exploratory study was launched to assess potential ETS inclusion, based on conceptual work by the Institute for European Environmental Policy and partners (Bognar et al., 2023).

3.2 Five Design Models for an Agricultural ETS

The exploratory study identifies five possible ways in which an agricultural emissions trading system (Agri-ETS) could be structured. These models differ not only in the emissions they cover, but also on who would be responsible for compliance and how the carbon price signal would reach farmers. At the heart of the debate lies a fundamental distinction: should cost be placed on farmers - creating an immediate and transparent carbon price signal at farm level, or should it be shifted to the agri-food value chain, either upstream (input suppliers) or downstream (processors). This choice has profound implications for environmental effectiveness, administrative feasibility and overall acceptability.

3.2.1 The On-Farm Models: Direct Carbon Pricing at Farm Level

The first group of options examined in the preliminary report applies the Polluter Pays Principle (PPP) in its most direct form, and expects groups of farmers themselves to monitor their emissions and use their

allowances accordingly. This would ensure that the cost of carbon is clearly visible to producers, but entails significant technical and administrative challenges.

- **Option 1: All-GHG ETS.** The most comprehensive proposal is an all-GHG on-farm ETS covering the full spectrum of agricultural emissions. This would include methane (CH₄) from enteric fermentation and manure management, nitrous oxide (N₂O) from agricultural soils and manure, and carbon dioxide (CO₂) from urea and lime application as well as on-farm energy use. Because it includes all major sources, this model would effectively function as a sector-wide carbon market for agriculture. This option has the advantage of clarity: every tonne of emissions reduced would translate into a financial gain for the group of farmers. They would have a strong motivation to adopt mitigation measures. At the same time, this model would require highly robust monitoring and reporting systems. The diversity of farms and emission sources would make accurate measurement complex and potentially costly.
- **Option 2: Livestock ETS.** A more targeted approach focuses exclusively on livestock-related non-CO₂ emissions. Methane from enteric fermentation and manure management, together with nitrous oxide from manure, would be included, while emissions from agricultural soils would remain outside the system. By narrowing the scope, this model reduces administrative complexity, but still addresses a major share of agricultural emissions. The price signal remains direct, but the range of incentivised actions is more concentrated. Measures such as methane-reducing feed additives, anaerobic digestion, improved manure storage and animal breeding strategies would become financially more attractive. Although less comprehensive than the all-GHG model, this option still requires farm-level emission accounting and could face similar political resistance.
- **Option 3: Peatland ETS.** The peatland-focused model is narrower still. It targets emissions arising from the drainage of organic soils used for agriculture. Drained peatlands are a particularly carbon-intensive land use, and rewetting them can generate significant emission reductions. By placing a carbon cost on emissions from drained peat soils, this model would create a strong economic incentive to shift land management practices, potentially toward rewetting, paludiculture (wet agriculture) or full ecological restoration. This option is limited in scope and geographical application, and it could be seen as unfairly targeting regions and farmers on wetlands.

3.2.2 Off-Farm Models: Indirect Price Signals

These options shift the burden away from individual farmers and focus on corporate actors within the agri-food value chain. It has two options:

- **Option 4: Upstream ETS.** Where the obligation to use allowances would lie with producers and importers of key emission-intensive inputs, such as nitrogen fertilisers, animal feed, urea and lime. By pricing the embedded emissions in these inputs, the carbon cost would be reflected in higher input prices. Farmers would then face incentives to reduce fertiliser use, to adopt precision agriculture technologies, to substitute synthetic inputs with organic alternatives, or improve feed efficiency. The effectiveness of this approach depends heavily on how fully and transparently the carbon cost is passed on. If upstream firms absorb part of the cost to protect market share, the incentive at farm level may weaken.
- **Option 5: Downstream ETS.** In the downstream model, the compliance obligation would be placed on processors, particularly large meat and dairy companies and slaughterhouses. They would cover the non-CO₂ emissions associated with the raw products they process. Here, the carbon signal would travel through product markets. Processors facing higher carbon costs might pass these on to consumers, raising prices for emission-intensive products such as beef and dairy. Alternatively, they might modify payments to farmers based on emission intensity, rewarding lower-emission production systems. They could also invest in value-chain partnerships to reduce supplier emissions. Unlike the upstream model, which primarily influences input efficiency, the downstream approach could affect both production practices and consumer demand. It therefore has the potential to reshape the entire livestock value chain, but also introduces greater social and political sensitivity.

All five models are likely to be highly unpopular in the agricultural sector, and use of the phrase “polluter pays” is not likely to evoke much enthusiasm. Apart from Options 1 and 3 they focus exclusively on non CO₂ fluxes, and ignore the opportunity for “insetting” carbon sequestration within the combined agriculture and forestry sector (i.e. an AFOLU approach).

Options 4 and 5 concentrate regulatory responsibility in a relatively small number of large firms, which may respond by developing certification schemes, strengthening contractual requirements and investing in digital monitoring systems. Larger, well-capitalised farms may be better positioned to comply with such demands, while smaller farms could face higher adjustment costs and be less competitive.

The upstream and downstream approaches generate different innovation pathways. The upstream model (Option 4) could encourage technological solutions that reduce high dependence on inputs like fertilizers. The downstream model (Option 5), by contrast, may influence consumers to think about the energy and pollution cost of the products they purchase. The on-farm models (Options 1-3) would prioritise environmental precision and direct accountability but would be technically difficult or geographically iniquitous to implement. The eventual choice will reflect not only technical feasibility, but also political priorities and distributional considerations (EESC, 2024; Mal, 2024).

3.3. Comparative Assessment and Social Considerations

The five models have different emission reduction potentials. The on-farm models (particularly Options 1 and 2) score highly in mitigation potential because they attach a clear price to emissions at the point where production decisions are made. The off-farm models may still generate mitigation, but the signal is indirect and depends on how strongly it is transmitted along the value chain.

A key factor in comparing the models is administrative burden and MRV feasibility. (Vanderheyden et al., 2026). There are at least six million farmers in the EU and enrolling all of these in a comprehensive monitoring system for emissions will be a daunting task, especially when monitoring methane and nitrous oxide at farm level is complex and often model-based (Coderoni et al., 2024). On-farm systems therefore face higher reporting and verification costs, while upstream or downstream systems reduce the number of regulated entities but introduce attribution challenges.

Another consideration is the impact on farmers income. An on-farm Agri-ETS could expose farms to explicit carbon costs, potentially increasing financial pressure, especially for small and medium-sized holdings. Indirect models may soften this exposure but would still affect farm margins through input prices or contractual arrangements imposed by processors.

There are also competitiveness and carbon leakage risks. If EU agriculture faces higher carbon costs than international competitors, production could shift outside the EU. This would undermine both environmental objectives and rural economic stability. Leakage risks are particularly relevant for livestock and dairy sectors exposed to global markets. Options exist to level the market through the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM), but the current implementation of this for six sectors (iron, steel, aluminium, cement, fertilizers, hydrogen and electricity) is causing major administrative problems (Völler, 2023).

Beyond technical evaluation, the debate increasingly recognises the social dimension of carbon pricing in agriculture. Civil society organisations such as the European Environmental Bureau warn that an Agri-ETS could have regressive distributional effects if not carefully designed. Smaller farms, with limited capital and lower bargaining power, may struggle to absorb additional compliance costs. The EEB therefore argues that any carbon pricing instrument must be accompanied by strong social safeguards, including revenue recycling, targeted support mechanisms and protection for vulnerable producers (Mal, 2024).

Similarly, the European Economic and Social Committee stresses that climate ambition must be aligned with social equity and sustainable rural development. In its opinion on ensuring a “Just Transition” for EU

agri-food systems, the Committee emphasises that decarbonisation should not come at the expense of farm viability, employment or territorial cohesion (EESC, 2024).

In this light, the comparative assessment is not purely technical. The choice between Agri-ETS models also reflects a broader policy question: how to reconcile environmental integrity with economic resilience and social fairness. Carbon pricing in agriculture cannot be evaluated solely in terms of tonnes reduced; it must also be assessed in terms of who bears the costs, who captures the benefits, and how rural communities are supported through the transition.

3.4. Implementation Challenges

Beyond the specific features of each Agri-ETS model, the exploratory study highlights a set of cross-cutting implementation challenges that would need to be addressed regardless of the chosen design. These challenges concern not only technical feasibility, but also the distribution of costs and benefits, institutional coordination and long-term political acceptability.

3.4.1 MRV (Monitoring, Reporting, Verification)

Monitoring, Reporting and Verification (MRV) is consistently identified as the most significant barrier to integrating agriculture into an emissions trading system. The credibility, environmental integrity and economic efficiency of any ETS depend fundamentally on the ability to measure emissions accurately and reliably.

In agriculture, this task is particularly complex. Unlike industrial sectors, where emissions often originate from identifiable point sources, agricultural emissions are diffuse and biologically driven. Methane (CH₄) from enteric fermentation and manure, and nitrous oxide (N₂O) from soils and fertiliser application, vary according to seasonality, soil conditions, animal types and management practices. As a result, standardised, farm-level measurement is extremely challenging (Bognar et al., 2023; Hernández, 2024).

For on-farm models, the MRV challenge is particularly acute. Emissions cannot be directly measured with physical sensors in most cases; instead, they must be estimated using models based on farm activity data such as fertiliser use, herd size, feed composition or manure management systems. This approach is inherently complex, may generate uncertainty, and can impose significant administrative and financial burdens on farmers.

In off-farm models, the MRV problem does not disappear, it shifts. Emissions occurring at farm level must be attributed to upstream inputs or downstream products. This requires robust data systems, harmonised methodologies and clear accounting rules to avoid double counting or gaps in coverage.

Recognising that MRV is a foundational prerequisite, the study recommends developing a harmonised EU-wide farm-level GHG reporting tool before introducing any pricing mechanism. Ecologic Institute materials similarly emphasise the need for standardised accounting infrastructure as a first step (McDonald et al., n.d.). Such a tool would not only prepare the ground for a potential ETS, but also strengthen existing CAP climate measures, support participation in voluntary carbon markets and improve advisory services.

Importantly, this sequencing, building reporting capacity before imposing carbon costs, may help decouple the technical challenge of data collection from the politically sensitive step of carbon pricing. By familiarising farmers with GHG accounting gradually, policymakers can increase data maturity and institutional readiness, potentially making future regulatory instruments more feasible.

3.4.2 Allowance Allocation: Auctioning or Free Allocation?

Another critical design question concerns how emission allowances would be distributed. In principle, auctioning, the default method in the EU ETS, aligns most closely with the "Polluter Pays Principle".

Regulated entities must purchase allowances for every tonne emitted, ensuring that carbon costs are fully internalised (DG-Environment, 2026). A major advantage of auctioning is the generation of public revenue. These funds could be recycled to support the sector's transition, for example by financing low-carbon investments, research and innovation, or compensatory measures for vulnerable households facing higher food prices.

However, full auctioning could significantly increase cost exposure for the agricultural sector, particularly in its early stages of adaptation. For this reason, transitional free allocation is often discussed as a political compromise. Granting a limited number of allowances for free, at least temporarily, may ease financial pressure and reduce carbon leakage risks by limiting cost disadvantages for EU producers relative to international competitors. At the same time, free allocation can weaken the carbon price signal and reduce incentives for rapid mitigation. There is also a political risk that once free allocation is granted, stakeholders may resist its gradual phase-out, slowing structural change.

The choice between auctioning and free allocation therefore involves balancing environmental integrity, economic realism and political feasibility.

3.4.3 Transition Support and Income Stability

The political sensitivity of agricultural carbon pricing is well illustrated by national experiences such as the Danish Green Tax Reform debate (Svarer et al., 2024). Farm-level carbon costs can become highly contentious if income impacts are not mitigated (Carlsson, 2024).

For this reason, transitional support mechanisms are widely regarded as indispensable. Without accompanying financial and technical assistance, carbon pricing could disproportionately affect small and medium-sized farms, potentially accelerating structural consolidation.

DG AGRI's cautious stance reflects this concern. Protecting competitiveness and supporting a just transition for farmers remain central policy priorities. Any Agri-ETS would therefore need to be embedded within a broader transition framework that ensures income stability while enabling gradual decarbonisation.

3.4.4 Governance, Compliance and Integration with the CAP

An Agri-ETS would not operate in isolation. It would need to function coherently within the EU's existing governance framework and, above all, alongside the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). Clear institutional roles would need to be defined for setting the emissions cap, conducting allowance auctions, accrediting verifiers and enforcing compliance. Given the diversity of agricultural systems across Member States, coordination between EU institutions and national authorities would be essential.

Perhaps the most delicate issue concerns interaction with the CAP. The CAP already includes environmental and climate objectives through its "green architecture" and eco-schemes. Introducing an ETS without careful alignment could create contradictory signals, for example, penalising emissions through carbon pricing while simultaneously subsidising similar practices under CAP instruments.

A more coherent approach would link the two frameworks. Revenues generated from allowance auctions could be channelled into dedicated funds that complement CAP resources, supporting farmers in adopting low-carbon technologies and management practices. In this way, the "polluter pays" logic of carbon pricing could be combined with a "supporter enables" mechanism, ensuring that responsibility is matched with practical capacity to transition.

3.5. Institutional Strategy: Converging Goals, Different Pathways

The debate on a possible Agri-ETS reflects a broader institutional dynamic within the European Commission, where climate objectives are shared but policy pathways differ. On the one hand, DG CLIMA views carbon pricing as a structurally powerful instrument to align agriculture with EU climate neutrality goals, extending the Polluter Pays Principle to a sector that remains outside direct carbon pricing. On the other hand, DG AGRI adopts a more cautious and gradualist approach, prioritising incentive-based mechanisms embedded in the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). Through eco-schemes and agri-environmental measures, DG AGRI seeks to reward sustainable practices and support climate-friendly transitions without exposing farmers to immediate carbon liabilities. This orientation is closely linked to the concept of a “just transition”: as underlined by the European Economic and Social Committee, climate ambition must be reconciled with social equity, farm viability and rural competitiveness (EESC, 2024). Concerns persist that a rigid ETS applied prematurely could disproportionately affect smaller farms and accelerate structural consolidation. The Commission’s exploration of carbon farming further illustrates this intermediate pathway: remunerating carbon sequestration in soils and biomass could generate new income streams, yet the integration of such credits into a compliance ETS raises technically sensitive questions around measurement, permanence and environmental integrity. Measurement challenges more broadly reinforce DG AGRI’s cautious stance, as methane and nitrous oxide emissions are inherently difficult to quantify at farm level, and premature pricing without robust MRV systems could undermine both credibility and political acceptability. This strategic preference for gradual alignment is reflected in the 2024 Transition Pathway for the Agri-Food Industrial Ecosystem, which emphasises cooperation, innovation, sustainability and competitiveness rather than immediate mandatory ETS inclusion (European Commission, 2024).

Importantly, the study *“Pricing agricultural emissions and rewarding climate action in the agri-food value chain”* is explicitly framed as an exploratory technical assessment rather than a political verdict. The ultimate decision on whether and how to introduce carbon pricing in agriculture remains a political choice for the European Parliament and the Council. One of the clearest conclusions emerging from the analysis, however, is that any form of agricultural carbon pricing would require robust transitional support. Given the sector’s tight margins, high capital intensity and exposure to climate and market volatility, imposing new carbon costs without providing adaptation pathways could threaten farm viability, particularly for small and medium-sized holdings. Transitional support would therefore need to combine revenue recycling from allowance auctions, strategic alignment of CAP funds toward mitigation investments, and the mobilisation of private finance through risk-sharing mechanisms that de-risk sustainable investments. Without such measures, carbon pricing risks becoming economically disruptive rather than transformative.

At the same time, the exploratory nature of the study leaves several critical questions unresolved. The feasibility of applying a Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) to agri-food products remains uncertain, given the heterogeneity of agricultural production systems and the difficulty of calculating embedded emissions in a WTO-compliant manner. The interaction between a domestic agricultural carbon price and existing trade agreements, tariff-rate quotas and international obligations also requires further legal and economic analysis. Finally, linking an Agri-ETS to carbon removals under the Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) sector presents both opportunities and risks: while removals could provide additional revenue streams for land managers, issues of non-permanence, measurement uncertainty and potential “mitigation deterrence” raise significant environmental integrity concerns. Taken together, these unresolved issues underline that policy development in this field remains at an early and cautious stage, with capacity-building, data infrastructure and transitional governance likely to precede any direct and comprehensive carbon pricing mechanism for agriculture.

Taken together, these unresolved issues underline that policy development in this field remains at an early and cautious stage, with capacity-building, data infrastructure and transitional governance likely to precede any direct and comprehensive carbon pricing mechanism for agriculture. In this evolving landscape, the objectives of DigitAF acquire particular relevance, although their potential should be interpreted with caution. By promoting agroforestry systems that combine production, carbon sequestration and biodiversity

co-benefits, DigitAF contributes to forms of structural transformation that broadly align with the long-term objectives of both DG CLIMA and DG AGRI. However, the extent to which such systems can be scaled across diverse agricultural contexts remains uncertain, particularly given differences in farm structure, regional conditions and access to capital.

Agroforestry may function as a bridge between incentive-based CAP mechanisms and potential future carbon pricing frameworks; however, its effectiveness in this role depends on adequate financial support, farmer uptake and the development of credible and cost-efficient monitoring systems. While these systems can generate climate benefits, enhance resilience and diversify income streams, such outcomes are not guaranteed and may not be evenly distributed across farming systems. Moreover, the development of monitoring methodologies for tree-based systems contributes to broader EU efforts to strengthen Climate Impact Accounting, which would be a prerequisite for any credible Agri-ETS. At the same time, persistent challenges related to measurement, reporting and verification, particularly given the variability of agricultural emissions across climate conditions, soil types and management practices, raise concerns about accuracy, cost and equity. In this context, there is a risk that imperfect MRV systems could produce imprecise or uneven outcomes, potentially undermining both environmental integrity and farmer trust. In this sense, DigitAF should not be seen as a direct pathway toward the implementation of carbon pricing in agriculture, but rather as one of several exploratory approaches contributing to the technical, ecological and socio-economic conditions under which such policies might, over time, become more feasible though not necessarily universally appropriate or politically uncontested.

3.6. Agroforestry within the EU ETS Debate

Agroforestry occupies a particularly strategic position within the evolving debate on an EU Agri-ETS. By integrating trees into agricultural systems, it combines productive land use with measurable carbon sequestration, biodiversity enhancement and increased climate resilience. In principle, this makes agroforestry a promising candidate for inclusion as a removal pathway within a broader climate policy architecture. However, as highlighted in the Commission's exploratory study (European Commission, 2023) and reinforced by external analyses such as Carbon Market Watch (Hernández, 2024), integrating biological removals into a compliance-based ETS requires extreme caution. Ensuring environmental integrity would necessitate conservative accounting methodologies, robust buffer mechanisms to manage reversal risks, clear additionality criteria and transparent verification systems. Without such safeguards, linking removals to a tradable carbon market could undermine credibility and dilute mitigation incentives. More broadly, the study demonstrates that while an Agri-ETS is technically conceivable, its implementation would be complex and politically sensitive. The central policy dilemma persists: on-farm models provide strong environmental precision but face high administrative, financial and political barriers, particularly for smaller farms with limited investment capacity, whereas off-farm models may be more feasible but rely on effective price transmission and careful management of distributional impacts. Institutionally, DG CLIMA views carbon pricing as a structural alignment tool for climate neutrality, while DG AGRI prioritises incentive-based instruments under the CAP, emphasising a just transition and competitiveness safeguards. For farmers, this dual trajectory points toward gradual policy evolution rather than abrupt regulatory change. The most plausible pathway involves first strengthening harmonised GHG accounting systems, expanding incentive-based climate measures and carbon farming, and mobilising transitional financial support, before considering more direct market-based price signals once MRV, trade and equity concerns are adequately addressed. Ultimately, the study suggests that the indispensable foundation for any credible carbon pricing mechanism in agriculture is not the immediate imposition of a carbon price, but the establishment of a robust and harmonised data infrastructure. Without reliable accounting systems, an ETS would lack environmental credibility; even with them, however, its appropriateness and political feasibility would remain contingent on broader economic, social and institutional conditions.

Part 4 - Carbon Farming Certification Worldwide

4.1 The Kyoto Clean Development Mechanism

4.1.1 Policy and governance context

The Clean Development Mechanism, established under Article 12 of the Kyoto Protocol, was the first global project-based mechanism designed to link climate mitigation finance in developing countries with compliance obligations in industrialised economies. Its purpose was twofold: to assist, Annex B, Parties in achieving their emission reduction commitments cost-effectively, and to support sustainable development in host countries through climate mitigation investments. In practice, the CDM created a market for Certified Emission Reductions (CERs), which could be generated by eligible projects and traded internationally. Globally, the mechanism registered more than 7,500 projects and issued over 1.4 billion CERs, but its application to forestry and land use, especially through Afforestation and Reforestation (A/R) activities, remained limited, particularly in Africa (Jindal et al., 2006).

In the African context, the CDM must be understood not simply as an early carbon market instrument, but as a governance model that attempted to apply a highly standardised, compliance-oriented architecture to land-use systems characterised by fragmented tenure, limited institutional capacity, and high biophysical and social variability. The mechanism was formally open to African participation, yet in practice it remained difficult to access. The underlying problem was not only a shortage of finance or projects, but a mismatch between the design logic of the CDM and the operational realities of forestry and agroforestry systems in many African countries. This is one of the central lessons that makes the CDM relevant to the current design of the EU Carbon Removal and Carbon Farming Regulation (CRCF): mechanisms that aim for high environmental integrity can nonetheless fail if their institutional demands exceed the capacities of likely participants.

4.1.2 Main practices and project models

Within the CDM, the only eligible forestry activities were Afforestation and Reforestation projects (CMW, 2012b). These were intended to increase terrestrial carbon sinks by establishing trees on non-forested land. In theory, this opened a pathway for restoring degraded land, improving rural livelihoods, and generating carbon finance (Ngwadla et al., 2024). In practice, however, the number of forestry projects remained small compared with other CDM sectors, and African uptake was particularly limited. What emerged was not a broad-based landscape of community-led carbon farming, but a narrow set of projects that could bear the transaction costs and technical demands of CDM participation (Mulenga, 2017)

The project model embedded in the CDM was fundamentally project-based and transactional. Each intervention had to establish a defined boundary, a baseline scenario, a monitoring methodology, and a crediting pathway under internationally approved rules. This model was ill-suited to many African land-use contexts, where agroforestry and restoration often occur through dispersed, smallholder-led and socially embedded practices rather than through singular, industrial-style project units. The historical evidence therefore suggests that the CDM tended to privilege larger, more technically sophisticated and externally supported initiatives over smaller, community-based efforts. That pattern is particularly significant for the CRCF, since a European carbon farming framework will face similar tensions between project-level accounting rigour and the realities of heterogeneous farm structures.

4.1.3 Standards, instruments and actors

The CDM operated through a dense architecture of modalities, procedures, approved methodologies, validation and verification requirements, and Executive Board oversight. The UNFCCC secretariat published extensive manuals and methodological documents to support project development (United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, 2013), but the system remained highly technical and

procedurally demanding. A major eligibility rule, for example, required that A/R projects be established only on land that had not been forested since 31 December 1989. Although this rule was intended to prevent perverse incentives, it created a substantial evidentiary burden, especially in settings where historical land-cover records were incomplete or difficult to verify.

The main actors in the CDM system included project developers, Designated National Authorities, validation and verification bodies, technical consultants, the UNFCCC Secretariat, and the CDM Executive Board. In countries with limited institutional and technical capacity, these actors were often difficult to access or expensive to engage. As a result, participation in CDM forestry required not only a viable restoration idea, but also access to specialised legal, methodological and carbon-market expertise. This helps explain why the mechanism struggled to generate a broad pipeline of forestry projects in Africa (Desanker, 2005). It also illustrates a broader lesson for carbon farming certification: standards and registries do not simply measure mitigation; they shape who can participate in the first place.

4.1.4 MRV and methodological constraints

Measurement, reporting and verification were central to the CDM's claim to environmental integrity, but they also became one of its principal barriers (Shishlov & Bellassen, 2016). A/R projects had to demonstrate additionality, define credible baselines, quantify leakage, and monitor carbon stock changes over time using approved methodologies. Each of these requirements was complex in its own right; together, they formed a demanding system that was difficult to operationalise in low-capacity contexts (Cames et al., 2016). Additionality was especially problematic because it required proponents to construct a credible "business-as-usual" counterfactual and prove that carbon removals would not have occurred without CDM finance. This created substantial room for uncertainty and methodological challenges (CMW, 2012a).

Non-permanence was another major issue. Because biological carbon can be reversed through fire, disease, land-use change or management failure, the CDM created two special crediting instruments: temporary CERs (tCERs) and long-term CERs (lCERs), to reflect the impermanent nature of forest carbon (Galinato et al., 2011; Locatelli & Pedroni, 2006). Although conceptually defensible, these instruments proved commercially unattractive because buyers inherited future replacement liabilities (CMW, 2012b). In effect, the mechanism solved a scientific problem by creating a market problem. This is a critical lesson for future carbon farming frameworks: permanence rules must be robust enough to maintain credibility, but not so cumbersome that they undermine market usability or farmer participation.

Leakage assessment added a further layer of complexity, requiring project developers to quantify emissions increases outside the project boundary caused indirectly by project activities (Wavinya & Getahun, 2021). Similarly, methodology approval was often expensive and time-consuming, especially where no existing methodology fit the local context. Taken together, these MRV challenges suggest that the CDM was not only technically demanding but structurally biased toward contexts where land rights, baseline data, modelling capacity and project finance were already well developed. That combination was rare in many African forestry and agroforestry settings.

4.1.5 Lessons for the EU CRCF

The CDM experience offers a historically important caution for the CRCF. First, it shows that environmental integrity and practical accessibility must be designed together. A framework that is technically rigorous but operationally inaccessible risks excluding precisely the land managers it seeks to mobilise. Second, it demonstrates that one-size-fits-all methodologies are poorly suited to heterogeneous land-use systems, especially where smallholders, mixed landscapes and complex tenure arrangements dominate. Third, it highlights the importance of designing permanence and additionality rules that are scientifically credible without being commercially or administratively paralysing.

A further lesson concerns the transition from Kyoto to Paris. The debate around the migration of legacy CDM activities into the Paris Agreement's Article 6.4 mechanism has shown how easily unresolved quality

concerns can be carried forward into new systems (Schneider & La Hoz Theuer, 2019; UNFCCC, 2024). The credibility of future carbon markets depends not only on technical continuity but on the willingness to learn from past design failures. For the CRCF, this implies that robust MRV, proportionality, farmer accessibility, and alignment with real land-management practices must be treated as co-equal design objectives rather than sequential ones. In this sense, the CDM remains highly relevant: not as a model to replicate, but as a governance experiment from which clear design lessons can be drawn.

4.2 Carbon Certification in Africa

By the end of 2024, more than 6,200 carbon projects had been registered across the twelve largest international carbon crediting registries, collectively issuing approximately 305 MtCO₂e of credits in that year alone. Since the adoption of the Paris Agreement in 2016, these registries have issued more than 2.1 billion credits globally, underlining how voluntary carbon markets can mobilise climate finance at scale RAF 2025 (EURAF, 2025).

Africa has become a major geography for voluntary carbon markets, particularly for projects in agriculture, forestry and other land use (AFOLU). A large share of activity is concentrated in nature-based solutions (afforestation/reforestation, agroforestry, forest conservation, sustainable land management), often designed to deliver climate outcomes alongside biodiversity and livelihood co-benefits. Market overviews suggest that thousands of projects across the continent have issued credits under voluntary standards, spanning reforestation, agroforestry and community-based land restoration (Anon, 2024). This aligns with the evidence base compiled in the CIFOR-ICRAF contribution to DigitAF, which documents carbon, commodity, and ecosystem certification pathways through representative African case studies.

African experience is particularly relevant for the EU Carbon Removal and Carbon Farming (CRCF) because many projects operate in smallholder-dominated landscapes and community-managed commons. This has required practical solutions for participation, benefit sharing, and participatory MRV, themes that recur across African case studies and are directly transferable to the governance challenges Europe will face as it scales carbon farming.

4.2.1 Typologies of certification schemes

To guide the analysis, certification initiatives relevant to agroforestry and land use in Africa can be grouped into three typologies:

- Carbon-based certification: Projects issuing carbon credits from agroforestry, forestry, soil carbon, or REDD+ activities (e.g., Kenya Agricultural Carbon Project, Humbo Assisted Natural Regeneration, Kasigau Corridor REDD+, Mai-Ndombe REDD+).
- Commodity certification: Agroforestry-related production systems certified under sustainability schemes such as Rainforest Alliance, Organic or Fairtrade (e.g., cocoa in Cameroon and Ghana; shade coffee in Uganda; shea and baobab in West Africa). Rainforest Alliance provides region-specific policy and assurance requirements for cocoa certification in West and Central Africa (Anon, 2025b).
- Ecosystem and biodiversity certification: Certification focused on sustainable forest management, ecosystem services and biodiversity outcomes, commonly linked to standards such as FSC and, in some emerging registry infrastructures, ISO-aligned approaches (e.g., ISO 14064 series).

To illustrate the diversity of approaches, Table 1 summarises selected agroforestry and land-use certification case studies in Africa (location, certification type, standards applied, scale, and key outcomes).

4.2.2 Integrity principles and relevance for African contexts

High-integrity offset schemes typically require robust criteria, such as additionality, permanence, measurability, transparency, leakage management, independent auditing/verification, and registration, to

ensure that credits represent real and durable climate benefits. These integrity principles are referenced, for example, in Australian Climate Active-related (Climate Change Authority, 2022; WeAct Pty Ltd, 2022) materials and reviews of international offsets.

In the African context, applying integrity principles is especially important given (i) high exposure to delivery risks (e.g., permanence and leakage in land-based projects) and (ii) capacity constraints, including limited local availability of accredited validation and verification bodies (VVBs). This reinforces the value of digital MRV approaches that combine remote sensing with locally collected data to reduce transaction costs while improving credibility.

4.2.3 Voluntary carbon standards operating in Africa

The principal standards used to certify land-based carbon projects in Africa are:

- Verified Carbon Standard (VCS) administered by Verra
- Gold Standard for the Global Goals
- Plan Vivo

These certification systems represent the most widely used voluntary carbon standards globally and together account for a large share of projects in the voluntary carbon market (RioTinto, 2024).

Verra/VCS is particularly prevalent for large-scale AFOLU projects (ARR, IFM, REDD+). Verra's program documentation defines rules for project registration, monitoring, and validation/verification, while the registry provides public access to project documentation and issuance.

The Gold Standard registry hosts a smaller number of projects in Africa, typically focusing on community-based restoration activities that generate strong sustainable development co-benefits alongside carbon mitigation.

Plan Vivo has historically specialised in community-led nature-based projects, often involving smallholder agroforestry and participatory monitoring; it publishes a project certification pathway and approved methodologies.

Many carbon projects in Africa involve large numbers of smallholder farmers, often organised into farmer groups or cooperatives. Aggregating farmers allows projects to overcome the high transaction costs associated with carbon certification and enables smallholders to participate in global carbon markets.

Examples include the Kenya Agricultural Carbon Project, which was the first project globally to issue soil carbon credits to smallholder farmers under the Verified Carbon Standard, and the TIST Program, which operates across Kenya, Uganda and Tanzania and supports thousands of farmers to plant trees and adopt agroforestry practices.

Other initiatives focus on forest conservation and avoided deforestation through REDD+ mechanisms. Prominent examples include the Kasigau Corridor REDD+ Project in Kenya and the Mai-Ndombe REDD+ Project in the Democratic Republic of Congo, both of which combine large-scale forest conservation with community development programmes.

4.2.4 Current AFOLU carbon projects in Africa

Information on African AFOLU projects currently registered under the Verified Carbon Standard, Gold Standard and Plan Vivo registries has been compiled from publicly available project registries.

Under the Verra registry, projects include afforestation, reforestation and revegetation (ARR), REDD+ projects and integrated forest management (IFM). These projects represent some of the largest sources of voluntary carbon credits in Africa. (Table 10).

The Gold Standard registry contains a smaller portfolio of terrestrial carbon projects on the continent, mainly focused on community-based reforestation and agroforestry. (Table 11).

The Plan Vivo registry includes a number of agroforestry and landscape restoration initiatives that work directly with local communities and smallholder farmers. (Table 12).

Based on registry data available in September 2025, the estimated annual emission reductions or removals from currently registered projects are approximately:

- 35.08 MtCO₂e per year under VCS
- 4.47 MtCO₂e per year under Plan Vivo
- 0.90 MtCO₂e per year under Gold Standard

These figures highlight the dominant role of VCS projects within African voluntary carbon markets. Many African carbon projects focus on forest conservation and REDD+ initiatives, which generate carbon credits by preventing deforestation and protecting forest ecosystems. These initiatives often operate in high-biodiversity landscapes and deliver multiple environmental and social co-benefits. Forest-based projects therefore represent a major component of voluntary carbon markets in Africa (Anon, 2023b).

However, REDD+ projects are currently outside the scope of the EU Carbon Removal and Carbon Farming Regulation (CRCF). This is partly because deforestation is not considered a major policy issue within the European Union compared with tropical regions.

Table 10: VERRA AFOLU projects in Africa (Operational [September 2025](#)).

Country	Project Name	Verra ID	Project Type	Start Year	Projected End Year	Projected Sequestration / Reduction (tCO ₂ e per year)	Number of Beneficiaries	Project Proponent	Status
Burkina Faso	Tond Tenga	4987	ARR	2023	2053	14,034	1,600 households	TREE AID	Registered
Cameroon	Greenzone Reforestation Project	4176	ARR	2023	2053	48,162	Not specified	DGB Group	Under validation
DRC	Mai-Ndombe REDD+ Project	934	REDD+	2011	2041	5,989,289	~180,000 community members	Wildlife Works Carbon, LLC	Registered
DRC	Nkuba REDD+ Project	2614	REDD+	2018	2048	6,432,192	~35,000 people	Jadora LLC	Registered
DRC	Isangi REDD+ Project	1477	REDD+	2010	2040	3,467,419	~45,000 community members	ERA-Environmental Services, Inc.	Registered
DRC	Lomami REDD+ Project	2891	REDD+	2021	2051	3,189,458	~100,000 community members	Wildlife Works Carbon, LLC	Under validation
Ghana	The Form Ghana Reforestation Project	1395	ARR	2011	2061	185,257	~1,000 employees	FORM Ghana	Registered
Guinea	Carbon-Plus for an Agroforestry-based Restoration of the Fouta Djallon Massif	1978	ARR	2018	2048	27,249	2,500 households	Climate Action and Resilience Nexus (CARN)	Registered
Kenya	Kasigau Corridor REDD Project	612	REDD+	2006	2036	1,466,613	~116,000 community members	Wildlife Works Carbon, LLC	Registered
Kenya	Chyulu Hills REDD+ Project	1118	REDD+	2013	2043	557,597	~90,000 people	Conservation International Foundation	Registered
Kenya	Northern Kenya Grassland Carbon Project	1468	IFM	2013	2043	1,387,480	~14,500 pastoralist families	Northern Rangelands Trust	Registered
Kenya	TIST Program in Kenya	737	ARR	2004	2034	129,576	94,000+ farmers	The International Small Group and Tree Planting Program	Registered
Madagascar	Conservation of the Ankeniheny-Zahamena Corridor	873	REDD+	2007	2037	933,707	~30,000 households	Conservation International Foundation	Registered
Republic of the Congo	Reforestation on Degraded Lands in the Republic of Congo	872	ARR	2011	2051	344,834	Not specified	The Pachama Company	Registered
Republic of the Congo	OKA 2 Project	2971	ARR	2021	2051	157,690	Not specified	Forêt Aurifère	Under validation
Rwanda	Rwanda Riparian Restoration Project	3072	ARR	2021	2051	19,410	Not specified	EcoPlanet Bamboo Group	Registration requested
Tanzania	The TIST Program in Tanzania	1005	ARR	2007	2037	74,482	12,000+ farmers	The International Small Group and Tree Planting Program	Registered
Tanzania	Acacia II Reforestation Project	1493	ARR	2012	2052	87,000	Not specified	Green Resources	Registered
Uganda	The TIST Program in Uganda	863	ARR	2003	2033	82,028	13,000+ farmers	The International Small Group and Tree Planting Program	Registered
Zambia	Luangwa Community Forests Project	1765	REDD+	2014	2044	2,752,946	~217,000 people	BioCarbon Partners	Registered
Zambia	Zambia Agroforestry Grouped Project	3999	ARR	2022	2052	100,000	10,000+ smallholder farmers	The Nature Conservancy	Under validation
Zimbabwe	Kariba REDD+ Project	902	REDD+	2011	2041	7,631,096	~200,000 people	South Pole	Registered

Table 11: Live Gold Standard Terrestrial Carbon Projects in Africa (Operational [September 2025](#))

Country	Project Name	GS ID	Start Year	Projected End Year	Projected Sequestration / Reduction (tCO ₂ e per year)	Key Activities & Beneficiaries	Project Proponent	Status
Burkina Faso	Community Based Reforestation Project	2933	2014	2034	40,000	Reforestation and agroforestry activities benefiting over 10,000 community members with improved food security and income.	Tiipaalga	Certified
Ethiopia	The Northern Ethiopia Community-based Reforestation	2250	2011	2031	100,000	Community-managed reforestation and restoration of degraded lands, benefiting ~45,000 people through improved natural resources.	World Vision Ethiopia	Certified
Ethiopia	Reforestation of Degraded Slopes in Amhara	2249	2011	2031	25,000	Community-led reforestation of over 5,000 hectares, improving livelihoods for ~12,000 people in the Amhara region.	World Vision Ethiopia	Certified
Ethiopia	Uplands Reforestation Project (New)	2796	2012	2032	45,000	Farmer-led reforestation and land restoration on degraded uplands, benefiting ~15,000 people with improved resources and income.	World Vision Ethiopia	Certified
Kenya	The TIST Program	1279	2007	2027	130,000	A farmer-led network for reforestation and sustainable agriculture, involving more than 70,000 farmers.	The International Small Group and Tree Planting Program (TIST)	Certified
Malawi	Malawi Afforestation Project	1045	2008	2028	15,000	Establishes community woodlots for sustainable timber and fuelwood, reducing pressure on native forests and benefiting 1,500 households.	C-Quest Capital	Certified
Mali	Trees for a Safer Future	10864	2022	2042	35,000	Agroforestry project supporting 5,000+ farmers to integrate trees on their farms, enhancing food security and climate resilience.	World Vision	In Development
Rwanda	Rwanda Agroforestry Project (New)	12015	2023	2043	20,000	Supporting over 10,000 smallholder farmers to implement agroforestry practices, improving soil health and creating sustainable livelihoods.	Ecotrust	In Development
Senegal	Sustainable Community Reforestation (New)	2420	2011	2031	10,000	Community-managed natural regeneration and reforestation of degraded lands, benefiting ~5,000 people.	World Vision	Certified
Sierra Leone	Gola Rainforest Conservation Project	5946	2017	2047	480,000	A large-scale REDD+ project conserving a critical biodiversity hotspot and providing benefits to ~24,000 people in 122 forest-edge communities.	The Royal Society for the Protection of Birds	Certified

Table 12: Plan Vivo Terrestrial carbon farming projects in Africa (Operational [September 2025](#))

Country	Project Name	Start Year	Projected End Year	Projected Sequestration Reduction (tCO ₂ e per year)	Key Activities & Beneficiaries	Project Proponent	Status
Ethiopia	Carbon Livelihoods	2023	2043	50,000	Helping communities restore watersheds through soil/water conservation, tree planting, and sustainable agricultural practices.	World Vision Ethiopia	In Development
Ethiopia	Trees for Prosperity	2022	2042	45,000	Community-led restoration of degraded forests, involving local communities in planting and protecting native tree species.	WeForest	Operational
Kenya	Livelihoods Mount Elgon	2012	2032	115,000	Working with over 30,000 farmers to implement sustainable agricultural land management and agroforestry.	Vi Agroforestry	Operational
Kenya, Tanzania, Uganda	The TIST Program	2006	2036	3,500,000+	A massive network supporting tens of thousands of subsistence farmers in restoring degraded lands through tree planting.	The International Small Group and Tree Planting Program	Operational
Malawi	Kulera Landscape REDD+ Program	2014	2034	182,000	A community-based REDD+ project empowering communities to manage forests, improve agriculture, and develop alternative livelihoods.	The Terra Viva Foundation	Operational
Malawi, Zambia	C-Quest Capital Community Reforestation	2021	2046	165,000	Engaging with smallholder farmers to establish woodlots and forests for sustainable timber, income, and carbon sequestration.	C-Quest Capital	Operational
Mozambique	Nhambita Community Carbon Project	2003	2028	15,000	One of the world's first carbon projects, pioneering methods for community-led forest restoration and agroforestry.	Envirotrade	Operational
Mozambique	Sofala Community Carbon Project	2014	2039	48,000	Supporting communities in the Gorongosa National Park buffer zone to conserve forests and adopt agroforestry.	Envirotrade	Operational
Uganda	Trees for Global Benefits	2003	2053	98,500	Supporting over 12,000 smallholder farmers in planting native trees for carbon sequestration, fruit, and timber.	Ecotrust Uganda	Operational
Zambia	Luangwa Community Forests Project	2021	2041	250,000	A large-scale project partnering with thousands of families to protect a critical wildlife corridor through forest conservation.	BioCarbon Partners	Operational

4.2.5 Market dynamics and institutional context

The African carbon market is growing rapidly as countries seek to mobilise climate finance through nature-based solutions. Several international initiatives aim to scale up carbon credit production on the continent.

One of the most prominent initiatives is the Africa Carbon Markets Initiative (ACMI), which aims to dramatically expand carbon credit generation across Africa while supporting sustainable development and job creation. According to the ACMI roadmap, the continent could increase carbon credit production nearly twenty-fold by 2030, generating significant climate finance flows for African economies (ACMI, 2022)

Growing interest from international buyers is also supporting market expansion. Corporations in sectors such as aviation, automotive manufacturing and digital services increasingly purchase African carbon credits to meet voluntary climate commitments. At the same time, several African governments are developing policy frameworks to support participation in global carbon markets (Yeates, 2024).

Despite this growing momentum, the development of carbon markets in Africa also faces a number of structural challenges. These include:

- high transaction costs associated with MRV systems
- limited availability of local validation and verification bodies (VVBs)
- dependence on international certification standards
- volatility in voluntary carbon credit prices
- the need for transparent benefit-sharing mechanisms.

Addressing these challenges will be essential to ensure that carbon certification systems generate long-term benefits for local communities while maintaining environmental integrity.

4.2.6 Lessons from African certification experiences for the EU CRCF

Experiences from African carbon markets provide several insights that are highly relevant for the implementation of the EU Carbon Removal and Carbon Farming Regulation (CRCF) and the broader evolution of land-based carbon certification systems.

First, African projects demonstrate how carbon markets can successfully engage large numbers of smallholder farmers through aggregation mechanisms, farmer groups and community cooperatives. These organisational models reduce transaction costs and enable participation in carbon markets despite the fragmented structure of agricultural landscapes. Similar approaches may be relevant in Europe, where farms are often small or medium-sized and participation in carbon farming schemes may require cooperative or landscape-scale approaches.

Second, African initiatives highlight the importance of transparent governance and benefit-sharing mechanisms. Successful projects frequently establish community institutions that manage carbon revenues and ensure that benefits reach participating farmers and local stakeholders. These governance arrangements contribute to social acceptance and long-term sustainability of carbon projects.

A further emerging dimension, particularly relevant to DigitAF, is the gap between project-level MRV systems and national greenhouse gas (GHG) inventories. The EURAF report *“Integrating Carbon Farming and Advanced Soil Mapping into Africa’s National GHG Inventories”* notes that Africa is simultaneously developing innovative carbon farming initiatives and continental-scale soil mapping programmes. However, much of the detailed data generated by carbon projects and soil monitoring initiatives is not yet systematically integrated into national AFOLU inventories submitted under UNFCCC reporting frameworks.

The report emphasises the importance of high-resolution soil carbon mapping initiatives, such as the African Soil Information Service (AFSIS) and national soil information systems, as enabling infrastructure for improving AFOLU accounting. These datasets could support transitions from IPCC Tier 1 default emission factors toward higher-tier (Tier 2 or Tier 3) reporting approaches, where countries use national data to produce more accurate greenhouse gas inventories.

Bridging this “data-to-policy” gap is directly aligned with the objectives of the DigitAF project. Digital MRV architectures that combine remote sensing, soil data platforms and locally collected monitoring data could enable scalable and cost-effective monitoring systems while ensuring interoperability with national reporting frameworks and international climate policy requirements.

Finally, the historical experience of land-based carbon mechanisms, such as the Clean Development Mechanism (CDM) and REDD+ initiatives, provides additional lessons for future certification frameworks. Analyses of these mechanisms highlight how overly complex rules, high transaction costs and limited local capacity constrained participation in many developing countries. Designing next-generation systems such as the CRCF therefore requires balancing environmental integrity with practical feasibility, ensuring that monitoring requirements remain robust while still accessible to land managers and project developers.

Together, these experiences suggest that future carbon farming frameworks should prioritise transparent governance, cost-effective MRV systems, strong integrity standards and interoperability with national climate reporting systems. In this context, African carbon certification initiatives provide valuable real-world experience that can inform the development of credible, inclusive and scalable carbon farming systems in Europe.

4.3 United States

4.3.1 Policy and governance context

In the United States, carbon farming has developed in a fragmented but highly innovative governance environment that combines federal agricultural programmes, voluntary carbon markets, philanthropic and research funding, private MRV providers, and growing corporate demand for climate-smart supply chains. Unlike the European Union, the United States does not have a single national certification framework for agricultural carbon removals. Instead, carbon farming is shaped by overlapping public and private initiatives, with the federal government increasingly supporting pilot programmes while private actors continue to drive methodological experimentation and market formation. This decentralised architecture has enabled rapid innovation, but it has also generated uneven standards, varying programme rules and limited harmonisation across initiatives.

A major turning point was the launch of the USDA **Partnerships for Climate-Smart Commodities** programme ([ref](#)), which committed very large public funding to pilot projects designed to scale climate-smart agricultural practices and create market demand for climate-smart commodities. The programme mobilised a wide range of actors, including commodity groups, corporations, universities, conservation organisations and farmer networks. This has made the U.S. case especially relevant to the CRCF, because it illustrates how carbon farming can be promoted not only through offset markets, but also through supply-chain programmes, outcome-based contracts and public support for adoption.

4.3.2 Main practices and project models

The principal carbon farming models emerging in the United States combine agroforestry, regenerative agriculture, soil carbon management, improved grazing, and climate-smart forestry practices. Agroforestry has become particularly important in policy and research discussions because it offers a relatively durable form of carbon sequestration while also delivering broader ecosystem services. Scientific literature has consistently shown that agroforestry systems can increase both aboveground and belowground carbon

stocks relative to conventional cropland or treeless pasture systems, while also improving biodiversity, water regulation and farm resilience. Yet agroforestry remains underdeveloped at national scale. This gap has prompted a series of adoption-focused initiatives, especially in the Midwest. The Savanna Institute has become one of the most visible actors in this field, promoting perennial agriculture and tree-based farming through research, farmer engagement, demonstration farms and policy advocacy. Its work is particularly important because it links carbon sequestration to viable farm business models, rather than treating agroforestry solely as a conservation add-on. The institute's growing prominence in climate-smart agriculture discussions also reflects the broader U.S. shift toward seeing agroforestry as a practical climate solution rather than a niche land-use option. (Parker, 2022; Souli, 2025)

Other important project models include soil-carbon-focused programmes based on cover crops, reduced tillage and improved nutrient management, as well as rangeland and silvopasture interventions. What is distinctive in the U.S. context is the coexistence of multiple “delivery models”: public subsidy programmes, private carbon contracts, climate-smart commodity supply chains, and demonstration-oriented research platforms. This plurality has generated innovation, but it has also made comparability and programme coherence more difficult.

4.3.3 Standards, tools and actors

The standards and tools landscape in the United States is diverse. Agricultural carbon projects may rely on voluntary carbon standards, proprietary programme rules, supply-chain accounting models, or public programme metrics. Rather than one dominant framework, there is a mosaic of registries, corporate programmes, agronomic platforms and project developers. This means that the “standard-setting” function is distributed across both public and private actors.

Key actors include USDA, research institutions, conservation organisations, agribusiness firms, carbon developers, private data platforms and MRV providers. In parallel, climate-smart forestry initiatives have pushed the frontier of measurement approaches by integrating remote sensing, machine learning and inventory systems to improve the quantification of carbon gains from forestry and agroforestry practices. The Stanford climate-smart forestry report (Hayes et al., 2023) is particularly relevant since it argues that improved MRV can unlock better incentives not only for reforestation and improved forest management, but also for agroforestry and tree-based systems on farms.

This diverse landscape matters for the CRCF because it shows that carbon farming standards do not emerge only from regulation. They also emerge from the interaction between registries, researchers, public programmes, corporate procurement and digital infrastructure. The U.S. case therefore offers an example of “distributed standardisation”: dynamic and innovative, but also difficult to harmonise.

4.3.4 MRV and methodological development

MRV remains one of the central bottlenecks in U.S. carbon farming. The diffuse nature of agricultural emissions, the heterogeneity of soils, and the long time horizons of biological sequestration make direct measurement expensive and uncertain. This has been recognised for over a decade. Earlier work on agricultural offset projects showed that the mitigation potential of agriculture is substantial, but that uptake remains constrained by the cost and complexity of quantification (Proville et al., 2020). Agricultural projects are therefore often underrepresented relative to their technical potential.

In response, the U.S. system has become a major site of experimentation in digital and hybrid MRV (Foucherot & Bellassen, 2011). The Rangeland Carbon Monitoring Program (Foster et al., 2023) is one example of an effort to build structured, tiered field methods for monitoring carbon in working landscapes, including soil carbon, herbaceous biomass, woody biomass and practice-specific indicators. Its importance lies not only in the indicators it selects, but in the way it links scientific rigour to practical field implementation.

At the same time, the U.S. is seeing rapid growth in private MRV tools, remote sensing applications and digital data platforms (Liao et al., 2023). This trend suggests that the future of carbon farming verification will depend less on a binary choice between field measurement and modelling, and more on hybrid systems that combine sampled field data, farm management records and geospatial analytics (Hurt et al., 2024). For the CRCF, this is a highly relevant lesson: harmonisation should not come at the expense of innovation, but innovation needs interoperable rules if it is to support trustworthy certification at scale.

4.3.5 Lessons for the EU CRCF

The United States offers five major lessons for the CRCF (EURAF [Research Report #143](#)):

1. Public funding can accelerate adoption even in the absence of a unified national carbon certification framework.
2. Agroforestry is far more likely to scale when it is tied to farmer-oriented business models, demonstration systems and regional advisory networks, rather than framed only as a carbon accounting exercise.
3. Distributed innovation can generate powerful new MRV tools, but without harmonisation it can also lead to methodological fragmentation.
4. Climate-smart commodity programmes show that carbon farming can be linked to value chains and procurement incentives, not only to offsets.
5. Carbon farming governance can evolve rapidly through public-private experimentation, but that model requires strong safeguards if credibility and comparability are to be maintained over time.

4.4 Canada

4.4.1 Policy and governance context

Canada presents a different model from the United States. Carbon farming is developing within a policy environment shaped by national climate targets and carbon pricing. This gives Canada a more hybrid governance profile: not fully centralised, but more structured than the U.S. voluntary-market mosaic. The government of Canada is currently designing a specific methodologic for soil enrichment protocol. In this context, the province of Quebec is especially significant because it combines a cap-and-trade carbon market infrastructure scheme, where a methodology was published in 2024 on afforestation/reforestation on private land where agroforestry practices may be eligible with alignment with the MAPAQ under that protocol.

The Canadian case is useful for the CRCF because it shows how agricultural mitigation can be embedded in broader climate governance rather than treated as a standalone offset market. It also shows that regional specificity matters. Carbon farming in Canada is not evolving uniformly across the country; it is strongly shaped by provincial institutions, sectoral structures and cooperative delivery models.

4.4.2 Main practices and project models

Canadian carbon farming initiatives increasingly extend beyond simple soil carbon narratives to include improved crop management, agronomic advisory services, carbon-sequestering practices in field crops, intensive grazing, and the integration of renewable energy and nutrient cycling into farm systems. The practical emphasis is often on making carbon-related practices agronomically and economically workable for farmers, rather than on carbon certification alone.

Example of the Canadian Alliance for Net-Zero Agri-food (CANZA), federal level. The initiative was founded in 2023 by Royal Bank of Canada, Loblaw Companies Ltd., Maple Leaf Foods, Nutrien, McCain Foods, BCG Centre for Canada's Future, Smart Prosperity Institute and the Arrell Food Institute. CANZA aims to accelerate climate action across Canadian agriculture, by collaborating with farmers, organizations and

researchers to develop and scale practical solutions that reduce emissions, improve environmental outcomes, and create new value across the Canadian agri-food system (Anon, 2025c).

On the other hand, a good provincial example is the collaboration between Coop Carbone and Sollio Agriculture through the AgroCarbone Grandes Cultures initiative in Quebec. This programme was launched to help farmers reduce and sequester greenhouse gas emissions while developing new protocols and business models adapted to Quebec's agricultural conditions. What makes this model noteworthy is that it places farmer participation and cooperative governance at the centre, rather than relying exclusively on external project developers. In effect, it treats carbon farming as a sectoral transition challenge rather than merely a credit-generation opportunity (Anon, 2023a).

4.4.3 Standards, tools and actors

The Canadian actor landscape includes agricultural cooperatives, regional carbon market organisations, agronomic service providers, financial actors and renewable energy developers. Among these, Sollio Cooperative Group is particularly important because of its scale and embeddedness in the agri-food system. Its sustainability programmes show how carbon farming and climate-smart practices can be delivered through institutions that farmers already know and use. This matters for the CRCF because uptake often depends less on abstract regulation than on trusted intermediary structures.

The role of cooperative networks is broader than one institution. Research on cooperative economic systems suggests that collaborative regional ecosystems can support innovation by linking farmers, finance, knowledge institutions and market actors. In the carbon farming context, this means that standards and methodologies are more likely to diffuse when embedded in networks of trust and mutual support than when offered only through arm's-length market contracts.

In this sense, Canada offers an important governance lesson: the delivery structure matters as much as the carbon methodology. Cooperative actors can reduce transaction costs, create legitimacy, and support practice adoption in ways that purely transactional carbon markets often struggle to achieve.

4.4.4 MRV and integrated monitoring approaches

Canadian carbon farming also points toward a more integrated understanding of MRV. Rather than treating carbon accounting as separate from agronomic services and digital agriculture, several Canadian initiatives are embedding monitoring within broader farm advisory and data systems. Sollio's digital tools and agronomic platforms are relevant here because they illustrate how farm-level environmental data can be linked to advisory services, precision agriculture and climate-oriented decision support.

A second distinctive feature is the connection between carbon farming and circular bioeconomy accounting. In Canada, mitigation on farms is increasingly linked not only to soil carbon but also to methane reduction, nutrient recycling and renewable energy generation. This broadens the scope of what counts as carbon farming-related mitigation and suggests that future certification systems may need to think across multiple farm-level carbon pathways rather than privileging one metric alone.

4.4.5 Lessons for the EU CRCF

Canada offers four particularly relevant lessons for the CRCF:

1. Cooperative governance can be a powerful delivery mechanism for carbon farming, especially where producer trust and long-term participation are essential.
2. Regional or provincial adaptation of methodologies may be necessary even within a larger national or supranational framework, suggesting that harmonisation should allow some contextual flexibility.
3. Carbon farming is more likely to scale when linked to agronomic services, business models and digital farm tools, rather than to carbon accounting in isolation.

4. Carbon farming can be integrated into wider circular bioeconomy and rural development strategies, which may increase both political legitimacy and farm-level value creation.

4.5 Comparison with EU CRCF

The experiences of carbon farming certification systems in Africa and North America provide valuable insights for the development of the European Union Carbon Removal and Carbon Farming Regulation (CRCF). While each region operates within distinct institutional, economic and ecological contexts, several similarities and differences can be identified in terms of governance structures, certification standards, monitoring systems and market actors.

The table below presents a comparative overview of key features of carbon farming initiatives in Africa, the United States and Canada, highlighting how these approaches relate to the emerging CRCF framework in the European Union. Overall, the comparison highlights several important differences between the regions. Carbon farming initiatives in Africa are strongly driven by international voluntary carbon markets and often focus on large-scale landscape restoration and community-based agroforestry projects. In contrast, the United States relies heavily on federal agricultural programmes and private-sector initiatives promoting climate-smart agriculture. Canada represents an intermediate model in which cooperative governance structures and carbon pricing frameworks support the development of carbon farming initiatives.

The emerging EU CRCF framework differs from these approaches by introducing a harmonised regulatory system for carbon removal certification. While voluntary markets play a central role in Africa and North America, the CRCF aims to establish common European standards for monitoring, reporting and verification while ensuring environmental integrity and transparency.

Experiences from Africa and North America therefore provide valuable lessons for the development of the CRCF, particularly with regard to farmer participation, digital monitoring systems and the integration of carbon farming within broader agricultural sustainability strategies.

Table 13: Carbon farming certification systems in Africa, the United States, Canada and the EU CRCF

Dimension	Africa	United States	Canada	EU CRCF
Governance framework	Predominantly voluntary carbon markets with international standards and project-based initiatives. Many projects operate through NGOs, international developers and community-based organisations.	Decentralised system combining federal agricultural programmes, voluntary carbon markets and private-sector initiatives. No unified national carbon farming certification framework.	Hybrid system combining national climate policy, carbon pricing mechanisms and cooperative governance structures. Strong role of agricultural cooperatives and provincial initiatives.	EU-wide regulatory framework currently being implemented through the Carbon Removal and Carbon Farming Regulation (CRCF), aiming to establish harmonised certification rules for carbon removals and carbon farming activities.
Main certification standards	Verified Carbon Standard (Verra), Gold Standard and Plan Vivo dominate AFOLU projects. Some additional ecosystem certification schemes (FSC, Rainforest Alliance) also operate in agroforestry contexts.	Multiple voluntary carbon standards and private programmes operate simultaneously, including Verra and private carbon programmes developed by companies and agricultural platforms.	Emerging agricultural carbon programmes often linked to cooperative initiatives and voluntary standards; pilot methodologies developed through organisations such as Coop Carbone.	CRCF will establish EU-wide certification methodologies for carbon removals and carbon farming practices, focusing on permanence, additionality and sustainability criteria.
Main carbon farming practices	Agroforestry, forest restoration, REDD+, sustainable land management and community-based landscape restoration projects.	Agroforestry, regenerative agriculture, soil carbon sequestration, improved grazing management and climate-smart commodity production.	Soil carbon sequestration, improved crop management, renewable natural gas from agricultural residues and cooperative carbon farming initiatives.	Soil carbon sequestration, agroforestry, peatland restoration, forest management and biochar production.
MRV systems	MRV systems primarily developed through international carbon standards; monitoring often combines remote sensing with community-based monitoring approaches.	MRV approaches increasingly combine field measurements, digital monitoring technologies and modelling tools to estimate carbon sequestration in agricultural systems.	Monitoring systems are emerging through cooperative initiatives and pilot projects combining agronomic data, carbon accounting methodologies and regional carbon market requirements.	CRCF aims to establish harmonised monitoring, reporting and verification methodologies based on standardized EU rules, supported by digital monitoring tools and scientific data.

Role of farmers and communities	Strong involvement of local communities and smallholder farmers, particularly in agroforestry and landscape restoration projects. Benefit-sharing mechanisms are often integrated into project design.	Farmers participate primarily through voluntary programmes and pilot projects supported by federal funding or private carbon markets.	Farmers often participate through cooperative networks and producer organisations that facilitate access to climate programmes and carbon market initiatives.	CRCF aims to support farmer participation in carbon farming initiatives through incentive mechanisms and integration with the EU Common Agricultural Policy.
Market actors	International project developers, NGOs, development agencies and voluntary carbon market buyers.	Agribusiness companies, carbon market platforms, research institutions and federal programmes.	Agricultural cooperatives, regional carbon market organisations and renewable energy developers.	EU institutions, national governments, farmers, carbon market actors and certification bodies.
Key opportunities	Large potential for nature-based carbon sequestration, strong community engagement and biodiversity co-benefits.	Strong innovation ecosystem with research institutions and climate-smart agriculture initiatives.	Integration of carbon farming with cooperative governance and circular bioeconomy strategies.	Harmonised certification framework, strong policy integration and potential links with CAP incentives.
Key challenges	MRV costs, governance complexity and ensuring equitable benefit sharing.	Fragmented governance and lack of unified certification standards.	Need for scaling carbon farming initiatives and developing consistent monitoring systems.	Implementation challenges, methodological complexity and ensuring farmer participation at scale.

Part 5 - Linkages between carbon farming certification, CAP policies and nature policies.

The EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification Framework (CRCF) is developing within an increasingly complex policy landscape that combines agricultural support instruments under the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), emerging biodiversity finance mechanisms, voluntary carbon markets and international carbon accounting rules under the Paris Agreement. These frameworks are not isolated; they interact across funding streams, monitoring systems and land-use practices. Understanding their linkages is essential to prevent fragmentation, avoid double counting, ensure fairness for land managers and deliver climate and biodiversity objectives in a coherent and mutually reinforcing manner.

5.1 CRCF and CAP

CAP instruments remain the primary financial driver of land-use change in Europe, particularly through eco-schemes, agri-environment-climate measures (AECMs), and rural development funding. Under the proposed 2028–2034 Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF), CAP support will be embedded within new National and Regional Partnership Plans (NRPP), explicitly designed to move beyond fragmented EU spending and deliver more coherent, territorial and impact-oriented investment across agriculture, rural development, climate and innovation policies (DG-AGRI, 2026). While CAP will continue to prioritise farmers' income support (with a ring-fenced minimum of EUR 293.7 billion), Member States will be encouraged to mobilise additional non-ring-fenced resources and complementary EU instruments to address environmental and climate objectives.

Despite this evolution, current CAP instruments largely remain action-based or practice-based, rewarding compliance with prescribed measures rather than verified environmental outcomes. CRCF introduces a complementary logic: certification of quantified carbon removals and emission reductions, combined with mandatory sustainability safeguards. This creates the basis for outcome-based finance that can mobilise private capital alongside public support, consistent with the MFF objective of leveraging synergies between EU funding streams and market-based mechanisms.

Evidence from Climate Farm Demo project (ClimateFarmDemo, 2026), coming from Deliverable 6.1 "Incentivizing farm-level climate action through rewarding mechanisms. A categorization framework", shows that farm-level climate action is currently supported through a diverse and fragmented mix of rewarding mechanisms, including direct payments, grants, advisory services, labels, and voluntary carbon credits. No single mechanism is sufficient; instead, combinations of instruments are required to reflect farm heterogeneity and differing objectives. Mitigation incentives are more developed than those targeting climate adaptation or biodiversity, while blended finance approaches remain limited but are gaining attention.

CRCF therefore represents a structural shift: from CAP-funded incentives toward outcome-based certification capable of attracting private investment. As neither of the two are sufficient alone to finance these projects, we need to coordinate them, as they enable sequenced financing pathways, whereby CAP-funded practices (such as agroforestry establishment, soil management, or landscape diversification) may later become eligible for certified removals, provided additionality, permanence, and monitoring criteria are met. In this way, public funding can de-risk early adoption and innovation, while carbon markets reward verified outcomes and contribute to long-term farm resilience and competitiveness, objectives explicitly highlighted in the post-2027 CAP reform debate.

Farms that are already participating in EU-funded innovation projects are generating measurable climate and biodiversity benefits, yet remain largely excluded from voluntary markets due to high transaction costs and rigid additionality rules. Facilitating earlier access to CRCF-aligned certification for such farms would directly support the MFF objective of integrated programming and could help bridge public and private

finance, reward early movers, and accelerate the transition toward climate-smart and nature-positive agricultural systems.

5.2 Agroforestry as a convergence point between carbon farming and biodiversity policy

Within the Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification Framework (CRCF) (DG-CLIMA, 2026), agroforestry emerges as a key activity for operationalising the integration of climate mitigation with biodiversity protection and ecosystem service provision (European Commission, CRCF Draft Annex, presented during the expert group on the 5th of February 2026). Unlike most carbon farming practices, which primarily address either soil organic carbon or biomass sequestration, agroforestry systems integrate woody perennials into productive agricultural land, enabling simultaneous carbon sequestration in soils and living biomass while increasing landscape structural complexity. This multifunctionality places agroforestry in a particularly strong position to meet CRCF requirements, which extend beyond carbon accounting to include mandatory sustainability and environmental integrity criteria (Lawson, Monteleone, et al., 2025).

The CRCF embeds biodiversity and ecosystem services directly into its certification logic through the QU.A.L.I.T.Y framework and the “do no significant harm” principle. In the new draft they explicitly indicate that certified activities must demonstrate compliance with environmental safeguards and deliver at least one positive sustainability outcome, with explicit reference to biodiversity protection, soil health, water regulation, and ecosystem resilience. For agroforestry systems, these outcomes are intrinsically linked to system design, including the retention and establishment of trees and hedgerows, mixed species composition, and long-term management of woody elements. CRCF draft methodologies prohibit the removal of existing trees and carbon-rich landscape features and promote practices that enhance ecological stability, ensuring that carbon removals are not achieved at the expense of ecosystem integrity.

This approach represents a substantive departure from most voluntary carbon standards, where biodiversity and ecosystem services are treated as optional or purely ancillary outcomes. Under CRCF, biodiversity is formally framed as a sustainability co-benefit subject to mandatory safeguards and monitoring requirements. However, it is not a primary certification objective. While this already marks progress compared to voluntary market practices, it arguably understates the central role of ecosystems in delivering durable climate mitigation. From a policy perspective, biodiversity and ecosystem services should not be regarded merely as secondary co-benefits of carbon farming, but as fundamental environmental objectives in their own right.

This would align CRCF even more closely with the EU Nature Restoration Regulation ([2024/1991](#)), which introduces binding restoration targets at EU level and specific indicators for agricultural and forest ecosystems, including soil organic carbon stocks, the share of agricultural land with high-diversity landscape features (such as hedgerows, tree rows and scattered trees), and overall ecosystem condition. Agroforestry directly contributes to several of these indicators by increasing woody elements within agricultural landscapes, improving soil structure and carbon content, and enhancing habitat connectivity. This highlights the opportunity, and the need, for closer alignment between CRCF and restoration policy, moving beyond a “carbon-first with co-benefits” model toward integrated certification approaches in which climate mitigation and ecosystem recovery are treated as mutually reinforcing pillars.

EURAF Policy Brief #18 *"Agroforestry and the EU Nature Restoration Regulation"* (Lawson, Hahn, et al., 2025) further highlights the role of agroforestry as a delivery mechanism for Nature Restoration objectives. Agroforestry trees and hedgerows are explicitly recognised as “high-diversity landscape features” under the Nature Restoration Regulation, including when they remain productive, and can be monitored at parcel level using CAP LPIS systems. The policy brief proposes harmonising CAP, NRR and CRCF spatial data within a unified Rural Land Parcel Information System, enabling consistent reporting across biodiversity, carbon removals and land-use change frameworks. In parallel, Policy Brief #69, *"Governance and Performance of the CAP: the Role of Agroforestry"* (Lawson et al., 2024) emphasises that carbon farming certification should follow CAP-supported tree establishment, reinforcing a sequenced financing model in which public funding enables adoption while CRCF rewards verified outcomes.

Scientific evidence compiled under the DigitAF project further reinforces the suitability of agroforestry for this integrated policy approach. Recent synthesis of EU-funded research confirms agroforestry's role as a core nature-based solution for resilient agricultural landscapes, delivering biodiversity enhancement, soil health improvement and climate adaptation simultaneously. The CORDIS Results Pack showcases 12 EU-funded projects supporting nature-based solutions in agriculture (CORDIS, 2026). DigitAF Deliverable 3.3 demonstrates predominantly positive or neutral biodiversity outcomes across multiple functional groups, particularly where agroforestry increases landscape heterogeneity and reconnects semi-natural habitats (DigitAF D3.3, 2024). These biodiversity effects underpin key regulating ecosystem services, including pollination, biological pest control, erosion reduction, nutrient cycling and microclimate regulation, as also synthesised in *Agroforestry for biodiversity and the protection of ecosystems* (2024). Importantly, DigitAF's proof-of-concept biodiversity assessment shows that such outcomes can be monitored through proportionate hybrid MRV approaches combining spatial data, field observations and scientifically grounded proxies, providing a practical pathway for implementing CRCF sustainability requirements without excessive monitoring burdens on land managers (DigitAF D3.3, 2024).

CRCF further requires that biodiversity and ecosystem outcomes be explicitly documented and monitored alongside carbon removals, creating a direct link between certification and ecosystem performance. By embedding ecosystem services within certification requirements, CRCF positions agroforestry as a delivery mechanism not only for climate mitigation but also for broader environmental objectives under the EU Biodiversity Strategy and Nature Restoration Regulation.

At the implementation level, agroforestry systems are compatible with existing CAP administrative and spatial frameworks, including LPIS/IACS, enabling alignment between CAP-supported land-use practices and CRCF-certified outcomes. The Agroforestry Carbon Farming Management Plans proposed in Policy Brief #66 (Lawson, Kara, et al., 2025) illustrates how parcel-level planning can integrate carbon accounting, biodiversity objectives and farm management decisions in a coherent framework consistent with CAP governance structures. Such approaches support the practical translation of CRCF sustainability criteria into farm-level implementation.

In this context, agroforestry exemplifies CRCF's ambition to move beyond single-metric carbon accounting toward integrated land-use certification. By linking carbon removals with biodiversity enhancement and ecosystem service provision within a single regulatory framework, CRCF positions agroforestry as a flagship activity demonstrating how climate and nature objectives can be jointly addressed in agricultural landscapes. The effective implementation of CRCF methodologies for agroforestry will therefore be central to assessing whether the framework succeeds in delivering genuinely integrated climate–nature outcomes at scale.

5.3 Nature credits: complementary but distinct from carbon certification

In parallel with the development of the Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification Framework (CRCF), the European Union is advancing nature credit frameworks to mobilise private finance for ecosystem restoration. In July 2025, the European Commission adopted the *Roadmap towards Nature Credits* ([COM\(2025\) 374 final](#)), launched an exploratory process to develop high-integrity biodiversity credit markets in the EU. The initiative responds to the persistent biodiversity finance gap, estimated at €37.4 billion per year in the EU, which cannot be bridged by public funding alone despite the target of allocating 10% of the EU budget to biodiversity and 35% to climate and environmental objectives. While CRCF formally recognises biodiversity and ecosystem services as sustainability co-benefits of certified carbon removals, it remains primarily a carbon accounting framework. Nature credits, by contrast, are being developed as instruments to recognise verified improvements in ecosystem condition and biodiversity, supported by science-based indicators and context-specific assessment methodologies.

This dual policy track highlights the need for alignment, but not merger, between CRCF and emerging nature credit frameworks. CRCF provides robust methodologies for quantifying carbon removals, managing permanence risks and ensuring traceability through registries. Nature credits must address ecological

complexity, spatial heterogeneity and long recovery times that cannot be captured through carbon accounting alone. Attempting to combine both objectives within a single crediting instrument risks methodological dilution and could prioritise easily measurable carbon outcomes over ecologically meaningful restoration.

The Commission's Roadmap towards Nature Credits therefore foresees complementary but interoperable systems, with coordination across CRCF delegated acts, CAP instruments, the Nature Restoration Regulation and EU sustainability reporting frameworks. CRCF-certified activities may generate biodiversity co-benefits that are relevant for nature credit schemes, while nature credits may support restoration actions that do not necessarily produce measurable carbon removals. Alignment is expected through shared governance principles, proportional MRV approaches and interoperable geospatial registries.

Stakeholder contributions, including the landowners' organisation, further underline the importance of maintaining conceptual separation between carbon removals and biodiversity outcomes while ensuring coherence across policy frameworks. Differences in measurability, permanence and additionality mean that biodiversity should not be reduced to a secondary attribute of carbon farming. Instead, dedicated nature credit frameworks are required to value ecosystem restoration appropriately, while CRCF continues to provide a carbon-focused certification pathway.

From a land-use perspective, agroforestry illustrates how such complementarity could function in practice. CRCF can certify carbon sequestration in soils and biomass associated with agroforestry systems, while nature credits can reward biodiversity enhancement, habitat connectivity, water regulation and ecosystem resilience generated by the same land-use interventions, provided that each outcome is assessed and verified through distinct methodologies. This layered approach enables land managers to access multiple revenue streams reflecting different ecosystem services, while avoiding double counting by maintaining clear separation between carbon accounting and biodiversity valuation. Ensuring transparency across the registry and applying consistent safeguards will be essential to preserve environmental integrity and prevent overlapping claims.

Taken together, CRCF and emerging nature credit frameworks point toward an integrated climate–nature finance architecture based on alignment rather than consolidation. By keeping carbon certification and biodiversity restoration as distinct yet interoperable systems, the EU can ensure that each environmental objective is measured and governed appropriately, while enabling coherent implementation across CAP policies, the Nature Restoration Regulation and private finance initiatives.

5.4 Toward an integrated climate–nature finance architecture

Taken together, CRCF, CAP instruments, emerging nature credit frameworks and international carbon markets are gradually converging toward a multifunctional land-use finance model in which climate mitigation, biodiversity restoration and agricultural resilience are addressed in an integrated manner. Rather than operating as isolated policy silos, these mechanisms increasingly interact across farm management, spatial planning and private finance, creating new opportunities for complementary funding approaches that reward environmental outcomes alongside food production.

Agroforestry exemplifies this convergence in practical terms. By embedding trees within productive agricultural systems, agroforestry links certified carbon removals with biodiversity enhancement, soil restoration and climate adaptation, while maintaining economic viability for farmers. It therefore provides a concrete test case for integrated certification and financing approaches, demonstrating how land-use systems can simultaneously deliver climate, nature and rural development objectives.

Digital MRV tools developed under DigitAF (tools [catalogue](#)) offer a practical blueprint for operationalising this integration. By combining soil carbon modelling, biomass accounting, spatial data and biodiversity proxies within unified workflows, DigitAF aims at demonstrating how CRCF sustainability requirements can be implemented at parcel and farm scale while keeping transaction costs proportionate. Such multi-purpose

systems are essential for enabling agroforestry and other multifunctional practices to participate in certification frameworks without imposing prohibitive monitoring burdens, particularly for smaller farms.

However, the effectiveness of this emerging architecture will depend on coordinated governance across multiple levels. Key enabling conditions include interoperable registries linking CAP spatial systems with CRCF and future nature credit platforms, recognition of early adopters who have delivered environmental benefits prior to formal certification, proportional verification approaches adapted to farm diversity, and a clear conceptual separation, yet operational alignment, between carbon certification and biodiversity valuation. Without these elements, Europe risks replicating the fragmentation observed in voluntary carbon markets, increasing administrative complexity and undermining land manager participation.

CRCF therefore represents more than a standalone certification scheme. It has the potential to serve as a backbone for integrated climate-nature finance in Europe, connecting CAP-supported land management with private investment and international carbon accounting frameworks. Realising this potential will require embedding CRCF within CAP policy design, aligning methodologies with Nature Restoration objectives, and ensuring compatibility with Article 6 accounting rules, while maintaining high standards of environmental integrity.

If successfully implemented, this integrated approach could shift European land-use policy from fragmented incentives toward outcome-based stewardship, rewarding farmers and landowners not only for carbon removals, but for sustaining the ecosystems on which long-term climate resilience and food security ultimately depend.

Part 6 The Buyers Club, Public Procurement and Biodiversity

The European Climate Law makes a commitment to climate neutrality by 2050, and promises net-negative emissions thereafter. Yet the EU Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF [2024/3012](#)) recognises that current deployment rate of durable carbon dioxide removal (CDR) technologies and high-integrity carbon farming systems remains grossly insufficient to meet this trajectory. The CRCF, Roadmap Towards Nature Credits ([Jul 2025](#)), Bioeconomy Strategy ([Nov 2025](#)), and the innovation Fund "Net Zero Technologies Call" ([Nov 2025](#)), all emphasise the need for carbon removals, and particularly carbon farming, to be linked as closely as possible to biodiversity and ecosystem benefits.

The European Commission has repeatedly acknowledged the existence of a structural “demand gap” that limits investment in high-quality carbon removals, and studies commissioned by the Commission on a purchasing programme for permanent carbon removals confirm that insufficient predictable demand is the primary bottleneck (McDonald et al., 2025; Ramboll Management Consulting, 2025).

In response, the Commission’s Bioeconomy Strategy proposes two complementary demand-creation instruments:

- **An EU Buyers’ Club (Private Demand)** - which is a voluntary mechanism designed to aggregate corporate purchasing power and secure long-term offtake agreements for CRCF-certified credits.
- **A Pilot Public Procurement Programme (Public Demand)** - which is a publicly financed purchasing scheme, primarily via the Innovation Fund, aimed at stimulating demand at competitive prices (Battersby et al., 2024).

Together, these mechanisms seek to overcome the so-called “valley of death”, where technology is proven but cannot be developed because it is commercially unviable.

6.1 The EU Buyers’ Club: Concept and Market Function

The Buyers’ Club is conceived as a centralized demand aggregator designed to connect corporate net-zero commitments with the emerging supply of CRCF-certified removal units. Rather than constituting a regulatory obligation, it functions as a coordinated market platform that could be implemented through a public financial intermediary, with the European Commission acting as convener, rule-setter and governance architect.

Recent reporting confirms that the Commission has formally endorsed the Buyers’ Club as a financing strategy for CRCF credits (Breilean, 2025). The initiative is explicitly framed as a mechanism to stimulate voluntary corporate demand for both permanent removals and carbon farming credits. In parallel, Carbon Herald notes that the Buyers’ Club forms part of a broader CRCF operationalisation package, which also includes the development of an EU carbon farming database aimed at facilitating monitoring, reporting and verification (MRV) and methodological standardisation (Ranevska, 2025).

The underlying economic logic is relatively straightforward. High-durability removal pathways such as Direct Air Carbon Capture and Storage (DACCS) currently cost several hundred euros per tonne, well above EU ETS allowance prices and most voluntary carbon market transactions. In the absence of predictable, long-term revenue streams, project developers struggle to secure commercial financing. The Buyers’ Club seeks to address this constraint by aggregating corporate demand and translating it into long-term offtake agreements. By pooling commitments from multiple companies and guaranteeing future credit purchases at predefined prices, the platform aims to enhance the bankability of removal projects and reduce investment risk.

Nevertheless, the central challenge is not certification alone but effective demand creation, “*the devil is in the demand*” (Martel et al., 2026). Voluntary corporate appetite for high-cost, high-integrity removals remains uncertain, particularly in the context of tightening anti-greenwashing regulation. Critical

perspectives have therefore questioned whether a purely voluntary Buyers' Club can generate sufficient scale to meet the Union's long-term climate objectives (Lengyel, 2025).

6.2 Public Procurement to support carbon markets

The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) is predominantly based on funding "interventions" or "activities" rather than payments based on results. In contrast, the Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF) focuses mainly on climate mitigation results, with, as yet undeveloped, options for higher payments if co-benefits can be demonstrated by carbon removal projects.

The inability of the CAP to reward quantitatively monitored results, is partially blamed on restrictions imposed by WTO rules. These are rules which do not apply to climate priorities (footnote), but for farmers, the transition from activity-based subsidies to outcome-based remuneration implies greater exposure to performance risk, complex monitoring, reporting and verification (MRV) requirements, and market volatility.

While CAP payments offer relative predictability, CRCF-certified carbon farming credits depend on monitored outcomes, payment reductions made for risks and uncertainty, and stability of voluntary corporate demand. MRV costs, data requirements and uncertainty regarding future credit prices are significant barriers - particularly for small and medium-sized farmers. Without adequate technical assistance and simplified interoperability between CAP, CRCF and soil monitoring frameworks, participation risks becoming concentrated among larger and better-capitalised operators.

The interaction between CAP, CRCF and procurement mechanisms raises significant governance concerns. As emphasised by the CREDIBLE Focus Group, safeguards are necessary to prevent double funding where farmers receive CAP support and carbon credit revenues for the same activity without demonstrable additionality. Potential conflicts with State aid rules must also be addressed, and public finance must complement, rather than substitute, private investment to preserve market integrity. Without clear coordination, overlapping instruments may increase administrative burden rather than generate policy coherence.

At the same time, the demand side is increasingly shaped by horizontal compliance-oriented regulation. The forthcoming Green Claims Directive introduces stricter requirements for the substantiation and independent verification of environmental claims ([Kemp et al. 2025](#)). Although not a carbon market instrument per se, the Directive reshapes corporate incentives by limiting the scope for unsubstantiated neutrality claims and increasing legal and reputational risk associated with low-integrity offsets.

For companies, this may transform high-integrity CRCF-certified removals from a purely voluntary reputational choice into a compliance-relevant necessity for defensible climate communication. For farmers, stronger claim regulation could enhance the credibility and potential value of certified carbon farming units, provided methodologies are robust and additionality clearly demonstrated. However, if the Directive significantly restricts offset-based narratives and favours contribution claims over compensation, voluntary corporate demand may remain constrained.

In this sense, while the Buyers' Club and public procurement aim to construct voluntary and semi-public demand, the long-term stability of the carbon farming market may ultimately depend on compliance-oriented frameworks that discipline corporate claims. The evolution of carbon removals in Europe therefore sits at the intersection of agricultural policy reform, public market-making, and corporate environmental liability, a complex policy mix in which regulatory coherence will determine whether demand becomes structurally embedded or remains fragile and voluntary.

6.3 Regulatory Tightening: The Green Claims Directive

Corporate demand for CRCF-certified credits, and therefore the viability of the Buyers' Club, will also be significantly shaped by horizontal EU anti-greenwashing regulation. The forthcoming Green Claims Directive

introduces stricter requirements for the substantiation and independent verification of environmental claims, reinforcing the legal accountability of companies that communicate climate neutrality or carbon compensation strategies (Vidal Morant et al., 2025).

This evolving regulatory environment has direct implications for the Buyers' Club. By tightening the conditions under which companies can make neutrality or offset-based claims, the Directive reduces the space for low-integrity credits and increases the reputational and legal risks associated with weakly substantiated compensation strategies. In principle, this could strengthen demand for high-integrity CRCF-certified removals aggregated through the Buyers' Club, as companies seek defensible and verifiable climate actions (Guidi & Aubert, 2025).

At the same time, stricter claim rules, particularly if they limit the use of offset-based neutrality claims for temporary sequestration, may constrain overall voluntary demand. As highlighted in the Project CREDIBLE analysis (Mal, 2025), this creates a dual effect: integrity is strengthened, but market scale may remain limited if corporate actors shift toward contribution-based narratives rather than compensation claims. The Buyers' Club therefore operates within a regulatory context in which demand is not only aggregated, but increasingly disciplined by compliance-oriented environmental communication rules.

Table 14 summarises three methods of stimulating demand for carbon farming: (a) Buyers Clubs, which are market catalyst stimulating voluntary groups of operators, providing markets and reducing transaction costs, but which are currently constrained by lack of corporate appetite and worries over greenwashing; (b) Public Procurement, which can provide early liquidity for operators and stabilise prices, but which is insufficient to deliver at the gigatonne-scale; (c) EU ETS Integration, which could massively shift demand from the voluntary to mandatory sector but which has problems of "fungibility" between permanent industrial carbon units and temporary agricultural units, and which would be seen as unfair to the agricultural sectors which are high emitters, with little opportunity for mitigation.

Table 14: Characteristics of the Buyers' Club Public Procurement and EU ETS Integration

Dimension	EU Buyers' Club	Pilot Public Procurement Programme	EU ETS (Potential Integration of CRCF Credits)
Nature of Instrument	Voluntary private demand aggregation mechanism	Public purchasing mechanism (Innovation Fund)	Compliance-based carbon pricing system
Legal Basis	Policy initiative under Bioeconomy Strategy (non-binding)	Innovation Fund Regulation + Commission calls	EU ETS Directive (compliance legislation)
Type of Demand	Voluntary corporate net-zero commitments	Public anchor demand	Mandatory compliance demand
Primary Objective	Overcome first-mover disadvantage; create bankability	Provide liquidity and price discovery	Ensure legally binding emission reductions
Market Signal Strength	Medium (depends on corporate participation)	Medium–High (public financial backing)	High (legally enforced compliance demand)
Price Formation	Bilateral/aggregated offtake agreements	Competitive reverse auctions	Market-based allowance price
Risk Allocation	Shared between buyers and developers	Public sector absorbs early risk	Compliance obligation on regulated entities
Role in Carbon Farming	Purchases CRCF-certified carbon farming credits	May procure carbon farming units	Currently excludes CRCF removals from compliance (future review possible)
Durability Preference	Likely stronger focus on permanent removals (DACCS, BECCS), but may include carbon farming	Can prioritise high-durability via auction criteria	Strong preference for emissions reductions; removals not yet fungible
Interaction with Green Claims Directive	High relevance (corporate claim substantiation required)	Limited (credits likely counted toward EU targets)	Less exposed to voluntary claim scrutiny
Scale Potential (Short Term)	Limited–Moderate	Moderate (budget-constrained)	Very High (largest carbon market globally)
Scale Potential (Long Term)	Dependent on voluntary demand	Dependent on EU budget expansion	Structural and predictable if CRCF credits admitted
Integrity Safeguards	CRCF Q.U.A.L.I.T.Y criteria	CRCF + public procurement rules	Strict MRV under ETS Directive
Key Limitation	Voluntary demand uncertainty	Budget limitations and state aid constraints	Political sensitivity of allowing removals for compliance

Part 7. Conclusions

Carbon farming is gaining increasing attention as a promising approach to support climate mitigation in the agricultural sector while simultaneously delivering important environmental co-benefits such as improved soil health, biodiversity enhancement, and greater resilience of farming systems. As the European Union moves towards its climate neutrality objectives, land-based carbon sequestration and sustainable land management practices are expected to play a growing role within broader climate and agricultural policy frameworks.

This report has analysed the current policy landscape and MRV approaches for carbon farming across voluntary and statutory systems. The findings highlight that carbon farming initiatives are emerging within a complex governance environment that includes voluntary carbon markets, agricultural policy instruments such as the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), and evolving regulatory frameworks such as the EU Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF). While voluntary carbon markets have contributed to the early development of methodologies and certification systems, important challenges remain regarding transparency, environmental integrity, and the consistency of monitoring and accounting approaches.

A key element for the credibility and scalability of carbon farming is the establishment of robust Monitoring, Reporting and Verification (MRV) systems. Reliable MRV frameworks are essential to ensure that carbon removals and emission reductions are measurable, verifiable, and transparently accounted for. In this regard, digital technologies, remote sensing, and integrated data platforms can significantly improve monitoring efficiency and reduce transaction costs, making carbon farming more accessible and scalable.

Strengthening the role of carbon farming within EU climate policy will also require greater integration between existing policy frameworks. In particular, improved alignment between the LULUCF Regulation and the Effort Sharing Regulation in national greenhouse gas reporting could provide greater visibility of the mitigation opportunities available in the land sector, including the possibility for livestock farmers to offset part of their non-CO₂ emissions through carbon sequestration generated by tree planting and agroforestry practices.

At the same time, stronger integration with agricultural policy will be essential. This includes improving the quantification of the climate impacts of CAP interventions and prioritising, in future CAP programming periods, those measures that deliver the greatest climate mitigation and adaptation benefits.

Improved spatial data and monitoring systems will also be critical. Consistent geospatial mapping of afforestation, agroforestry and landscape features across EU policy frameworks, including the CAP, LULUCF, the Nature Restoration Regulation, the EU Deforestation Regulation and the CRCF, would help reduce administrative inconsistencies and improve the reliability of monitoring systems. Ensuring full implementation of EU geospatial data standards, including the High Value Datasets Implementing Regulation ([2023/138](#)) for IACS, LPIS and GSAA datasets, will further strengthen the transparency and credibility of monitoring and certification systems.

Among the different land management practices considered within carbon farming, agroforestry represents a particularly promising solution. By integrating trees with crops and livestock systems, agroforestry can enhance carbon sequestration while simultaneously providing multiple environmental and socio-economic benefits, including improved soil fertility, reduced erosion, enhanced biodiversity, and diversified farm income. Despite these advantages, agroforestry remains underrepresented in many carbon certification schemes and policy frameworks, highlighting the need for stronger integration within carbon farming initiatives and MRV methodologies. In this context, recognising the contribution of early adopters who have already implemented agroforestry and other carbon farming practices could help strengthen incentives and ensure a fair transition towards emerging certification frameworks.

In this context, the DigitAF project contributes to advancing the digitalisation of agroforestry systems and improving the availability of reliable monitoring tools for carbon farming practices. By exploring innovative

digital approaches for data collection, monitoring, and decision support, DigitAF supports the development of more transparent, efficient, and scalable MRV systems that can facilitate the wider adoption of agroforestry and other carbon farming practices across Europe.

Overall, carbon farming has the potential to become an important component of the EU's climate mitigation strategy and a key instrument for achieving the Union's climate neutrality objectives. However, its success will depend on the development of credible certification frameworks, harmonised methodologies, robust MRV infrastructures, and coherent policy support. Strengthening digital monitoring systems, improving policy coordination across climate and agricultural frameworks, and promoting practices such as agroforestry will be essential to unlock the full potential of carbon farming as part of the transition towards climate-neutral, resilient and sustainable agricultural systems in Europe.

References

- Abebe, S., Barton, D. N., & Rusch, G. (2011). *A review of the cost-effectiveness and performance of selected Verifiable Emission Reduction (VER) carbon offsets*.
<https://policymix.nina.no/Portals/policymix/Documents/Carbon%20offsets%20-%20Policymix-FUNCiTre%20Joint%20Technical%20Brief%20-%20final.pdf>
- ACMI. (2022). *Roadmap Report*. Africa Carbon Markets Initiative.
https://www.seforall.org/system/files/2022-11/acmi_roadmap_report_2022.pdf
- Anon. (2023a). *Coop Carbone and Sollio Agriculture launch the AgroCarbone Grandes Cultures initiative*. Sollio.ag.
https://sollio.ag/en/media/coop-carbone-and-sollio-agriculture-launch-agrocarbone-grandes-cultures-initiative?utm_source=chatgpt.com
- Anon. (2023b, August 24). *Ultimate guide to Africa's 47 afforestation and reforestation projects*. *Green.Earth*.
<https://www.green.earth/blog/carbon-ar-afforestation-reforestation-projects-africa>
- Anon. (2024). *Introduction to the Voluntary Carbon Market in Africa*. Removall-Carbon.
<https://www.removeall-carbon.com/en/introduction-to-the-voluntary-carbon-market-in-africa-key-trends-and-opportunities/>
- Anon. (2025a). *Climate Action*. Website of the Federal Government | Bundesregierung.
<https://www.bundesregierung.de/breg-en/issues/climate-action>
- Anon. (2025b). *Farm and Supply Chain Certification in Cocoa in Wet and Central Africa* (No. Document A-19-SRCL-B-CH). Rainforest Alliance.
<https://knowledge.rainforest-alliance.org/docs/policy-for-farm-and-supply-chain-certification-in-cocoa-in-west-and-central-africa>
- Anon. (2025c, September 14). *Home*. CANZA - Unlocking Value, Turning Outcomes into Real Investment and Measurable Impact across Canada; Canadian Alliance for Net-Zero Agri-food. <https://canza.ca/>
- Anon. (2026a). *About NOBV – NOB*. <https://www.nobveenweiden.nl/en/about-nobv/>
- Anon. (2026b). *Oncra – Open Natural Carbon Removal Accounting*. <https://oncra.org/>
- Anon. (2026c). *Proba Registry*. <https://proba.earth/registry>
- Anon. (2026d). *Stichting Nationale Koolstofmarkt*. <https://nationaleco2markt.nl/>
- Anon. (2026e). *Woodland carbon code version 3.0*.
https://www.woodlandcarboncode.org.uk/sites/default/files/2026-01/Woodland_Carbon_Code_V3.0_Wit_h_Clarifications_Jan2026.pdf
- Arkema, E. (2024, November 11). *Dutch Government Launches Innovative Carbon Certificate Program for Farmers Growing Construction Crops*. Climate Cleanup.
<https://climatecleanup.org/dutch-government-launches-innovative-carbon-certificate-program-for-farmers-growing-construction-crops/>
- Battersby, F., Delerce, S., Dunand, A., & Selén, V. (2024). *Introducing an EU carbon removal pilot procurement programme*.
https://carbongap.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/Pilot_procurement_programme_updated.pdf
- Black, H., Cuba, D., Ebrahim, S., Leeson, A., Strong, A., Awad, A., Kremers, J., Horstmann, T., Kachelmeyer, J., Kane, D., Kellner, J., & Wadoux, A. (2026). *Draft soil sampling and analysis handbook*. Agricarbon.
https://verra.org/wp-content/uploads/2026/02/7_VM0042-SSAHandbook_draft_26FEB2026-1.pdf
- BMEL. (2024). *Strengthening Agriculture and Forestry to Combat the Climate Crisis*.
https://www.bmleh.de/SharedDocs/Downloads/EN/Publications/climate-crisis-strengthening-agriculture.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=3
- Bognar, J., Springer, K., Nesbit, M., Nadeu, E., Hiller, N., van Dijk, R., Lam, L., Forestier, O., Finesso, A., Bolscher, H., Jakob, M., Tarpey, J., McDonald, H., Zakkor, P., Heller, C., Tarpey, J., Görlach, B., Scheid,

- A., Tremblay, L.-L., ... Heller, C. (2023). *Pricing agricultural emissions and rewarding climate action in the agri-food value chain*.
- Breilean, I. (2025, December 1). *EU endorses Buyer's Club as financing strategy for CRCF credits*. S&P Global Energy.
<https://www.spglobal.com/energy/en/news-research/latest-news/energy-transition/120125-eu-endorses-buyers-club-as-financing-strategy-for-crcf-credits>
- Brennan, M. (2025). *Carbon farming*.
https://data.oireachtas.ie/ie/oireachtas/libraryResearch/2025/2025-04-03_carbon-farming_en.pdf
- Calvo Buendia, E., Tanabe, K., Kranjc, A., Baasansuren, J., Fukuda, M., Ngarize, S., Osako, A., Pyrozhenko, Y., Shermanau, P., & Federici, S. (2019). *2019 Refinement to the 2006 Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories V.4 Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use*. IPCC, Switzerland.
<https://www.ipcc-nggip.iges.or.jp/public/2019rf/vol4.html>
- Cames, M., Harthan, R. O., Füssler, J., Lazarus, M., Lee, C. M., Erickson, P., & Spalding-Fecher, R. (2016). *How additional is the clean development mechanism?*
https://climate.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2017-04/clean_dev_mechanism_en.pdf
- CAP Network. (2025). *Rough estimate of the climate change mitigation potential of the CAP Strategic Plans (EU-27) over the 2023-2027 period*. DG Agri.
- Carlsson, I. (2024, June 25). Denmark will be first to impose CO2 tax on farms, government says. *Reuters*.
<https://www.reuters.com/sustainability/denmark-will-be-first-impose-co2-tax-farms-government-says-2024-06-25/>
- Climate Change Authority. (2022). *Review of International Offsets*. Climate Change Authority.
- ClimateFarmDemo. (2026). *Climate Farm Demo*. <https://climatefarmdemo.eu/>
- CMW. (2012a, May 30). *Additionality & Baselines*. Carbon Market Watch.
<https://carbonmarketwatch.org/2012/05/30/additionality-and-baselines/>
- CMW. (2012b, May 30). *Forestry/Land-use projects in the CDM*. Carbon Market Watch.
<https://carbonmarketwatch.org/2012/05/30/forestry-projects/>
- COA. (2024). *Common Agricultural Policy Plans: greener, but not matching the EU's ambitions for the climate and the environment* (No. Special Report 20). European Court of Auditors.
https://www.eca.europa.eu/ECAPublications/SR-2024-20/SR-2024-20_EN.pdf
- Coderoni, S., Dell'Unto, D., & Cortignani, R. (2024). Curbing methane emissions from Italian cattle farms. An agro-economic modelling simulation of alternative policy tools. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 351(119880), 119880.
- ConsulenzaAgricola. (2023). *Registro dei crediti di carbonio al CREA: nuove opportunità reddituali in vista per il settore agroforestale*. consulenzaagricola.it.
<https://consulenzaagricola.it/circolari/varie/19231-registro-dei-crediti-di-carbonio-al-crea-nuove-opportunita-reddituali-in-vista-per-il-settore-agroforestale>
- CORDIS. (2026, January 13). *Enabling nature-based solutions in sustainable agriculture*. CORDIS | European Commission; Publication Office/CORDIS.
<https://cordis.europa.eu/article/id/461624-enabling-nature-based-solutions-in-sustainable-agriculture>
- DAFM. (2023). *Carbon Farming Framework for Ireland*. Gov.ie.
<https://gov.ie/en/department-of-agriculture-food-and-the-marine/consultations/carbon-farming-framework-for-ireland/>
- Desanker, P. V. (2005). *The Kyoto Protocol and the CDM in Africa: a good idea but* Fai.org.
<https://www.fao.org/4/a0413e/a0413E05.htm>
- de Wit, E., Kiewel, L., & Sacayan, D. (2023, July 7). *VCMI Claims Code of Practice*.
<https://www.nortonrosefulbright.com/en-419/knowledge/publications/a3ee21be/vcmi-claims-code-of-practice>
- DG-AGRI. (2026, January 26). *Europe's budget - Unlocking synergies integrating EU funding for farming and rural communities*. Publications Office of the EU; Publications Office of the European Union.
https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/20163519-fbf9-11f0-8da5-01aa75ed71a1/language-en?WT.mc_id=Searchresult&WT.ria_c=164596&WT.ria_f=9791&WT.ria_ev=search&WT.URL=https%3A%2F%2Fagriculture.ec.europa.eu%2F
- DG-CLIMA. (2026). *Carbon removals and carbon farming – methodologies for certifying carbon farming*. European Commission - Have Your Say.
https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/14574-Carbon-removals-and-carbon-farming-methodologies-for-certifying-carbon-farming_en
- DG-Environment. (2026). *Ensuring that polluters pay - toolkit*. DG Environment.
https://environment.ec.europa.eu/economy-and-finance/ensuring-polluters-pay_en
- Duault, M. (2025, May 16). *Low-carbon label: how does it work?* Tennaxia.
https://www.tennaxia.com/en/blog/label-bas-carbone-comment-fonctionne-t-il-et-a-quoi-sert-il?&_hstc=175113149.bd7219a4d2efb1074bac6d734da206d5.1745280000063.1745280000064.1745280000065.1&_hssc=175113149.1.1745280000066&_hsfp=1721781979

- EEA. (2024). *Greenhouse gas emissions from land use, land use change and forestry in Europe*. European Environment Agency.
<https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/indicators/greenhouse-gas-emissions-from-land>
- EESC. (2024). *A just transition to ensure a sustainable future for EU agri-food systems - EESC Opinion* (No. NAT/925-EESC-2024). European Economic and Social Committee.
<https://www.eesc.europa.eu/en/our-work/opinions-information-reports/opinions/just-transition-ensure-sustainable-future-eu-agri-food-systems>
- Enoki, T., Hayat, M., Grassi, G., Sanz, M., Rojas, Y., Federici, S., Seneviratne, S., Rupakheti, M., Howden, M., Sukumar, R., Fuglestedt, J., Itsoua Madzous, G., Krug, T., & Romanowskaya, A. (2024). *Report of the ipcc expert meeting on reconciling anthropogenic land use emissions*. Institute for Global Environmental Strategies.
https://www.ipcc-nggip.iges.or.jp/public/mtdocs/pdf/2407_EM_Land_Report.pdf
- ESABCC. (2026). *Climate adaptation and mitigation in the agri-food system*. European Scientific Advisory Board on Climate Change.
https://climate-advisory-board.europa.eu/reports-and-publications/2026-03-1120260311_eu-agri-food-system-report.pdf/@download/file
- Espinosa, P., Kerry, J., Matsuzawa, M. Y., & Brady, P. (2024, May 1). *Driving real-world climate action*. VCMI.
<https://vcmintegrity.org/>
- EURAF. (2025). *From Kyoto to Paris: A Historical Analysis and Synthesis of Lessons from CDM and REDD+ Forestry Initiatives in Africa*.
<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1OBm6rsOIjxvxXNkNhnZbKICvmz2VxsK-PWpTyZKghzs/edit?tab=t.0#heading=h.78wnp7zdrfd6>
- European Commission. (2016). *Commission Staff Working Document - Impact assessment accompanying the "LULUCF Regulation"* (No. COM(2016) 479 final). European Commission.
- European Commission. (2024). *Transition pathway for the agri-food industrial ecosystem*. Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs.
https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/publications/transition-pathway-agri-food-industrial-ecosystem_en
- Farmmaps. (2026). *Farmmaps*. <https://www.farmmaps.net/en/>
- Foster, E. J., Paustian, K., Taylor, P., Fitzgibbon, M., Porzig, L., & Carey, C. (2023). *The rangeland carbon monitoring program: Handbook of field methods v1.0*. Point Blue Conservation Science.
https://www.pointblue.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/FINAL_Range-C_Monitoring-Handbook_Feb2023_V1.0.docx.pdf
- Foucherot, C., & Bellassen, V. (2011). *Carbon Offset Projects in the Agricultural Sector*. *ResearchGate*.
<http://dx.doi.org/>
- Galinato, G. I., Olanie, A., Uchida, S., & Yoder, J. K. (2011). Long-term versus temporary certified emission reductions in forest carbon sequestration programs: Long-term certified emission reductions. *The Australian Journal of Agricultural and Resource Economics*, 55(4), 537–559.
- Gold Standard. (2024). *Methodology for afforestation/reforestation (A/R) - GHG Emission Reduction and Sequestration*.
https://globalgoals.goldstandard.org/standards/403_V2.1_LUF_AR-Methodology-GHGs-emission-reduction-and-Sequestration-Methodology.pdf
- Gold Standard. (2025). *Validation & Verification Bodies*. Gold Standard for the Global Goals.
<https://globalgoals.goldstandard.org/verification-validation-bodies/>
- Guidi, M., & Aubert, T. (2025, April 24). *How the EU Green Claims Directive can fix corporate climate claims and drive demand for high-quality carbon removal*. Carbon Gap.
<https://carbongap.org/how-the-eu-green-claims-directive-can-fix-corporate-climate-claims-and-drive-demand-for-high-quality-carbon-removal/>
- Hayes, D. J., Ferruolo, S., Haines, D., McEvoy, K., Neftalim, L., Roberds, L., Sachdeva, S., Scott-Buechler, C., Tsao, A., Vogelheim, K., Ward, B., Walker, C., & Zehr, B. (2023). *Measuring the Carbon (and Other) Benefits of Climate-Smart Forestry Practices*. Stanford Law School.
<https://law.stanford.edu/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/Measuring-the-Carbon-and-Other-Benefits-of-Climate-Smart-Forestry-Practices.pdf>
- Hendriks, C., Lesschen, J. P., Timmermans, B., Hanegraaf, M., Dijkman, W., Rougoor, C., Crujisen, J., & Schepens, J. (arch 2023). *Description and development Soil Carbon Tool*. WENR.
https://slimlandgebruik.nl/sites/default/files/2023-07/Handleiding_BodemCoolstof_ENG.pdf
- Hernández, M. R. (2024, July 4). *Does the EU need an Emissions Trading System for agriculture?* Carbon Market Watch.
<https://carbonmarketwatch.org/2024/07/04/does-the-eu-need-an-emissions-trading-system-for-agriculture/>
- Hurt, G. C., Ma, L., Lamb, R., Campbell, E., Dubayah, R. O., Hansen, M., Huang, C., Leslie-Bole, H., Lister, A., Lu, J., Panday, F. M. S., Shen, Q., Silva, C. E., & Tang, H. (2024). *Beyond MRV: combining remote*

- sensing and ecosystem modeling for geospatial monitoring and attribution of forest carbon fluxes over Maryland, USA. *Environmental Research Letters*, 19(12), 124058.
- ICROA. (2023a, February 24). *Accrediting Best Practice in Carbon Offsetting*. ICROA. <https://icroa.org/>
- ICROA. (2023b, March 6). *ICROA Code of Best Practice*. ICROA. <https://icroa.org/approval/icroa-code-of-best-practice/>
- ICROA. (2024, February 9). *Endorsed Crediting Programmes*. ICROA. <https://icroa.org/endorsed-organisations/>
- ICVCM. (2023, December 21). *ICVCM Leading the way to a high integrity Voluntary Carbon Market*. ICVCM; ICVCM New. <https://icvcm.org/>
- ICVCM. (2024a). *Core carbon principles, assessment framework and assessment procedure*. The Integrity Council for the Voluntary Carbon Market. <https://icvcm.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/CCP-Book-V3-FINAL-LowRes-10May24.pdf>
- ICVCM. (2024b, February 14). *How We Assess Carbon-Crediting Methodologies*. ICVCM; ICVCM New. <https://icvcm.org/how-we-assess-carbon-crediting-methodologies/>
- ICVCM. (2025, December 5). *Core Carbon Principles Impact Report 2025*. ICVCM; ICVCM New. <https://icvcm.org/engagement-impact/ccp-impact-report-2025/>
- IPCC. (2006). *2006 IPCC guidelines for national greenhouse gas inventories*. Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change.
- Jindal, R., Swallow, B., & Kerr, J. (2006). *Status of carbon sequestration projects in Africa: Potential benefits and challenges to scaling up* (No. WP 26). World Agroforestry Centre. <https://www.cifor-icraf.org/publications/downloads/Publications/PDFS/wp14441.pdf>
- Lavreckyte, V. (2024, June 6). *Carbon Offset Standards Comparison: Verra VCS vs. Gold Standard*. ECOHEDGE. <https://www.ecohedge.com/blog/carbon-offset-standards-comparison-verra-vcs-vs-gold-standard/>
- Lawson, G., Hahn, A., Huebner, R., & Kay, S. (2025). *Agroforestry and the EU Nature Restoration Regulation*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.14810873>
- Lawson, G., Kara, A., Kay, S., Vandendriessche, J., Smith, J., Gorenc, T., & Krajnc, U. (2025). *Agroforestry for carbon farming certification: how to demonstrate co-benefits for biodiversity and ecosystems?* (No. Policy Briefing 66 v1). European Agroforestry Federation. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.14937786>
- Lawson, G., Monteleone, D., Rocha, A., Dupraz, C., Hübner, R., & Torres Guerrero, C. A. (2025). *Initial approach to monitoring reporting and verification (MRV) of agroforestry carbon farming in the EU*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.16939713>
- Lawson, G., Muraru, C., & Kay, S. (2024). *Governance and performance of the CAP: the role of agroforestry* (No. Policy Briefing 69 v2). European Agroforestry Federation. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14000545>
- Lengyel, Z. (2025). *Why the EU "Buyers' Club" for carbon farming and engineered carbon dioxide removals CDR is structurally flawed and cannot work*. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/why-eu-buyers-club-carbon-farming-engineered-dioxide-removals-zsolt-bqtmf/>
- L'Hôte, A. (2022). *Label Bas Carbone and Carbon Agri method: a feedback from field*. https://ec.europa.eu/enrd/sites/default/files/05_tg2-carbonfarming_anais-lhote_label_bas_carbone.pdf
- Liao, H.-T., Pan, C.-L., & Zhang, Y. (2023). *Smart digital platforms for carbon neutral management and services: Business models based on ITU standards for green digital transformation*. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2023.1134381>
- Locatelli, B., & Pedroni, L. (2006). *Will simplified modalities and procedures make more small-scale forestry projects viable under the clean development mechanism? Mitigation and Adaptation Strategies for Global Change*, 11(3), 621–643.
- MAGRAMA. (2016). *The Spanish registry of carbon footprint, offsetting and CO2 removal*. https://www.miteco.gob.es/content/dam/miteco/es/cambio-climatico/publicaciones/publicaciones/spanish_registry_carbon_footprint_offsetting_co2_removal_tcm30-178352.pdf
- Mal, M. (2024). *Reducing emissions from agriculture*. European Environmental Bureau. https://eeb.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/Agri-ETS-Position-Paper.pdf?utm_source=chatgpt.com
- Mal, M. (2025). *An effective policy mix for scaling up carbon farming (Full report)*.
- Martel, S., Tronquet, C., & Grimault, J. (2026, January 21). *On Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming the devil is in...the demand*. I4CE. <https://www.i4ce.org/en/carbon-removals-carbon-farming-devil-demand-climate/>
- MASA. (2022). *Les méthodes agricoles du label bas-carbone*. Ministère de l'Agriculture et de la Souveraineté alimentaire. <https://agriculture.gouv.fr/les-methodes-agricoles-du-label-bas-carbone>
- MaterialDistrict. (2025, November 3). *Farmers Growing Building Materials Earn Millions in Carbon Credits*. <https://materialdistrict.com/article/farmers-growing-building-materials-earn-millions-in-carbon-credits/>
- Matthews, A. (2024, October 13). *What can we learn from the dismantling of GAEC 8?* <https://capreform.eu/what-can-we-learn-from-the-dismantling-of-gaec-8/>
- Matthews, A. J. (2023, July 9). *Carbon removal certification and carbon farming*. CAP Reform.

- <http://capreform.eu/carbon-removal-certification-and-carbon-farming/>
- McDonald, H., Gardiner, J., & Görlach, B. (2025, July 1). *An EU Purchasing Programme for Permanent Carbon Removals*. Ecologic Institute. <https://www.ecologic.eu/20152>
- McDonald, H., Murillo, J. P., & Scheid, A. (n.d.). *Report on options for standards to ensure environmental integrity and uptake*. Ecologic Institute. <https://www.ecologic.eu/sites/default/files/publication/2025/33020-Report-on-Options-for-Standards-to-E nsure-Environmental-Integrity-and-Uptake.pdf>
- McGlynn, E., Li, S., F. Berger, M., Amend, M., & L. Harper, K. (2022). Addressing uncertainty and bias in land use, land use change, and forestry greenhouse gas inventories. *Climatic Change*, 170(1-2). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-021-03254-2>
- Melo, J., Rossi, S., Achard, F., Alkama, R., Canadell, J. G., Federici, S., Friedlingstein, P., Gibbs, D., Harris, N., Heinrich, V., O'Sullivan, M., Peters, G. P., Pongratz, J., Rose, M., Roman-Cuesta, R., Sanz, M. J., Schwingshackl, C., Sitch, S., & Grassi, G. (2026). The LULUCF Data Hub: translating global land use emissions estimates into the national GHG inventory framework. In *Earth System Science Data Discussions* (pp. 1–55). <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-2025-631>
- Mulenga, F. (2017). *Implementation status of redd+, cdm, afolu/indc and voluntary carbon market related activities in anglophone africa* (No. 3). African Forest Forum. https://afforum.org/sites/default/files/AFF168_Final-English.-Implementation-status-of-REDD-AFOLU-IN DC_30092018.pdf
- MyClimate. (2024). *Small-Scale Farmers Reforest Forests in Uganda*. MyClimate. <https://www.myclimate.org/en/get-active/climate-protection-projects/detail-climate-protection-projects/ug anda-forestry-7181/>
- Ngwadla, X., Das, A., Sharma, S., Cartwright, A., Letete, T., Manzini, L., Semelane, S., Naidoo, C., Lehmann-Grube, P., Sheehama, A., & Meerholz, Y. (2024). *AFRICAN PERSPECTIVES OF A JUST TRANSITION TO LOW-CARBON ECONOMIES*. https://uneca.org/sites/default/files/ACPC/2024/African_perspectives_of_a_just_transition_to_Low_Carb on_economies.pdf
- Oerlemans, A. (2025, October 31). *Boeren die bouwmaterial voor huizen telen krijgen miljoenen betaald in carbon credits*. MT/Sprout. <https://mtsprout.nl/impact/nationaal-groenfonds-boeren-carbon-credits>
- Parker, G. (2022, February 6). *Q&A: How the Savanna Institute is Helping Agroforestry Thrive in the Midwest*. <https://www.eesi.org/articles/view/qa-how-the-savanna-institute-is-helping-agroforestry-thrive-in-the-mid west>
- Plan Vivo. (2025a). *Methodologies*. Plan Vivo Foundation. <https://www.planvivo.org/pv-climate-methodologies>
- Plan Vivo. (2025b). *PV Climate - Documentation - Version 5*. Plan Vivo Foundation. <https://www.planvivo.org/pv-climate-documentation>
- Proville, J., Parkhurst, R., Koller, S., Kroopf, S., Baker, J. S., & Salas, W. A. (2020). *Agricultural offset potential in the United States*. EDF. <https://www.edf.org/sites/default/files/content/Agricultural%20Offset%20Potential%20in%20the%20Unite d%20States.pdf>
- Ramboll Management Consulting. (2025). *Carbon Removals in the EU: Review of current carbon removal projects and early-stage financing*. Ramboll. <https://doi.org/10.2834/0004994>
- Ranevska, S. (2025, December 2). *EU Commission Announces New Steps Towards The CRCF Regulation*. Carbon Herald. <https://carbonherald.com/eu-commission-announces-new-steps-towards-the-crcf-regulation/>
- RioTinto. (2024). *What are carbon standards?* Riotinto.com. <https://www.riotinto.com/en/sustainability/climate-change/nature-solutions/what-are-carbon-standards>
- Schneider, L., & La Hoz Theuer, S. (2019). Environmental integrity of international carbon market mechanisms under the Paris Agreement. *Climate Policy*, 19(3), 386–400.
- Shishlov, I., & Bellassen, V. (2016). Review of the experience with monitoring uncertainty requirements in the Clean Development Mechanism. *Climate Policy*, 16(6), 703–731.
- Souli, S. (2025, November 20). *The Savanna Institute: Scaling Agroforestry to Transform the U.S. Midwest and Beyond*. Food Planet Prize. <https://foodplanetprize.org/initiatives/the-savanna-institute-scaling-agroforestry-to-transform-the-u-s-mid west-and-beyond/>
- Steffan, F. (2023). *Position paper on the “Label Bas-Carbon” and its methods for the agricultural Sector - Update* (No. v2). Climate Action Network France. https://reseauactionclimat.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/decryptage-n2-lbc_en-002.pdf
- Streck, C., Schuck, M., Hahn, G., Haupt, F., Sias, J. M., Pfannschmidt, J., & Mikolajczyk, S. (2025). *Negative Emissionen in Land- Und Forstwirtschaft - Ein Win-Win-Win für Klima, Natur und Wirtschaft*. Climate Focus & DVNE.

- https://climatefocus.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/Web_Negative-Emissionen-in-Land-und-Forstwirtschaft-Ein-Win-Win-Win-fur-Klima-Natur-und-Wirtschaft-v3.pdf
- SustainCERT. (2025). *VVB for Agricultural Land Management*. SustainCERT. <https://www.sustain-cert.com/news/sustaincert-s-expand-ghg-validation-and-verification-services-to-agricultural-land-management-alm-projects>
- Svarer, M., Cordtz, J. F., John, S., Kreiner, C. T., Sorensen, P. B., & Termansen, M. (2024). *Green tax reform*. Expert Group for Green Tax Reform. <https://skm.dk/media/tng1b4r/green-tax-reform-final-report.pdf>
- Teagasc. (2025, May 13). *Life Carbon Farming - Teagasc*. Teagasc | Agriculture and Food Development Authority. <https://teagasc.ie/environment/climate-change-air-quality/research/life-carbon-farming/>
- The Gold Standard Foundation. (2013). *The Gold Standard Afforestation/Reforestation (A/R) Requirements*. https://globalgoals.goldstandard.org/standards/PRE-GS4GG-AF/ar-requirements_v0-9.pdf
- Triple Performance. (2025). *Label Bas Carbone*. Triple Performance. https://wiki.tripleperformance.fr/wiki/Label_Bas_Carbone
- Trullenque, R. (2024). *The Carbon Credit Market in Spain › Legal Services Spain*. Mariscal Abogados. <https://www.mariscal-abogados.com/how-the-carbon-credit-market-works-in-spain/>
- UNFCCC. (2024). *Transition of CDM activities*. United Nations Climate Change. https://unfccc.int/process-and-meetings/the-paris-agreement/paris-agreement-crediting-mechanism/CDM_transition
- United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. (2013). *Afforestation and reforestation projects under the clean development mechanism: A reference manual*. UNFCCC.
- Vanderheyden, L., Gayot, N., & Van den Broeck, G. (2026). What monitoring, reporting & verification (MRV) systems can reduce costs and enhance scalability of carbon farming? *Journal of Environmental Management*, 401(128885), 128885.
- VCMI. (2024, October 30). *Carbon Integrity Claims*. VCMI. <https://vcmintegrity.org/carbon-integrity-claims/>
- Verra. (2026, February 11). *Verra Consults on Major Revision to Improved Agricultural Land Management Methodology (VM0042)*. Verra. <https://verra.org/verra-consults-on-major-revision-to-improved-agricultural-land-management-methodology-vm0042/>
- Vidal Morant, M., Eagle, A. J., van de Ven, G., Lavallee, J. M., Zahra, J., de Wit, A., & Hijbeek, R. (2025). Carbon farming in Europe, policies of symbolic reassurance. *Outlook on Agriculture*, 54(4), 336–345.
- Völler, P. (2023). *Can CBAM solve the EU ETS carbon leakages?-A Stakeholder Perspective*. <http://essay.utwente.nl/96225/>
- Volpi, G. (2025). *EU policy on carbon removals*. CDG Environment and Climate Change. <https://www.iscc-system.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/Update-on-EU-Policy-on-Carbon-Removals-%E2%80%93-Giulio-Volpi-Policy-Coordinator-DG-CLIMA-European-Commission-Belgium.pdf>
- Wavinya, A., & Getahun, E. (2021, July 12). *Building evidence of “permanence” and “leakage” for sustainable restoration*. World Agroforestry | Transforming Lives and Landscapes with Trees. <https://worldagroforestry.org/blog/2021/12/07/building-evidence-permanence-and-leakage-sustainable-estoration>
- WeAct Pty Ltd. (2022). *Review of international offsets: consultation paper*. Climate Change Authority. https://www.climatechangeauthority.gov.au/sites/default/files/30_weact.pdf
- Woolen, E., Berry, N., Cross, A., Hagdorn, M., Hughes, M., & Ryan, C. M. (2014, December 1). *Smallholder Agriculture Monitoring and Baseline Assessment (SHAMBA) tool, Version 1.0*. <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/67025>
- Yeates, J. (2024, December 14). *A new dawn for African carbon markets?* Carbon Markets Africa. <https://www.carbonmarketsafrica.com/news-and-media/a-new-dawn-for-african-carbon-markets>
- Yu, Z., Lu, C., Tian, H., & Canadell, J. G. (2019). Largely underestimated carbon emission from land use and land cover change in the conterminous United States. *Global Change Biology*, 25(11), 3741–3752.